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PROFESSIONAL MOTIVATION AND LIVED EXPERIENCES: A
DETERMINANT OF LECTURERS' JOB (DIS)SATISFACTION IN
NIGERIAN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

This thesis investigates why lecturers choose a teaching career as a professional motivation and their experiences working in public Nigerian universities in order to determine their sources of job (dis)satisfaction. This is a qualitative study and adopts a phenomenological method, within an interpretivist paradigm. It uses phenomenological interviews to gather data from twelve lecturers from two public universities in port Harcourt southern Nigeria and uses thematic analysis to analyse the data.

The emergent themes revealed that lecturers' predominant motivation for entering the teaching profession is to make an impact on students' life, while their experiences working in the public university sector involves sectoral challenges and flexibility. In terms of the sectoral challenges they experienced, four themes emerged as follows: salary issues, corruption, lack of development, poor working conditions, facilities, and environment. Whereas in terms of flexibility, two themes emerged: flexible employment and work flexibility. While their experiences working in the public university sector reveal that lecturers are highly dissatisfied due to the negativities of dealing with the sectoral challenges, they are on the other hand, derive satisfaction from impacting students' lives as a way of contributing to their success and the society which was their predominant motive for choosing a career in teaching.

The findings showed that expectations of lecturers advocate the government to ensure positive changes in public education by: (1) increasing funding, pay and pension, (2) government to support them for research and development, (3) improve work environment and conditions and (4) implement policies that will develop education. This study contributes to knowledge by extending the sources of job (dis)satisfaction of Nigerian lecturers and highlights possible experiences and sectoral challenges that potential lecturers and teachers may come across therefore give a foresight of their career expectations. It also fills a methodological gap in determining lecturers' job satisfaction within the Nigerian higher education literature therefore contributes to the studies of Egbule, (2003) and Umaru and Ombugus, (2017).

Chapter One

Introduction

Introduction

This is a phenomenological study that investigates lecturers' professional motivation and lived experiences to determine the sources of their job (dis)satisfaction. It fills a methodological gap in contextual literature by exploring the predominant reason why lecturers chose a teaching career, and their lived experiences working in the public university sector in Nigeria. The purpose is not to look at relationship between these phenomena but to determine whether they (career motivation and lived experiences) influence lectures' job satisfaction or dissatisfaction using a phenomenological method.

The first chapter of this study lays the foundation for the study to follow by providing a detailed background of the study, focusing on some of the most important and relevant information concerning the chosen topic. Following the background study, the central problem of the research will be stated in precise terms. Next, the purpose or aim behind conducting this research will be stated. The section that follows this will state the specific objectives which are to be accomplished by the end of the work. A set of fundamental questions which will be addressed in the process will be presented in the next section. After these, the value of the research work in terms of its expected contribution to knowledge will be explained. The penultimate section of the first chapter will talk about the overall significance of the whole effort of exploring the nuances of the chosen subject matter. Finally, the last section of this chapter will present the basic structure that would be followed though out the research, presenting an overview of each of them and stating their significance to the whole work as well.

Background

Job satisfaction is one of the most important expectations in every career. Job satisfaction in an organisation is of great significance, especially because it brings about employees' productivity and accomplishment (Holmberg, 2016). An organisation's success largely depends on whether its employees enjoy their job or not and feel that their efforts are rewarded. It is one of the drivers of performance both to individuals and organisations (Wambui, Ngari, and Waititu, 2016). Although there are various job satisfaction antecedents, the phenomenon remains a major concern to most organisations globally as well as individuals as lack of job satisfaction is still experienced (Weiler, 2016). A diverse range of factors has over the years reported to influence employees' satisfaction within their work environment, and these include established relationships between supervisors and co-workers, job security, fringe benefits, promotion opportunities, contentment with pay, working conditions or environment, fair practices, and policies. Other aspects include the organisational culture, nature and level of appreciation, sense of belonging and identifying with an organisation, type of leadership, new challenges in the work environment, nature of duties or work assigned to an employee, job flexibility, and the frequency of feedback among others (Holmberg, 2016). On the other hand, Job satisfaction can lead to (a) lower employee turnover, (b) higher productivity, (c) increased level of customer satisfaction, (d) reduced absenteeism among employees, (e) increased revenues in an organisation, and (f) enables employees to handle any emerging pressure because they are satisfied among other merits [Wambui et al., (2016), Tomazevic, Seljak, and Aristovnik, (2014)].

Over the past three decades, job satisfaction has been of interest to so many researchers. The growing intensity of research in this area can be accounted to so many important factors both to individuals and organizations. For instance, quite a lot of literature have shown that job satisfaction has a positive impact on organizational performance [Ouedraogo and Leclerc, 2013; Judge et al. 2001; Schleicher, Watt and Greguras, 2004; Bowling, 2007] and also leads

to employee's commitment [Samwel, 2018; Ramous Agyare, et al 2016; Kipkebut, 2010]. Following this reason, organizations are keen in ensuring that employees are satisfied with their jobs as they are considered one of their most valued assets and the primary source of competitive advantage (Mazurenko and O'Connor, 2012).

Several studies have researched job satisfaction and work-related factors such as pay, work conditions, leadership, workload etc across different sectors in developed countries, for example in Britain (Gazioglu, and Tansel,2006), The United States of America (Han, Trinkoff, and Gurses, 2015) and in mainland, China (Lu, While, and Barriball, 2007). In relation to developing countries within the context of education, Sahito, and Vaisanen, (2020) carried out a study to review academic staff's job satisfaction across education institutions in developing countries around the world. The study was carried out in 21 developing countries in Asia and Africa of which Nigeria was among. They found out that many of the factors relating to teachers' job satisfaction is lacking. For example, conducive working conditions, promotional opportunities, fair remuneration, support from head teachers, teacher empowerment, friendship were found to be the major factors affecting the job satisfaction of teachers whereas autocratic management style, non-transparent system, work-life imbalance, poor teaching and learning environment and unavailability of resources were found to be the main factors causing teachers' job dissatisfaction. Such factors were reported to have resulted not only in job dissatisfaction and low motivation to teach but also leads to low productivity and high turnover rate of lecturers.

While the study of Sahito, and Vaisanen, (2020) was generic across African borders, in the Nigerian context, academic staff job satisfaction has received quite a reasonable number of research both in primary, secondary, and tertiary level. As elsewhere, many factors have been found to affect teachers' motivation and job satisfaction in Nigeria including job context, job content and reward system (Adelabu, 2005). In regard to job context, Adelabu, (2005), provide that Public universities in Nigeria have a collection of dilapidated buildings, many without

basic academic facilities. The schools are staffed by tired and frustrated teachers and lecturers. such environment does not engender high job morale but rather leads to job dissatisfaction and low commitment. Secondly, regarding job content, teachers particularly in elementary schools are seriously overworked. A typical government teacher is required to teach between seven to eight periods each day to classes, which frequently have more than forty pupils. Teachers are also expected to assist with other school-based activities that are sometimes labour-intensive. Thirdly, the reward system in terms of pay package and promotion across all educational levels in Nigeria does not appear to have job motivation as its goal. It is rather one of the areas that suggest the most dissatisfaction among teachers and lecturers in Nigeria. (Adelabu, 2005)

Common Effects of Lecturers' Job Dissatisfaction in Nigeria

According to Watt et al. (2012, p.1), 'teaching is an occupation considered central to a country's development and well-being' therefore lecturers' satisfaction is an important part of educational quality and development. Despite this, Saint, Hartnett, and Strassner, (2003), provides that efforts to improve educational quality in Nigeria are severely constrained by growing shortages of qualified lecturers. They reported a massive decline in the number of academic staff by 12% even as students' enrolments expanded by 13% in the early 2000s. Long term brain drain has left the federal university system with only 48% of its estimated staffing needs filled. A later study by Victor and Babatunde, (2014) confirmed this providing that, qualified lecturers consistently migrate from Africa yearly looking for better working conditions and out of their number reveal that about 10,000 Nigerians are employed in universities only in the United States of America. Victor and Babatunde, (2014) strongly believe that lack of good working conditions coupled with no motivational mechanisms has predominantly led to the low morale among Nigerian lecturers while Staffing scarcity is most

acute across faculties till today. It is true that while academic staff are running away from the system for several reasons, the all-encompassing reason is that they are dissatisfied.

Also, according to Offem, Anashie, and Aniah, (2018), lecturers within the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) in Nigeria have gone on strike severally due to several reasons that are directly related to their job. This makes academic job dissatisfaction a continual and major area of concern especially in public higher institutions. On the other hand, Nwadiani, Akpotu and Ejiro, (2002) says Nigerian Universities are experiencing continual staff turnover because lecturers leave their pedagogical jobs to join other industries. Those that stay put are not there because the job is interesting to them but because they do not have any alternative job therefore, they devise means of getting what will bring motivation to them. Chief among their sources of motivation has been financial. Yusuf et al, (2010, p433) provide thus: ‘over the years, the relatively poor university salary structure caused some of the best candidates from the universities to drift to industries and the universities had no option than to recruit or incorporate less brilliant but qualified applicants at their disposal’. A common consequence is that many lecturers collect bribes from students in return for high grades because the pay they are offered is not enough to care for their needs and expectations. This does not only have to do with pay but a failed system that sees what is wrong and refuses to put it in place. Similarly, they work for decades without an equitable progression considered appropriate for their effort and years of service in the academia and at retirement do not have their pension paid (Yusuf et al, 2010).

Furthermore, from the provisions of Yusuf et al, (2010), the poor university salary structure is a direct factor of poor funding and this is seen as one of the primary source of job dissatisfaction in Nigerian education according to several literature including Famurewa, (2014) and Ekundayo and Ajayi, (2009). The issue of poor funding is evident in the less than ten per cent of the National Budget set-aside for education in Nigeria in 2017 up till 2020 since the administration of president Muhammadu Buhari. Many researchers see this to be below the

threshold recommended by the United Nations and by far lower compared to other neighbouring African countries like Ghana, Rwanda and south Africa respectively (Adewole, 2020). The apparent shortage of fund available to universities is responsible for the declining state of quality teaching and learning facilities, low lecturer's pay, and the Brain-drain syndrome i.e the widespread migration of academic staff from the universities in the country to overseas [(Issa and Adebola, (2014), Yetunde, (2018)]. Yetunde, (2018) also discovered some bedevilling problems that have persisted in the system apart from poor funding. She outlined poor governance, lack of responsibility and control, lack of infrastructure, and politicization of education. These have resulted in instability of academic staff in the education sector which can otherwise be explained as employee job dissatisfaction.

Overview of Challenges faced by University Education in Nigeria

The education sector is considered one of the most important assets for a nation as it shapes the quality of education for future generations and elevates the standard of economic and social wellbeing for a nation (Jacob and Lawan, 2020). Therefore, the standardization and constant improvement of education is an integral part of a country's development plan. Universities have been acknowledged as essential to the advancement of knowledge, financial system, and human resources across the globe. In addition, universities and colleges are increasingly regarded as capital and social resources creating enterprises however, numerous challenges often emerge in the education sector. Some of the specified challenges affecting lecturers and hindering Nigerian educational development are as follows:

Inadequate funding

Insufficient financing has been the biggest obstacle to achieving high-quality educational opportunities in Nigeria. Ekundayo, and Ajayi, (2009) researched into the effective management of university education in Nigeria and asserted that funding remains one of the biggest issues faced by Nigerian Education. The country's educational growth has been hampered by a lack of appropriate financing for education according to Atinmo and IsiakaAmusa, (2016). As a result, many Nigerian higher institutions are unable to meet up with the financial requirements needed to run the system effectively. This has led to poorly equipped laboratories and workshops, poor employees' salaries and other administrative expenses and poor work environment. Lack of funding even results in low salary provisions for lecturers which demotivates them and hampers their professional zeal.

Poor policy implementation

Nigerian educators and education face challenges because of ineffective policy implementation. Saint, Hartnett, and Strassner, (2003) investigated the status of educational policy implementation in Nigeria this include institutional autonomy, greater system differentiation, strengthened governance, and mechanisms for quality assurance. Their findings reveal that the policies that sort to promote university responsiveness in four areas such as access, teaching and learning, finance, and governance and management has not been effectively implemented. In practice, the university system developed less rationally than anticipated by its policies (Saint, Hartnett, and Strassner, 2003).

Lack of resources or infrastructures

In order to provide a quality higher education, institutions of higher education must have adequate people and material structures in place. The standard of teaching is affected by the lack of facilities such as laboratory equipment, workshops, student residences, conducive classrooms, bookstores, and proper infrastructures (Asiyai, 2013). Many of the nation's higher education institutions' libraries are filled with out-of-date textbooks, while contemporary periodicals and teaching materials are in short supply (Adewole, 2020). Also, Adebowale (2016, p. 332) observed that there are "...low levels of familiarity and utilisation on the part of lecturers and students of some of the technologies that can be used to facilitate teaching and learning. This also hinders lecturers' capacity to provide proper guidance to their students which is also a barrier for these lecturers to develop professionally. Subair, Okotoni and Adebakin, (2012) also submitted that the quality of infrastructure in selected Nigerian universities are adequate in providing a good learning environment that is essential for students' success.

Lack of information communication technology facilities

The absence of information and communication technology infrastructure in Nigeria's universities is another obstacle to excellence. It has been a great obstacle for the lecturers as they did not have the access to the technology which could have easily expanded their ability to share more relevant information and extend their support to the students to enhance their overall teaching and learning practice standards (Atinmo and IsiakaAmusa, 2016). Because information communication technology implementation in educational practices is intended to improve teaching and learning, augment higher education exploration, strengthen peer collaboration, and increase focus on improving the standard of education, the Nigerian

government implemented information communication technologies in all stages of education as part of the education reform endeavour yet research has revealed that there is lack of information technology development in Nigerian Universities. According to Adewole, (2020) ‘there are no improvements in teaching and learning, as teaching methods remain predominantly archaic’.

Frequent labour disputes and closures of universities (strike)

Staff union conflicts and consequent shutdown of universities pose a major obstacle to excellent higher education in Nigeria (Salau et al., 2020). Within fourteen years, there were too many protests and strikes by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Senior Staff Association of Nigerian Universities (SSANU), some of which went up to six months in duration. ASUU/FGN accords have not been implemented, there is no flexibility or academic independence, and financing is insufficient are some of the key reasons for conflicts according to some experts (Salauetal, 2020). Since lecturers find it difficult to finish coursework when learning processes are disrupted, the educational values of students are compromised. In order to compensate for the hours wasted during a strike, a semester's worth of course material is usually inserted between a few weeks of hurried lectures (Asiyai, 2013). Higher education in Nigeria is at risk due to this sort of academic haste.

Statement of problem and Gap in literature

As discussed earlier, one of the prevalent and generic problems faced by academic staff such as lecturers in Nigerian universities is job dissatisfaction. According to Akpan, (2013, p84), ‘The incessant strikes by academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) shows that all is not well with the university system in Nigeria. Lecturers are dissatisfied with the working

conditions, funding of universities, and their earned allowances'. It will not be uncommon to say that employee's assessment of the sources of their (dis)satisfaction is a complex summation of several discrete job elements and experiences irrespective of the context or country in question and which can also be assessed through several means and methods. Although many researchers for example, Egbule, (2003), Iornem, (2019) and Umaru and Ombugus, (2017), have researched on this subject to determine lecturers' job satisfaction in Nigerian universities however, while it could be said that their research has for a good reason, focused quite well on the determinants and sources of lecturers' job satisfaction, it is difficult to see such research that adequately adopt an open perspective to determining lecturer's satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In essence, what this means is that studies have not investigated lecturers' lived experiences as a method of determining the source(s) of their (dis)satisfaction within the Nigerian context. It is also lacking and uncommon to see lecturers job satisfaction literature that is relative to their professional motivation - a significant determinant of teaching career satisfaction according to Heinz (2013) and Watt et al, (2012).

Moreover, Egbule (2003) have used quantitative methods to predefine criteria in determining lecturers' satisfaction (including pay/salary, job security, achievement/recognition, opportunities for promotion, boss leadership style/attitude, physical work environment, staff development programmes, academic freedom, responsibility at work, supervision, university autonomy and interpersonal relations) while that of Umaru and Ombugus (2017) included regular salary payment, promotion opportunities, work environment, attainment of work goals, opportunity to growth and development. Neither of these studies and many others can be said to have captured participants' lived experiences in determining the sources of their (dis)satisfaction. This can be seen as a methodological gap in the job satisfaction literature within the Nigerian education context which this research intends to bridge using a phenomenological method that will examine participants' lived experiences. It has also resulted in an abundance of findings which cannot be directly synthesised.

To a significant level, research has proven that most academic staff in Nigerian universities work under bad conditions leading to dissatisfaction, lack of professional growth and eventual turnover respectively among other factors [Victor and Babatunde, (2014), Omonijo et al, (2015), Adelabu (2005), Nwadiani, Akpotu, and Ejiro, (2002), Ekundayo and Ajayi, (2009), Ologunde, Asaolu, and Elumilade, (2003), Egbule (2003)]. Other researchers like Akinbote (2009), also submitted that there is lack of teaching motivation among Nigerian teachers. Despite these studies, the pedagogical motivation and systemic experiences of lecturers working in the Nigerian public education sector is yet to be known as it lacks considerable research/method that give them an opportunity to unveil their entire career experiences (including those that cannot be captured by quantitative instruments) and to determine the source of their (dis)satisfaction in the best appropriate manner possible.

Why it is important to approach this subject differently is because it gives another perspective and insight into understanding and solving the issues of declining lecturers' satisfaction, high turnover, and educational development in Nigeria other than the traditional sources and methods commonly used. In essence, it is important to understand lecturers' (dis)satisfaction from these two perspectives:

1. Lecturer's lived experiences: Gives a vast and unrestricted investigative knowledge and understanding about the subject matter (which may not be covered by quantitative measuring instruments).
2. Their professional motivation (reason why they choose the career): Give information about their career goal as there is a positive relationship between achieving one's teaching career motive and job satisfaction (Heinz, 2013), This means that professional motivation can be used to determine job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In essence, if lecturers' career motive is met, then the possibility that they will derive satisfaction will be high and vice versa. According to Heinz, (2013), The reasons (altruistic, intrinsic, and extrinsic) that people give for deciding

to become a teacher are important considerations in identifying the sources of their job satisfaction. In this regard, ‘the motive that related most strongly to high career satisfaction included the altruistic-type motivations’ (Watt et al 2012 p.2)

It can therefore be deduced that if the factors affecting lecturers’ job (dis)satisfaction are duly and appropriately identified through their lived experiences, implementations on that regard can be made to effectively improve their job satisfaction and will also be a step to devising means for career and educational development in Nigeria.

Research purpose statement

The study’s main purpose is to investigate lecturers' professional motive and what they experience in Nigerian public universities in order to determine the sources of their job (dis)satisfaction. The study employs a phenomenological method to explore the personal stories and lived experiences of lecturers regarding their career in two Nigerian public universities through face-to-face interviews. Considering their predominant career motive and experiences, this study will determine whether the motive and experiences they encounter inform their satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Research Objectives

To meet the above research purpose statement. The objectives of this research are stated below:

1. To determine the pre-dominant teaching motivation of professional lecturers in Nigerian public Universities.
2. To find out what lecturers experience working within a Nigerian public university.
3. To determine whether lecturers’ professional motivation and experiences inform their job satisfaction

Research Questions

1. What is the predominant teaching motivation of professional lecturers in Nigerian public universities?
2. What are lecturers' experiences working within a Nigerian public university?
3. Does lecturers' professional motivation and experiences inform their job satisfaction?

Significance of the study

Other than contributing to knowledge, the study results will be important to various stakeholders, including the public universities' management, lecturers, university students, the government, academic researchers, and policy formulators in human resources management, in the following ways:

Nigerian Public Universities Management Teams: Management teams across various public universities in Nigeria will highly benefit from this research as they will be given suggested and actionable strategies that can promote lecturers' job satisfaction based on their career experiences and professional motive. Thus, this will be beneficial as the research is intended to give them an insight on the management of teaching staff in public universities.

Public Universities lecturers in Nigeria: As the main target of the study, lecturers in two Nigeria's public universities will directly be reached for the purpose of data collection. Thus, their obtained feedback will be of great relevance in making inferences. As such, I will ensure that the findings are published so that they can be accessed by the participants (lectures), who will greatly benefit by developing a clear and deeper understanding of how their professional motive and lived experiences influences their job satisfaction. In this regard, the lecturers will be able to identify strategies they can use at a personal level to increase their own job satisfaction, which is imperative to improving the quality of their lives and job motivation, respectively.

Students: Although not directly targeted, students will also be part of the study beneficiaries in two ways. First, they will develop an understanding of how experiencing the university work context and professional motive of lecturers influences their job satisfaction and this determines how they perceive the lecturing profession. Second, they will intellectually benefit from the literature and theoretical discussions in this study in understanding the concept of professional motive and job satisfaction in the education sector specifically in Nigeria.

Government and educational management authorities: The government of Nigeria and other educational authorities like the National University commission (NUC) will also benefit from this study as the findings will shed light on the experiences of the core university resource in the country. This will help identify possible problems and ways of improving teaching and learning development across the public education sector in the country.

Academic Researchers: Researchers will also benefit from the study as the conclusions will point out the specific limitations and research gaps recommended for further inquiries to help in contributing to knowledge creation.

Policy Formulators in the field of Human Resource Management: Policy formulators in the practice sector will also benefit from the study since the findings will provide insights on the changing trends in the field of HR management, particularly in the context of job satisfaction and career development in the education sector.

Study Structure

This thesis is presented in six chapters each of which have its own purpose and included details. The study begins with the introduction chapter, which is where the research questions are formed, and from where subsequent analysis and potential conclusions are drawn. In this section of the research, everything has to be put forth to scrutinize and challenge the facts

presented in subsequent chapters, to ensure that all are factual and based on the foundation of the study.

The literature review is the second chapter. It focuses on empirical literature or existing studies that people have researched on the subject matter. Under the literature review, a conceptual framework will be developed, and theories related to the subject will be reviewed to understand its relevance.

Chapter 3 describes and justifies the methodology for this study. As a phenomenological research study, the methodology chapter will focus on outlining qualitative methods as well as any research approach suitable for understanding people's experiences, while primary data is collected through interviews from lecturers within the selected universities. As knowledge regarding the experiences of lecturers and what influences their job satisfaction is gained, interpretations and analyses will be carried out in chapter 4 based on that information. This allows formulating a possible solution for any problems that lecturers face.

Chapter 5 presents the discussion and interpretation of findings. This outlines the outcome of the research and the author's primary contribution to what the findings entails. This chapter will explain all the aspects and conclusive arguments gathered in the study and relate them back to existing literature and/or theories. Chapter 6 is the conclusion where the contribution to knowledge and practice will be established. This chapter will also discuss the practical implications of my findings, outline the limitations of the study, reconceptualize a new framework and make a case for future research.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

Overview

The chapter presents a critical analysis of literature on the topic of the study based on different researchers and authors. Thus, the chapter will be split into three main sub-sections, namely: empirical review, theoretical review, and conceptual review, respectively. Through the critical assessment of past studies and theories on the topic, one will be able to understand the core elements of the research and gaps in the areas of research.

Overview of the Nigerian Context

The purpose of this section is to present the context about university education in Nigeria. It seeks to discuss its development from inception putting into consideration the political and economic contributions since the country's independence in 1960. This includes the history of Nigerian education, the development of university education before independence until the present day, the decline in Nigerian education resulting from economic programs example; the structural adjustment program (SAP).

Brief History of University Education in Nigeria

The historical development of Nigeria has played a vital role in its political, socio-cultural and economic spheres prior to independence until the present day. This has also contributed significantly to the development of higher education institutions within the country. Nigeria gained independence in 1960 from British colonial rule under whose tutelage Yaba collage - the very first tertiary institution in Nigeria was established in 1932 now called University of Ibadan. Having first been established in Lagos, the university was later

transferred to Ibadan in 1948 and was renamed University collage Ibadan and subsequently cut its affiliation to the University of London in 1962 (Ike, 1976). On October 7th, 1960, the University of Nigeria Nsuka was also established to commemorate the country's independence on October 1st and by the beginning of the republican government in 1963, there already existed 5 universities in the country. Based on available records from the National Universities Commission (NUC) website as at the time of this research, Nigeria currently has 170 registered universities of which 43 belong to the federal government, 48 to the various state governments and 79 private universities.

The Growth and Trend of University Education in Nigeria.

The process of developing the education sector has been an uneasy one in Nigeria just as the popular quote by Lao Tzu says: “A journey of a thousand miles begins with a single step” so it has been in this sector. In Nigeria, university education has developed through a gradual and progressive achievement (Fafunwa, 2018). It started with traditional education which was focused more on delivering basic child training by the then British colonial masters, then it proceeded to a formal education from where primary, secondary and tertiary education gradually emerged. In this section, only tertiary (university) education is discussed. Tertiary education is said to have developed or grown through four different generations as shown in the diagram below.

Figure 2. 1: University development in Nigeria

Source: Adopted from Gberevbie, (2006) and Adeyeye, (2009)

The above diagram shows the trend of university development in Nigeria since its inception under colonial rule. Presently, the government controls higher education in Nigeria which consists of Universities (public and private), polytechnics, and colleges of education. In 1962, the government of Nigeria established the National Universities Commission (NUC) as an advisory agency aim at promoting quality higher education in the country. Based on available record from the NUC website, Nigeria currently has 170 universities registered with the National Universities Commission (NUC); among which 43 are federal, 48 are state owned while 79 are private universities. These universities are classified under; first to fourth generation universities although, this classification is not noticeable or observable in real life situations.

The first-generation universities were established in the country between 1948 and 1965. These universities were established based on the recommendation of the Ashby Commission instituted by the then British Colonial Government to ascertain the necessity for university education in Nigeria (Omolewa, 2007). These universities were fully funded by the government being established chiefly to meet the need for qualified manpower in the country

and set a standard for the requirements of the establishment of a university. Accordingly, these universities served the purpose for which they were established by producing the needed manpower with the required skill set to drive the various industries to a desired state of existence. These universities include University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN), University of Lagos, Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria, and University of Ibadan (UI).

The second-generation universities were created to enhance university education and increase the level of literacy among Nigerians. These set of universities came into existence between 1970 and 1985 to meet the need of the increasing population of qualified secondary school students for university education in Nigeria, based on the growing need for scientific and technical developments in the country. Nevertheless, observing the trend of technical development in the country led to the establishment of third generation universities.

The third-generation universities were established to address the need for university education in specialized areas like agriculture and technology. These set of universities were established between 1985 and 1999. As time goes on, pressure from suitable candidates from each of the states in the federation who could not obtain university admission in federal universities compelled the government to give licenses to the various states to establish state universities. Subsequently, fourth generation universities were established. These comprise of private organizations and individuals who were allowed to establish fully licensed universities following a federal government law in 1993. This is what has given birth to all the private universities in Nigeria today. According to the NUC, these set of universities were established to address areas of felt needs in higher education. In terms of university programmes, there is a consolidated curriculum that runs throughout the system, from the first to fourth generation universities. It is typical that undergraduate programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria are designed based on established course of study and regulated curriculum for example, courses in the sciences are 4 years including courses in social and management sciences. Engineering,

law and technology related courses are 5 years, while courses in medicine and surgery (Human and Veterinary) are 6 years respectively (Adeyeye, 2009).

According to Thom-Otuya and Inko-Tariah, (2016), formal or non-formal education is considered an important factor for the advancement of any society. This is because the need for qualified personnel in the socio-political and economic development of any nation will hardly be achieved without a proper educational structure. For a nation to attain and sustain high economic growth, they are likely to have highly skilled workforce. Based on this submission, the level of education of individuals or citizens, or employee (in whatever context it applies) is essential because it determines the occupational position, tasks, and reward or compensation to be given at the end of the day. For instance, in multinational organizations, the educational degree and skill set of an individual at the entry level has a long way of determining their position and pay (Schultz and Schultz, 2010). Having a constantly developed tertiary education system is therefore a plus to every nation in general

Beginning of the Decline in Nigerian Education

Winston Churchill's quote: 'To improve is to change, to be perfect is to change often' reflects the quest by Nigerian government to improve the economy in the 1980s which gave rise to its structural adjustment program (SAP). Nigeria is known for depending on oil and gas as the source of its revenue and development. Following the first oil discovery in Nigeria in 1956, the economy was doing well within the first two decades after independence with just few declines in the mid-1960s however, from 1981 to 1987 the country experienced extensive economic decline (Nigeria Data Portal, 2018; Gerhart, 1996). Two decades after independence (1980), the government was still able to meet basic educational needs, for example subsidized tuition fees, accommodation, and meals. However, due to its economic turndown in 1981, the country could not lay hands on another immediate source of revenue as there was an oil crash

that led to a lasting financial instability. Other contributory factors also hindered the situation for example, poor fiscal policies, high-level corruption in government and uncompetitive trading policies.

In order to curb the nation's financial difficulties, Nigeria began the implementation of a change process by adopting the Structural Adjustment program (SAP) in 1986 having been a member of the Britton Wood institution (BWI), World Bank and the International monetary fund (IMF). Its aim was to reduce government expenditures in the public sector as a way of stimulating economic growth by restructuring the economic system and fostering private sector investment (Ahmed Hameed, 2016). During this process, there was privatization of public institutions and consolidated export policies in other to boost the economy through public sector reforms. The structural adjustment program (SAP) greatly impacted on most sectors of the economy in the process of reducing budgetary expenditure in Nigeria. According to Abah, and Naankiel, (2016), it contributed to the collapse of manufacturing and agricultural industries, increased unemployment and social insecurity as well as endangering education just to mention a few.

Major academic labour union and associations in Nigeria such as Academic Staff Unions of Universities (ASUU) and the National association of Nigerian students (NANS) resisted SAP policies as it led to loss of jobs with very high retrenchment of workers both academic and non-academic staff and also eliminated subsidy from non-instructional cost that were enjoyed by students and staff. Eventually, this unrest led to ASUU strike and severe university student demonstrations which interrupted academic activities across the country leading to educational instability. In addition, research by Babalola, Lungwangwa, and Adeyinka, (1999) showed a devastating effect of SAP on education including low purchasing power of teachers, low quality of education, low access to education, high gender gap in the provision of education at all levels, low students' performance rate and a decline in teacher's training (Babalola, Lungwangwa, and Adeyinka, 1999). There was 8% fall in the government

budget for education and a fall of 60% in public spending per student. This implies a drop in teachers' salary and a decline in the provision of adequate facilities that enhances a better learning environment. perhaps, in a country like Nigeria where lecturers are evidenced to be motivated mostly by extrinsic factors such as pay, this could have led to a downward trend in their overall job satisfaction and can in fact trace to why the education sector in Nigeria is destabilized till the present day.

The teaching profession

Professional motivation is one of the focal points of this research. Apparently, a profession is often used interchangeably with career. In the process of human daily living, individuals get involved in diverse sets of activities that give them a source of living and a sense of belonging. This in its simplest term can give rise to their career or profession. In other words, a profession can also be seen as a paid occupation, especially when it involves formal qualification or a prolonged training. According to Greenwood (1957), in his book "attributes of a profession", he defines a profession as 'an organized group which is constantly interacting with the society that forms its matrix, which performs its social functions through a network of formal and informal relationships, and which creates its own subculture requiring adjustments to it as a prerequisite for career success' (Greenwood, 1957, p65). As Greenwood rightly said, career success is one primary reason why people decide to choose a certain profession. There are numerous professions among which is teaching. Teaching is among those that requires high interpersonal relationships or communication and mentorship aimed at improving one's life. According to MacBeath, (2012, p3) 'Teaching is a profession that lies at the heart of both the learning of children and young people and their social, cultural and economic development. It is crucial to transmitting and implanting social values, such as democracy equality, tolerance, cultural understanding, and respect for each person's fundamental freedoms'. The teaching

profession is therefore very important as they are the central contributor to economic development of a nation as provided by Akinbote, (2009, p69) who says that ‘no system of education can rise above the quality of its teachers. This implies that the teacher is the most important manpower needed to develop other manpower in any society’.

Teacher’s Professional Motivation

McGrail et al, (2010) provides that professional satisfaction is the extent to which a workplace matches with what a worker aspires to become or expects. The motivations and attributes of potential teachers during their preparation process for the profession is widely seen to substantially influence the development of students as well as their own fulfilment when they eventually become teachers (Aksu et al, 2010). In this regard, seeing a teacher as someone who needs to be equipped as a “knowledge base” of the profession is now believed to be invalid, they are rather now seen as intellectual agents who “remains forever rooted in personality and experience” (Heinz, 2015). Despite being individualistic, people can also have a common motivation especially when they are in the same profession or due to personality type or other factors.

Many studies have been conducted with regards to what motivate teaching professionals to choose the profession. For example, Bruinsma and Jansen, (2010), Akar, (2012), Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014), Balyer, and Ozcan, (2014), Heinz, (2013), Tomsik, (2016), Priyadharshini, and Robinson-Pant, (2003), Richardson and Watt, (2016). With these studies, there is a wide scope of career motives for teachers across the world. According to Glymour et al., (2004), teaching motivation is often determined by demographic factors such as race and gender while Filonenko, Mosienko, and Magranov (2020) argued that personal development is considered one of the strongest factors for career motivation in recent times. In spite of these submissions, numerous studies have also been carried out within Europe for

example, Heinz, (2013), Heinz (2015), Anghel (2020) and Moran et al, (2001) to examine the reason why people choose to train in a teaching career. A predominant response in this regard revealed that their motivation falls under three basic categories of reasons which are intrinsic, extrinsic, and altruistic as shown in fig 2.2.

Figure 2. 2: Factors of motivation for teaching career

Source: Adopted from Moran et al, 2001

According to Moran et al, (2001), The intrinsic reasons include specific aspects of teaching career such as the activities it involves, the passion to use one’s own scientific training to train others, the quest towards self-development and the intention to work in a school environment. Secondly, the extrinsic reasons cover aspects of the teaching profession that are somewhat indirectly related to the basic professional activities. This includes factors like job security, payment or salary and the programme teachers go through. Lastly, the altruistic reasons involve the pleasure they gain working with students and their passion to impact or contribute to the progress of student’s life. Significantly, one of the most recent study by Anghel, (2020), explains five “most” and “least” reasons why young people choose teaching as a profession in table 2.1.

S/N	Most Reasons	Least Reasons
1	Teaching gives me an opportunity to help students gain a sense of achievement and self-worth	It is less expensive to prepare to teach than to prepare for any other fields
2	It is an intellectually stimulating occupation	I was told about a scholarship or tuition reimbursement program available to persons entering teacher education programmers
3	I would like to work with young people.	Teaching is a tradition in my family.
4	I have a desire to impart knowledge to other people.	I trained for another field but could not get a job.
5	Teaching gives me a chance to serve as a positive role model for children.	I trained for another field but did not feel comfortable in that field.

Table 2. 1: Most and least reasons for choosing teaching career. Source: Anghel, (2020).

Since the 1950s, similar motivations for selecting teaching as a career have sufficed in varied forms, and rankings (Anghel, 2020). Studies conducted up until the early 2000's found that “altruistic, service-oriented reasons and other intrinsic motive are the source of the key reasons new teacher candidates give for why they chose teaching as a career” (Watt et al, 2012, p.2). in general, the most important sets of reasons influencing teachers' career choices, according to these studies, are intrinsic, extrinsic, and altruistic incentives. Working with children and adolescents, making a social contribution, making an impact, job security, job benefits, enjoyment of teaching, compatibility with family life, and self-education have all been identified as motives (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2005). In terms of being specific to context, the most frequently cited reasons for choosing teaching as a career in France, Australia, Belgium (French Community), Canada (Québec), the Netherlands, the Slovak Republic, and the United Kingdom are a desire to work with children

and adolescents, the potential for intellectual fulfilment, and a way to make a social contribution which all identify with altruistic-intrinsic motive. Extrinsic factors, such as money, work security, and career status, were found to be more relevant in research conducted in very different sociocultural contexts such as Brunei, Zimbabwe and Jamaica (Watt et al 2012).

Considering the various scholarly research done on teaching professional motivation, the below table shows some of the authors, topic for research and their proposed motivation correlates for peoples' choice of a teaching career:

S/N	Year	Context	Topic	Author(S)	Career Motivation Correlates
1	2020	Education	Defining Mid-Level Career Motivation and Primary Work Responsibilities in International Higher Education.	Pal, McNaughtan, and García, (2020)	Calling, career and Job
2	2020	Education	Choosing the teaching career by students in the arts.	Anghel, (2020),	Intrinsic, extrinsic and altruistic factors.
3	2015	Education	Why Choose Teaching? An International Review of Empirical Studies Exploring Student Teachers' Career Motivations and Levels of Commitment to Teaching, Educational Research and Evaluation	Heinz (2015),	Intrinsic, extrinsic and altruistic factors
4	2014	Education	Choosing Teaching Profession as a Career: Students' Reasons. International Education Studies, 7(5), pp.104-115.	Balyer and Özcan, (2014).	Intrinsic, extrinsic and altruistic factors
5	2014	Education	Teaching motivations in Hong Kong: Who will choose teaching as a fallback career in a stringent job market? Teaching and teacher education, 41, pp.81-91.	Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014).	Intrinsic, extrinsic and altruistic factors
6	2012	Education	Motivations of Turkish Pre-Service Teachers to Choose Teaching as a Career.	Akar, (2012)	social and personal utility value and prior teaching and learning experience
7	2010	Education	Is the motivation to become a teacher related to pre-service teachers' intentions to remain in the profession?	Bruinsma, and Jansen, (2010)	Adaptive and Maladaptive motivation
8	2001	Education	Training to teach: Motivating factors and implications for recruitment.	Moran et al, (2001)	Intrinsic and extrinsic
9	1990	General context	An investigation of the correlates of career motivation.	Noe, Noe, and Bachhuber, (1990)	Managerial support, career stage, distance from career goal, match between individual and organizational career goals
10	1987	Education	Teachers and their careers: Why do they choose teaching?	DeLong, (1987)	Security, technical/functional competence, managerial competence, creativity, autonomy, Identity, service and variety
11	1983	General context	Toward a theory of career motivation.	London (1983)	Career identity, career insight, and career resilience

Table 2. 2: List of literatures concerning professional motivation

According to Watt et al (2012), many countries recognise that teacher demand and supply are recurrent, yet there is a scarcity of systematically collected and analysed data on what inspires people to pursue teaching as a vocation. The majority of teacher motivation research has been conducted in the United States in the 1990's, with more of the studies employing a qualitative component (e.g., Alexander, Chant, & Cox, 1994; Bastick, 1999; Hanushek & Pace, 1995; Jantzen, 1981; Joseph & Green, 1986), even though the analytical methods and interpretation of results have not always been as sophisticated as they could have been; Single item indicators, raw frequency counts, and the ranking of themes are widely used, resulting in inconsistency among studies (e.g., Alexander, Chant, & Cox, 1994; Bastick, 1999). Researchers have always not agreed on what constitutes intrinsic, altruistic, extrinsic, or other motivations explored by individual researchers due to the lack of a consistent analytical and theoretical framework (Watt et al 2012). The lack of definitional accuracy and overlapping categorisations amongst studies has emerged from various operationalizations of intrinsic, extrinsic, and altruistic motivations. For example, the desire to work with children has been identified as a kind of intrinsic drive by Young, (1995) as well as a form of altruistic motivation by Anghel, (2020). This leads to the conceptualization of the Fit-choice scale. a model that spans through a range of motives and employ some underlying psychological processes which is used to investigate reasons for becoming a teacher (Watt et al 2012).

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction has been an important factor for employees' and organizational performance. In defining job satisfaction, the reference is often made to Locke's description of job satisfaction as a 'pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences' (Locke 1976 p1304). The appraisal for job satisfaction involves various elements related to the job such as salary, working conditions, colleagues and boss, career prospects and the job itself. It is viewed to emerge from a combination of factors including characteristics of the organizational environment, specific features of the job and the personal characteristics of the workers. Job satisfaction is the contentment of employees with their jobs which implies enthusiasm and happiness with one's work. It is the key ingredient that leads to the achievement of other goals and to a feeling of fulfilment (Kaliski, 2007). According to Statt (2004), job satisfaction can be defined as the extent to which a worker is content with the rewards he or she gets out of his or her job, especially in terms of intrinsic motivation. This implies that financial benefit is as important as any other aspect of a job.

Jason et al (2011) see job satisfaction as the achievement of one's job values in a work situation, which results in a pleasurable emotional state. This definition is an extension to that of Locke (1976) and in other words means that how you feel about your personal values compared to that of the organization where you work determine whether you are satisfied or not. No doubt employees with high job satisfaction experience positive feelings when they put their jobs into consideration while those with low job satisfaction experience negative feelings when they think about their jobs (Armstrong, 2006).

Furthermore, Cranny, Smith and Stone (2014) defined job satisfaction as staff's state of feeling regarding the work, considering what they wanted and what they really received out of it. Yet Agho, Mueller and Price (1993) also explained job satisfaction as the range to which employees are comfortable with their jobs. According to Khalid and Irshad, (2011), five component that shows that an employee is satisfied are: wages; position advancement; pay and

honour. Job satisfaction is a vital ingredient that leads to proper attention, compensation, promotion, and the realization of other goals that gives the employee a feeling of fulfilment (Kaliski,2007). Also, Robbins (2005) explained that an employee feels emotionally good and satisfied after doing the job. Here, positive emotion appears as an outcome of fulfilled psychological needs (Aziri, 2008). It is more of an attitude and internal state of mind (Mullins, 2005) and further implies enthusiasm and happiness with one's work (Brikend, 2011). Arnett, Laverie and McLane's (2002) all agreed that job satisfaction is shown as a worker's general emotional evaluation of themselves in the context of their work duties. Smith, Kendall and Hulin (2007) defined job satisfaction as feelings or affective responses to facets of the job situation while according to Colquit, Lepine and Wesson (2013), job satisfaction is explained as the enjoyable feeling of state arising from the assessment of employee's work rate. It is a phenomenon that transcends the borders of the Organization or firm, and impact individual life outside the Organization (Robbins, 2005).

Job satisfaction Within the African higher education context

Job satisfaction is not a new area of research. There has been wealth of studies conducted on this subject in different universities across the world, for example, Schulz, (2013) was carried out in UK universities, Malik, Danish, and Munir, (2012) in Pakistan, Liu, and Onwuegbuzie, (2014) in China, among many others. Within the African context, Makondo (2014) established that in South African universities, job satisfaction and retention of academic staff is affected by factors such as professional support, promotion, remuneration, and teaching load. This study suggested that proactive strategies are required by these Universities to keep attracting and retain quality lecturers to enhance their strategic positioning. Whereas in the case of Zimbabwe, one of the prominent factors that has affected academic job satisfaction is leadership style. The quality of leadership has been found to determine how the talents,

potential, and commitment of academics are optimized for the benefit of the workplace. Kuslivan (2003), has opined that leadership and turnover intentions are inextricably linked and in Zimbabwe, incompetent leadership resulted in poor lecturers' performance, high stress, low job commitment, little job satisfaction, and turnover intent (Gwavuya 2011). Gwavuya (2011) examined leadership and job satisfaction influences on turnover intent of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. His participants were 100 lecturers randomly selected from different departments in three State Universities. Gwavuya's (2011) findings revealed that lecturers who were satisfied with their chairman/dean had stay-intentions while those who were not happy with their chairman/dean had turnover intent. However, the respondents indicated that they were reasonably satisfied with most aspects of their work life as aspects like benefits, work ethics, and the job itself, result in a positive effect on job satisfaction. On the contrary, the result of this study shows that authoritarian or autocratic leadership style is dominant within the Zimbabwean education system. This exists in form of centralized power, authority, and decision making. An implication of this is that Zimbabwean university leaders and management dictates decisions down to the subordinates, and few opportunities are given to lecturers for making suggestions even if these are in the institution's best interest. Following from the study of Gwavuya's (2011), lack of involvement of lecturers in vital decision making can be said to reflect a leadership environment that is void of active participation which negatively impacts on their motivation to teach as well as indirectly affects their job satisfaction. One of the problems this poses is poor relationship of lecturers with the university authority which is an indicator of mistrust, breeding contempt and negativity, which, eventually undermines motivation and loyalty. Interestingly, Tetey (2006) whose research cut across African universities posits that consultation from and participation by academics in decision-making allow them to feel part of the university institution and give them a sense of ownership in the outcomes of those decisions. In essence, Employees are more likely to be motivated and remain with an organisation if they believe that their leaders show interest in them, give them

a chance to contribute and receive regular positive feedback and recognition. However, Gwavuya's (2011) claims that there is not enough time to get every employee's input therefore suggests that management to improve co-lecturer attitudes through team-building exercises and active involvement in order to reduce turnover intentions and increase job satisfaction.

Regarding Universities in Ghana, evidence from Appiah-Agyekum, Suapim, and Peparah, (2013) shows that job satisfaction among teachers remains a critical condition for the thriving of education in Ghana. One of its pinpoints remains that lecturer's retention is problematic especially as provisions that enhances their satisfaction are neglected. In this case, they look for other backup lecturing jobs in other institutions that would provide tools and materials for teaching, socio-economic resources and other accoutrements needed for effective teaching and learning. In as much as this may be a strategy to combat dissatisfaction of lecturers, on the other hand it also reflects the possibility of lack of commitment and stay intention. This is a major factor that leads to lecturers' job dissatisfaction in the Ghanaian context. Amos et al, (2015) revealed that lecturer's commitments to their teaching occupation was found to be a poor predictor of job satisfaction even though it was seen to have a positive correlation in other studies. Arguably, lack of lecturers' commitment in this instance can be seen as a greater threat when it leads them outside their original career path such that their interest in the teaching career is completely compromised. This is not to say that absence of employees' commitment cannot lead to negative work behaviours within their job or be attributed to other factors like gender and personal dispositions which eventually affects their satisfaction. In fact, the study of Amos et al, (2015) considered gender as a determining factor of Ghanaian lecturer's commitment however, found no significant relationship between sex differences of lecturers and their commitment level neither was there job satisfaction differences using respondents' sex variable (male and female). On the contrary, Egbule, (2003), revealed that the level of job satisfaction of lecturers was significantly influenced by their sex and university status among other factors. Likewise Machado, White and Gouveia, (2014) who

found that male respondents in Higher education institutions were in higher positions than women, making women lecturers less satisfied with their professional life and especially when there is no balance between their work and family life. Although the context of these studies are different likewise the methodologies used. However, Irrespective of their findings, there is a fact that the more lecturers are committed to their jobs the more satisfied they are therefore more effort is needed towards ensuring that lecturers are committed to teaching and research however not neglecting good relationship with colleagues and students as well as the work environment which will all result in improved performance in the university's development.

In the context of Nigeria, Egbule (2003) investigated factors relating to job satisfaction of lecturing staff in Nigerian universities. 1142 academic staff from the three categories of universities were sampled. A questionnaire, validated and tested for reliability, was used for data collection. Simple percentage, mean, t-test, and F ratio (ANOVA) were used for data analysis. The researcher found that the level of job satisfaction of the lecturers had generally increased over the past five years and that lecturers in federal universities had a higher mean of 40 job satisfaction score than those in state and private universities. The level of job satisfaction of the lecturers was significantly influenced by their sex and university status among other factors. (Egbule, 2003). Also, Umaru and Ombugus, (2017) assessed the level of job satisfaction among lecturers in a Nigerian University, and found that regular salary payment, promotion opportunities, work environment, attainment of work goals, opportunity to growth and development among others are the determinants of job satisfaction of the university lecturers. The significance of these studies are that while there are differing factors that contribute to the satisfaction and dissatisfaction of lecturers, the University work environment appear to be a constant factor of dissatisfaction irrespective of whether it is in the public or private sector. They both emphasized on the importance of financial obligations to provide a better work environment that will enhance adequate facilities for learning and development.

Furthermore, in determining the factors that impact on lecturer's job satisfaction, work stress was considered by Osibanjo et al (2016) in a Nigerian Public University sector. The survey method was deployed in sampling 170 staff members of the University. The results of the analyses recognized that stress factors such as equitable workload and role congruence have a significant influence on organisational performance through moderating variables such as employee job satisfaction and engagement. The result indicate that workplace stress influences the performance of academic staff and in turn affect their level of satisfaction on the job. The examination of this study made it imperative for organisations to invest necessary resources in developing strategies and interventions to reduce workplace stress. One of the means is through adequate staffing. If this is achieved, there will be endless opportunities in terms of increased performance, minimal stress, job satisfaction, and overall sustainability some of which are non-existent in public higher institutions. In spite of this, attracting adequate and qualified candidates may be a challenge in the face of changing career preferences and environment.

Leadership is another concern in the study of Ejimofor, (2007) in the case of Nigeria. Transformational leadership was found to have both direct and indirect relationship with job satisfaction among Nigerian academics. If Nigeria wants to join the comity of nations in all ramifications, then she must address the issue of leadership of the institutions and set out proactive policies especially in government owned higher institutions which are worse hit by bad leadership (Ejimofor, 2007). Leadership must inhibit good behaviour applied by the head of departments (HODs) and faculty deans as well as institutional management and other academic regulatory bodies to motivate the staff in ways to achieve objectives of the institution. Leadership is very important in higher institution because the behaviour of the leaders is supposed to be a catalyst in directing the followers to achieve the common goals; hence followers follow the leader's behaviour when carrying out their duties. From the above statement on leadership, it is obvious that leadership plays a key role in organisational commitment of employees as well as their job satisfaction.

Bola (2012), in his study, found a relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment. He hypothesized that there was a significant difference in the degree of organisational commitment of employees in public and private universities in Nigeria. Data were collected from 150 employees consisting of academic, administrative, and technical staff from both the public and private universities. The study revealed that employees in public universities had a higher degree of organisational commitment in comparison to those in private universities and that job satisfaction increased or decreased based on the increase or decrease in organisational commitment. In terms of organisational commitment, a significant difference was noticed between public and private universities. Against expectation, employees of public universities exhibited a higher degree of organisational commitment as compared to those of private universities (Bola, 2012). In sum, the study identified organisational commitment as an indicator of academic staff's job satisfaction (Bola, 2012).

A study by Ezirim, Nwibere, and Emecheta, (2010) examined the theoretical underpinning of job satisfaction among civil servants of which lecturers were also selected as participants. The study was carried out to test if Herzberg's et al. (1959) theory could be applied in the Nigerian situation. The factors studied include fringe benefits, favourable working conditions, favourable organisation policies, an increase in pay, good interpersonal relationship, job security, regular payment of salary, and status. The result indicated that these factors were good motivator for desirable performance and increases job satisfaction. Apparently, this slightly disproves Herzberg et al. (1959) two-factor theory that hygiene factors cannot improve job satisfaction and motivation. Ezirim, Nwibere, and Emecheta, (2010) explained that managers interested in job satisfaction tend to centre their effort on employees' performance.

Overall, job satisfaction in Nigeria and that of neighbouring African countries cannot be over emphasized. The Nigerian studies shows that although the factors responsible for job satisfaction are similar to those found globally however academic staff in Africa generally are

found to be dissatisfied mostly with factors like their salary, leadership and work environment. With satisfaction regarding pay, it can be observed that this is more predominant in Nigeria compared to other African countries like Ghana, Kenya, and Zimbabwe because of the issues about lack of adequate funding. For example, Arikewuyo, (2009, p17), reported that unlike Nigeria which spends an average of 1.1% of its GDP/GNP on education, Ghana spend 3.6%, Kenya spend 6.2%, and Zimbabwe spend 9.5%. It can be said that employee's assessment of how satisfied or dissatisfied they are with their work is a complex summation of several discrete job elements irrespective of the context or country in question. Also, what motivates an employee's job satisfaction and attitude to work, in general, differs from one person to another, one organisation to another and from one country to another. Understanding these dynamics is key to the success of any organisation in our constantly changing environment. Maier (1973) had shown that many of the job satisfaction items vary in importance depending upon the condition under which the employees are working. It is apparent that having a satisfied workforce within the academia therefore adds a lot of benefits to the institutions and lead to higher productivity and educational development (Issa and Adebola, 2014).

Job satisfaction determinants

Considering the numerous literatures on job satisfaction reviewed under this study, one thing that stands out is the fact that the contributing factors to job satisfaction can be categorized under three main categories. This ranges from individual attributes to work context to characteristics of the institution or environment where the work is carried out (Pichler and Wallace, 2009, Bozeman and Gaughan, 2011, Bilimoria et al, 2006). Agho, Mueller, and Price, (1993) found that the degree to which employees like their job is influenced by a combination of characteristics of the environment (opportunity), the job (routinization and distributive justice), and personality variables (positive affectivity and work motivation). For example,

from the study of Adelabu, (2005), the basic determinants he listed for job satisfaction in Nigerian public universities include remuneration, career advancement, vocational intent, teaching competence and working conditions. While vocational intent can be identified as an individual disposition, other factors like working condition and remuneration can be grouped under institutional characteristics. Therefore, in this regard, following the numerous literatures on this subject, Individual attributes may include gender, race, marriage, age, field and culture. On the other hand, the work context may include factors like organizational objectives and work composition, while institutional characteristics may include the industry, the country, leadership and management style, policies and procedures, wage levels and unionization.

Figure 2.3 shows the three key factors that influences employee’s job satisfaction in this regard.

Figure 2. 3: Key factors influencing employee’s satisfaction

Source: Adopted from Pichler and Wallace, (2009), Bozeman and Gaughan, (2011)

Individual Attribute or Disposition to Job satisfaction

The dispositional viewpoint assumes that measuring personal characteristics can aid in the prediction of job satisfaction (Anyango, Ojera and Ochieng, 2013, Furnham, Eracleous, and Chamorro-Premuzic, 2009). One reason for the dispositional/individual influence to job satisfaction comes from an individual's genetic makeup. Arvey, et al, (1989) found support for a genetic component to job satisfaction in their study of monozygotic, or identical, twins reared apart. They found that even when they were not raised together, identical twins tend to have job satisfaction levels that were significantly correlated. Because identical twins have the same genetic makeup but are reared apart and as such do not have the same environmental influences, this similarity in job satisfaction ratings is argued to represent a genetic component. Another study that has supported the dispositional nature of job satisfaction found a strong and consistent relationship in attitudes over time as well as a relationship in attitudes across different situations or settings (Staw and Cohen-Charash, 2005). The dispositional approach of job satisfaction is not a mirage as Staw and Cohen-Charash (2005) affirms that individual dispositions do indeed affect job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can therefore be seen in this regard as a function of employee's personality (Furnham, Eracleous, and Chamorro-Premuzic, 2009).

Institutional Characteristics and Job Satisfaction

In explaining job satisfaction or measuring the level of employee satisfaction, this determinant turns its attention to the characteristics of the organization within which the job is done. With this key factor, Pichler and Wallace, (2009) consider institutional factors like wage levels, unionization within the organization and the level of inequality or status differential that exist between worker and their managers or leaders. Institutional characteristics also extend to working conditions which can be subject to improvement by trade union influence in some

countries as compared to others. Provision of welfare packages and a range of benefits which is unique to every organization are likely to impact on work attitude and affect job satisfaction. Such welfare packages can lead employees to be more or less with their jobs as a result of general economic climate. Furthermore, leadership style and behaviour is another factor that is unique to specific organizations. A study by Bilimoria et al, (2006) reveal that employee's satisfaction is positively influenced by their institutional leadership style. Leadership researchers like Bartolo and Furlonger, (2000) also provides that employee's job satisfaction is susceptible to the influence of leadership behaviours in the workplace.

Work context and Job Satisfaction

This suggests that the measurement of the level of job satisfaction is founded on how workers evaluate the workplace and their work responsibilities. The work context put into consideration factors like the conditions under which the job is carried out and what the job itself entails. It ensures that there is congruence between the common goals or expectations of employees and the responsibilities they are assigned to do. This helps to reduce conflict of interest which may affect job satisfaction. It also entails how specific organizational goals are to avoid ambiguity in operation and also procedural constraints (Wright and Davis, 2003). It shifts its attention to the effects of the context surrounding job and also the job content and the consequences of employee's behaviour, rather than to individual pre-dispositions and rational decision-making processes. This approach has to do with individuals evaluating their job circumstances (Salancik and Pfeffer 2008).

Other Antecedents to Job Satisfaction

Bolag (2004) posit that some of the factors of job satisfaction example pay are however emphasized by researchers more than others. Irrespective of the different categories under which job satisfaction determinants are placed, most researchers do not follow this trend but rather consider factors that seem to be most common from their findings and other literature. The following section reviews literature on some of the common organizational determinants of academic staff's job satisfaction or dissatisfaction irrespective of the category they fall under (whether work context or institutional).

a) Pay and Remuneration

Pay is one of the basic determinants of job satisfaction. Reward or pay is considered another way employees measure whether the time they spend and the effort they put in working are worthwhile. However, Smith (2001), in line with Herzberg's (1959) theory, stated that money brings the workers into the organisation but does not necessarily keep them. Similarly, Johnshrud and Rosser (2002) stated that salary has never been shown to be the primary motivator for faculty members and hence does not influence their decision to leave or stay. Armstrong (2010) also argued that money in the form of pay or some other sort of remuneration is the most obvious extrinsic reward and provides the carrot that most employees want but that its motivation does not have intrinsic meaning. In another study conducted in China, Ping, Manhong, and Lo (2010) analysed job satisfaction of university professors from nine Chinese universities. The Ping, Manhong and Lo. (2010) study came up with the following findings: The overall job satisfaction levels were close to average, with salary and benefits receiving the lowest level of satisfaction. Also, the empirical findings from Kanwar, Singh, and Kodwani (2012) further affirmed that sufficient forms of rewards for workers in an organisation contribute to the feeling of confidence and satisfaction. The study disclosed that "from this

perspective, job satisfaction is seen to be an emotional response resulting from the interaction of work rewards and work values”.

Similarly, another research study by Stankovska et al, (2017) investigated the possible relationship between job motivation and job satisfaction among academic staff. Job Satisfaction Survey and Job Motivation Questionnaire were administered to a sample of 100 (50 males and 50 females) university employees. Specifically, their results showed that the academicians were more satisfied with their salary but were dissatisfied with fringe benefits and contingent rewards. The researchers concluded that pay is among the main determinants of job satisfaction. Their findings were similar to those from other research studies like the one by Saga, Talon, and Tekogul (2011). The latter found that pay and promotion were associated with job satisfaction among post-doctoral researchers. However, other researchers believed that having friendly and supportive colleagues also contributes to increasing job satisfaction.

Furthermore, according to Hashim and Mahmood (2011), one factor that stands out to reduce turnover rate of academic staff is their compensation package. They investigated the state of job satisfaction among academic staff in public and private Malaysian Universities. Their study ranked salary as the least satisfied with. They suggested that policymakers and academic leaders at the universities should seriously consider benchmarking their compensation system and practices with the best practices of other educational institutions or with other service industries. Other considerations that were suggested are the availability of research grants, funds for attending conferences, sabbatical leave, a close relationship with peers and superiors, and favourable working conditions, which would also enhance job satisfaction beside pay.

Regarding equitable rewards in the form of pay, several lecturers expressed satisfaction and increased devotion to their duties when they perceive that their salary is fair. Wang and Feng (2003) argue along the same line that employees are satisfied when they perceive that fair decisions are made resulting from policies and procedures that fix salary scales according to

their tasks. Thus, it is only when these basic conditions are met, irrespective of whether the university is public or private, that lecturers and employees are satisfied with pay. Lecturers quitting or working additional jobs and shirking their binding responsibilities are the dangerous consequences of not providing adequate lecturer salaries. Ebuara and Coker (2012) found that workers in the education sector experienced unequal treatment in terms of their salary, compared to employees in other public or private sector institutions, despite similarities in the academic or professional qualifications.

b) The work environment

Irshad and Afridi (2011) reported that the physical and work environment plays a pivotal role in an employee's decision whether to leave the job or stay and as a matter of fact considered as a significant factor in employee job satisfaction. The work environment is generally discussed from an industrial perspective, focusing on aspects such as noise, exposure to toxic substances, condition of service, supervisor and workers relationship, the management, type of industry and organization and the country in perspective just to mention a few.

Shin and Jung (2014), in their study, examined the impact of management on job satisfaction and job stress across 19 higher education countries. The researchers classified the 19 countries according to their job satisfaction and job stress and applied regression analysis to test whether new public management had impacts on either or both job satisfaction and job stress. Shin and Jung's (2014) study revealed that academics' job satisfaction was the highest in Mexico (87 %) and the lowest in the United Kingdom (47 %) while job stress also varied across higher education countries from the highest of 68 % (Korea) to the smallest of 20 % (Malaysia). The extreme differences between countries was related to various environmental factors such as pressure for publication, salary, empowerment, academic freedom, governance, work conditions, workloads, and a feeling of affiliation.

Also, the findings of De Lourdes et al. (2016) revealed that Portuguese academics were satisfied with their academic professions but not very satisfied in general. They expressed more satisfaction with teaching climate, and colleagues while on the contrary they express less satisfaction with the research climate and conditions of employment hence these are the characteristics or conditions of the environment where they work that predicts their satisfaction.

Job satisfaction and some key performance Indicators

The concept of performance can be very wide and controversial because of its multifaceted context. The term is extremely popular as it is used across different activities in the arts, literature and social sciences. Most times its usage is intended to analyse things in order to yield better understanding. According to Carlson, (2013), performance can be used in three different contexts: (1) The display of skills, (2) A patterned behaviour, (3) Keeping up the standard. According to Murphy and Olsen (2009), staff Performance definitions should focus on behaviours rather than outcomes because a focus on outcomes could lead employees to find the easiest way to achieve the desired results, which is likely to be detrimental to the organization because other important behaviours will not be performed. Baumeister et al, (2003) however argue that performance is not the consequence of behaviours, but rather the behaviours themselves. This is to say that performance consists of the behaviours that employees engage in which can be observed. Motowidlo (2003) emphasize this evaluative idea in defining the performance domain and still maintain that job performance is all about behaviours and not results. One further element of performance is that the behaviours must be relevant to the goals of the organization (Baumeister et al., 2003). One of the ways in which employees' behaviour can promote organizational goal is through their commitment and when there is commitment, turnover intention is reduced while the likelihood for retention is increased. These are considered three key indicators for performance which are also relative to

job satisfaction. Figure 2.4 shows three performance indicators which can be used to analyse job satisfaction.

Figure 2. 4: Performance indicators for Job satisfaction

Employee's Commitment:

Employee's commitment can be seen as a performance indicator which is usually described as the degree to which workers align themselves or identifies with the overall goals and objectives of the organization. This directly relates to the level of commitment they show in the work they do. Adeniji, (2011) posits that if employee's ideology is similar to that of the organization, they will naturally be more interested in their work hence if they are satisfied, they exhibit higher level of commitment through high-quality behaviour. If this is the case, then committed lecturers in this context can be said to deliver high quality of learning and vice versa.

Also, employees tend to showcase their commitment through building relationships and setting up for the long-term, which ultimately makes them become an essential asset for the organization and this is where retention comes in. When deciding what makes a job viable or aligned with their perceptions, employees consider the feelings of accomplishment and interest, how they contribute to the lives of people, and how they can be crucial to attach tangible meaning to the work they are doing (Adeniji, 2011). On the contrary, a perceived lack of job

commitment necessitates an investigation into why this supposedly meaningful work is not producing the intended satisfaction that would contribute to positive work outcomes. Employee's commitment can also be an employee's response to their employer's mission and goals hence if workers do not accept the goal of the organisation, they might not want to stay there, and this will subsequently influence their likelihood to perform poorly in an organisation they are not entirely committed to. In this case, they are more likely to have turnover intention. It can therefore be said that the higher the commitment of an employee to his organization, the higher his performance and retention and the lower the possibility of turnover (Meyer and Allen, 1991).

Employee's Retention/Stay intention

According to the research of Bozeman and Gaughan (2011), the related literature reviewed on job satisfaction acknowledges that successful organisations share a fundamental philosophy of valuing and investing in their employees and that managing retention of promising employees is considered as fundamental means of achieving competitive advantage among organisations. Every organisation tries to stay on top of their game by finding ways of retaining their best employees which means that their performance is high in order not to lose them to the competitive organisation. This is because a higher retention rate is valuable for organisations including educational institutions as it reduces the overall cost associated with the recruitment processes.

According to Samuel and Chipunza (2009), retaining skilled employees is critical in order to sustain competition and ensure an effective and efficient service delivery among organisations. The responsibility, therefore, lies with the employer to ensure that they preserve and maintain their best employees. As such, retaining good employees remains a primary concern for many organisations in general and it is very vital for higher institutions to cherish

their intellectual property since intellectual property is a critical component of wealth creation and a source of national development. In the study of Adeniji (2011), since retention of employees is directly related to motivation and job satisfaction of such employees), educational institutions especially public ones need to make the latter a top priority in order not to lose their staff to competitive organisations (private universities).

Similarly, Osteraker (1999) argued that employees' satisfaction and retention are considered the cornerstone for the success of any organisation; however, it also largely depends on the employees to remain with the organization based on whether they are achieving their own motive. This means that retention is voluntary to employees since they have their rights to remain or to leave. When organisations or institutions of learning begin to fail in ensuring the comfort, motivation, and retention of employees, then they are heading for serious problems that may lead them to quit. To retain employees, therefore, an organisation needs to gain information about the dynamics that characterised the motivation to work. According to Irshad and Afridi (2011), past studies on employee job satisfaction and retention divided such problems into mental, social, or physical dimensions. The retention factors of the mental dimension are work characteristics: employees are retained by flexible tasks where they can use their knowledge and see the results of their efforts. The social dimension refers to the contact employees have with other people, both internal and external. The physical dimension consists of working conditions and pay.

On the social dimension, Gaan (2008) indicated that the existence of supervisor support, co-worker support, and flexible time within the organisation helped a lot in the retention of talented employees and their job satisfaction. Viewed from another perspective, Allen and Van der Velden, (2001) argued that organisations which supported their employee in integrating between family responsibilities and work reduced the employee's intention of leaving the job and increased employee's job satisfaction. Similarly, Pasewark and Viator (2006) placed a flexible work arrangement as a very important part of family support that played a pivotal role

in the retention of employees and their job satisfaction. In line with these studies, Yanadoria and Katob (2010) investigated the family support effects at the workplace and confirmed the importance of the relationship between work-family support and employee retention. They, therefore, concluded that the existence of family support within the organisation reduced the turnover intention and helped the retention of talented employees in the organisation. The mental dimension is basically in training and development.

Turnover Intention

Staff turnover is simply the rate in which people leave an organization (Mobley, 1982). Pelit et al. (2010) define it as the ratio of the number of organizational members during the period being considered divided by average number of people in that organization during the period. A common acronym for the excessive turnover rate in Nigerian educational sector is often referred to as a brain drain (Oshagbemi, 2000). From a qualitative research standpoint, Issa and Adebola (2014) focused on the relationship between turnover and performance of academic staff in Nigeria. Their study was to answer the following research questions: Is the productivity slowdown due to a high turnover rate of workers? Is high turnover rate an indicator of poor performance? The researchers found out that academic staff left the organisation for a number of reasons including but not limited to: compensation, job demand, work environment, dissatisfaction with the job, dissatisfaction with the organisation, inability to cope with responsibility, moving out of the area, retirement, inability to get on with colleagues and line managers, career development or career change and domestic reasons. Nevertheless, Issa and Adebola (2014) were able to establish that low turnover in an institution was not an indication of high performance and job satisfaction. This implies that there may be a low turnover rate, and employees may still lack job satisfaction. There may, however, be high productivity with low job satisfaction. An example of such situation may be where employees are not happy with

their jobs or do not get all they desire on the job yet remain committed in carrying out their duties and meeting targets. An explicit reason why this could happen is where there is an excess supply of labour and high rate of unemployment such that people are left with no choice than to stay and deliver on their current job. Affirming this fact, Labedo, (2005) confirmed that teaching professionals with higher qualifications or degrees in Nigeria do not intend to leave their teaching career because of prevalent unemployment in the country which is an indication of feeling of apathy – a feeling of indifference regardless of their job dissatisfaction. From this study, it can therefore be argued that job satisfaction and productivity can be loosely correlated due to the dynamics of the workplace situation. Furthermore, It was discovered by Issa & Adebola, 2014 that turnover intention could slow down productivity and that turnover rate was high in academic staff compared to non-academic staff in educational institutions. This could imply that the later have a wide range of career prospects than the former hence the reason why they leave. The researchers, therefore, recommended that an exit interview is necessary for any staff leaving the institution with a view to determine the immediate and remote causes of leaving.

Similarly, Armstrong (2000) stated that staff retention plan should be based on an analysis of why people leave. However, Moorhead and Griffin (2010) suggested that empowering employees through participative management enhances employees' involvement as well as motivation and in turn ensures retention. They claim that getting employees to participate gives them the influence to make decisions regarding their careers. Moreover, it allows them to make decisions within the area of their authority and responsibility which is a way of solving problems that could have led them to leave the organization.

In a nutshell, it can be deduced from the literature reviewed in this section that; job satisfaction is an important factor which makes a huge difference not just in other industries but especially to lecturers within the context of higher education institutions. In this regard, job satisfaction is positively related to employee's retention, and both are key to the success of any

organisation in terms of productivity or high performance. In addition to this, it has a positive effect on high student attainment. This was the position in the studies of Aluko (2002) and Muhammad (2010), who opined that lecturer's motivation that flows out of satisfaction with their job is found to increase student's performance and academic achievement. Furthermore, from a macro perspective, the performance of the higher education institution can directly be dependent on lecturers' job satisfaction and their performance, and this further translates into educational development. In essence, as one of the indices of national development of a nation and an area of global sustainable development, lecturers job satisfaction becomes increasingly important. Its achievement makes a huge difference because it is one of the basic ways through which global SDG can be achieved.

Theoretical Review

For several centuries, scholars have developed theories that explain human involvement in social enterprises such as career. No doubt, these theories have been applied in corporate practices and influenced career choices, development, and job satisfaction. For the purpose of this study, the following theories will be explored: Herzberg's motivator- hygiene theory of job satisfaction, John Holland theory of career choice, and Watt and Richardson's Fit-choice model.

Job Satisfaction Theory

Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory

The theory was developed and validated by Frederick Herzberg in 1950 and it is also known as the two-factor theory. Research has consistently demonstrated its significance even in the contemporary world (Smith and Shields, 2013). According to Herzberg (2008), the Two-Factor Theory is a theory of job attitudes, and it is used to explain the job satisfaction of

employees in a given organisation. The theory states that there are those distinct factors characteristic of the workplace that cause job satisfaction, and there is a separate set of factors that cause job dissatisfaction (Smith and Shields, 2013). He called the factors that cause job satisfaction motivators or intrinsic factors and those that cause dissatisfaction; he referred to them as hygiene factors or extrinsic factors. Over the years, the hygiene factors have developed to include Company policy and management style, Interpersonal relationships, Salary, job security and Working conditions while motivators: recognition, achievement, the work itself, advancement or the possibility for growth and responsibility. Regarding this theory, a recent study by Peter (2019) discovered that there was no significant correlation between Herzberg's motivators and job satisfaction and performance among university lecturers in Tanzania while another study by Munyengabe, (2017) utilising a sample of lecturers from Rwandese universities, found a strong positive correlation between Herzberg's motivators and job satisfaction, thus contrasting with Peter's, 2019. Similarly, Hilmi, Ali and Nihal, (2016) discovered that Herzberg's motivators were positively and significantly correlated with job satisfaction among high school teachers in Turkey. The main difference between Munyengabe et al.'s (2017) study and that of Hilmi, Ali and Nihal, (2016) is that the former's findings agreed with Herzberg's theory's tenets. In contrast with the theory, the latter's conclusions indicated that both motivators and hygiene factors were positively correlated with high school teachers' job satisfaction. Overall, for the three studies critiqued, inconsistencies between their findings have been observed, a phenomenon or trend pointing out to the possible inadequacies of the theory, especially in the contemporary world. The Two-Factor Theory has remained relatively unchanged for several years, meaning there is a possibility that time is outpacing its usefulness. Especially, the most notable inconsistency between studies is Herzberg's (2008) assertion that the absence of hygiene factors (e.g., job security, good pay, insurance, work conditions, and fringe benefits) often result in job dissatisfaction, but their presence contributes non-significantly to job satisfaction.

In light of the contention highlighted in the previous paragraph, Hilmi, Ali and Nihal, (2016) indicate that the findings of their study were partly contrasting with the original tenets of the theory, probably due to the educational context under examination. Interpretively, Hilmi, Ali and Nihal, (2016) utilised a sample of high school teachers. Their study was reviewed because, despite the pedagogical and contextual differences between universities and high schools, there are similarities that can be considered intuitively adequate to make comparisons for theoretical reasoning only. As such, it was also imperative to confirm from prior studies whether the variations observed in studies utilising this theory could be attributable to contextual differences or simply because the theory is not conceptually consistent to render consistent findings across various practical domains. One way to do this is to search for studies that have examined the impact of Herzberg's hygiene factors on lecturers' motivation. For example, a recent study discovered that job security and workload positively impacted lecturers' job satisfaction in Punjab, India (Hussain and Saif, 2019). The perspectives under Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory formed the core of the theoretical framework formulated for the current study insofar as the theoretical perspective facilitated the explanation regarding how the absence of hygiene factors (e.g., job security, good pay, insurance, work conditions, and fringe benefits) often result in job dissatisfaction. Still, their presence contributes non-significantly to job satisfaction.

Locke (1976) also criticized Herzberg's theory for defensiveness. Locke believed that there is a fallacy in the views of employees that were interviewed in Herzberg's study such that they took credit for factors like their advancement and recognition (the satisfiers) while they laid blames on their supervisors, policies and co-workers for their dissatisfaction. With such implication, it can therefore be noticed that participants in Herzberg's study has both internal and external locus of control which psychologically affected the result of the research. Similarly, Armstrong (2000), also argued that Herzberg was uncovering people and making them "look good" by attributing positive events to internal factors and negative experiences

to external events. This is however not far from what Locke named “Defensiveness”. In a Nigerian Context, Evans and Olumide-Aluko (2010) presented a critique of Herzberg’s two-factor theory on lecturers’ job satisfaction. Their principal interest was on the issue of pay, which Herzberg categorized as a hygiene factor. The result of their study considered this as a motivator therefore disproved Herzberg’s theory on this ground.

Considering the foregoing critics, it can be said that most of these studies diverge dramatically and, in the end, different results emerged from their different research techniques, methodologies and different context within which they were carried out. As a result, Popper (1968) cited by Gray (2018 p23) submitted thus, ‘theories cannot be proven to be true – they can only be proven to be false’. In spite of all critics, Herzberg’s theory was validated to be suitable to apply across different careers (originally accountants and engineers) regardless of job content and context therefore chosen for this study on the basis of its applicability to lecturers’ career context.

Career Choice/Development Theory

John Holland's Theory of Career Choice

Holland's theory of career choice is traced back to his article published in the year 1958 and later expounded in the year 1959 in the journal of applied psychology (Athanasou, 2009). The following figure presents the six personalities in a summary form.

Figure 2. 5: Holland's 6 Personality Type. Source: Adopted from Holland, (1997)

According to Figure 2.5 above, the six career personality types are given with examples of careers that fall in each category. Nonetheless, to demystify the issue critically, it is important to have a brief review of the six personalities for building a better understanding. As observed in Figure 2.5, the doers exhibited the realistic trait, whose interests are mainly focused on working with their hands, fixing, making, building or assembling things with the help of machines, tools or equipment (Reardon and Lenz, 2015). The main skills of such professions include designing, maintaining, measuring, driving, caring for animals, moving, working with plants and in detail through manually being engaged in different duties. Moreover, Holland's theory argues that some of the common occupations that are characteristics of realistic features

include sportsperson, park ranger, computer technologist, electrician, upholsterer, mechanic, engineer, builder, horticulturalists, farmer, pilot, and personnel in the armed services (Sampson, 2016). In this case, it is common for realistic persons to work alone or with other realists, but the main objective is to enjoy concrete tasks from which they derive gratitude. These observations imply that lecturers with realistic traits are likely to have low job satisfaction and motivation. As applied to the Nigerian context, it can be said that Nigerian universities can implement this approach to map the personality types of lecturers for guidance and counselling purposes.

Figure 2.5 also makes reference to investigative personality according to Holland's theory, in which case emphasis is put on individuals whose interests are to research and discover ideas, experiment, investigate, observe, solve problems, and ask questions. The inherent skills of such individuals include investigating, experimenting, diagnosing, formulating, designing, computing, and thinking logically as well as analytically (Spokane, Moya and Faris, 2016). However, Spokane et al. (2016 p8) emphasised that "caution must be exercised in evaluating cross-cultural studies of the underlying structure of interests for several reasons". As such, common occupations in this personality type include doctors, dentists, zoologists, technicians (laboratory), forestry researchers, marine scientists, chemists, and researchers. Such individuals are defined by their overall character of wanting to critically know the underlying reasons and factors for a certain phenomenon (Sampson, 2016). For example, a study discovered that an investigative personality was positively correlated with sensation seeking among clerks and firemen (Gorji, Hatamy and Khoshkonesh, 2011). However, there is lack of research that investigates if an investigative personality influences job satisfaction and motivation among lecturers, considering that despite being researchers, their main activity is teaching.

Another important trait referred to is artistic, which is founded on the tenets of art, words, music, drama, and other ways of communicating, performing, and expressing views.

These professionals include fashion designers, hairdressers, advertisers, editors, writers, reporters, actors, dancers, singers, sign writers, photographers, illustrators, and instrument players, respectively (Spokane, Moya and Faris, 2016). The research disclosed the centrality of Holland theory, arguing that “we conclude that the underlying social mechanisms and processes influence the formation of vocational interests across cultures in a contingent manner” (Spokane, Moya and Faris, 2016, p.8). According to Yusof, Mohd and Jaafar (2014), based on the Holland theory, the best personality traits for teaching staff is SAE (social, artistic, and Enterprising). However, so far, there is no study that has demonstrated the extent to which artistic personality traits influence job satisfaction among university teaching staff. Therefore, these observations confirm the relevance of the current study on the necessity for empirical confirmations, especially by focusing on the significance level of the artistic trait in enhancing the job satisfaction and motivation of university lecturers.

The fourth personality type, according to Holland's theory, is the social aspect which is founded on the individuals that enjoy working with people, and they include; teachers, nurses, counsellors, secretaries, waiters, customer service agents, sales people, social workers and the police officers (Reardon and Lenz, 2015). As well, as highlighted above, the social trait is also key in the teaching profession, as demonstrated by Yusof, Mohd, and Jaafar, (2014). Yet, like the artistic trait, the social trait is least explored in the literature from the perspective of university faculty's job satisfaction and motivation. However, there are studies closely related to the current topic of investigation hinting that lecturers who are not sociable have low job satisfaction and motivation. For example, Idrus (2015) discovered that agreeableness had a positive impact on lecturers' job commitment (due to increased job satisfaction) in one Indonesian public university. In contrast, a previous study undertaken by Peter, Gitonga and Kubai (2021) reiterated that the level of the agreeableness of an individual closely correlated with the degree of socialisation. From this perspective, it can be claimed that through agreeableness, lecturers are able to be sociable, implying that lecturers with social traits in their

personalities were more likely to perform better at work due to increased job satisfaction and motivation. However, this hypothetical claim needs to be confirmed in future research, especially under the fact that social traits have been positively linked to better job retention among teaching staff (Yusof et al., 2014). Yusof, Mohd, and Jaafar, (2014 p.142) linked to career and personality by asserting that “therefore, the precise choice of career may lead to individual effectiveness in performing their duties, in facing challenges and thus feeling satisfied for being successful in their respective fields”.

The fifth personality (enterprising) stands for individuals that like meeting and talking with people, and the main professionals include accountants, lawyers and politicians, among others (Sargent and Kennelly, 2016). As highlighted earlier, Yusof, Mohd, and Jaafar (2014) discovered that an enterprising personality was best suited for the teaching profession. In agreement, a recent study discovered that the ambitious personality of teachers had a positive impact on the performance of public primary schools in Kenya (Peter, Gitonga and Kubai, 2021). Although no study has investigated how an enterprising personality affects job satisfaction and motivation among university lecturers, it can be hypothesised that this personality type could be beneficial for Nigerian public university lecturers. As well, future research should investigate the significance level of the enterprising personality training on lecturers' job satisfaction.

Finally, a conventional personality stands for those who enjoy working indoors and organising things accurately, such as clerks, store men, and secretaries (Holland and Messer, 2013). From this discussion, it can be deduced that lecturer's professional drive and career experiences are determined by their inner personality types. This fact refers to an intrinsic form of motivation. Moreover, this demonstrates that individuals are motivated to make career choices that are in line with their individual interests (Lent, 2017). At this stage, the puzzling phenomenon is how Holland's theory of career choice can be used to foster increased or deter job satisfaction among university lecturers in Nigeria. Remarkably, I settled for this theory

because the theory is relevant to job satisfaction. Holland’s description of personality types and their influence to choice of career has been confirmed by researchers (example; Idrus, 2015, Yusof, Mohd, and Jaafar, 2014), to indirectly influence job satisfaction of university lecturers making it relevant to the subject (job satisfaction) and career context (university lecturers) of this study.

Factors Influencing Teaching Choice: The FIT-Choice model

The Fit-choice model is a theory developed by Watt and Richardson (2007). The model illustrates several underlying factors that are involved in the decision to pursue a career as a teacher or lecturer, and all components of the model function together in the decision-making process of individuals. Individuals are more likely to pursue options for which they believe they have the necessary skills, for which they place a high value, and for which they do not expect to pay a high cost example, considering level of effort (Watt and Richardson, 2007).

Figure 2. 6: The FIT choice model Adopted from Watt and Richardson, (2007)

The fit choice model was developed based on the expectancy value theory which advocate that ‘...values and ability beliefs are crucial motivations in predicting career choices’ (Den Brok et al., 2013, p. 4). In regard to the diagram in figure 2.6, determining the choice of teaching career is linked to two set of intrinsically motivated values; personal utility value and social utility value. These values are a product of socialization influences such as social dissuasion, prior teaching and learning experiences and social influences. Personal utility value refers to the tendency to which teachers feel that teaching tasks are related to their personal career goal. These goals according to this model include; job security, time for family and job transferability. On the other hand social utility value refers to the extent to which teachers feel that the teaching career enable them impact lives and contribute to society. This includes shaping the future of children or adolescents, enhancing social equity, making a social contribution and working with children or adolescents. These two intrinsic values according to Den Brok et al., (2013, p. 4) are ‘the enjoyment an individual experiences when carrying out a certain task’. Additionally, from this model, there are other factors that also influences the choice of teaching career which are external to the individual. By external, this means the extent to which the teaching career will be in future (Den Brok et al., 2013, Salifu, Alagbela, and Gyamfi, 2018) These factors include task demand and task return. Task demand entails whether the career is an expert career and whether it is in high demand while task return entail the social value of the job and the salary involved. The last set of factors that influences teaching career choice are; self-perception which is the perceived teaching abilities of the individual and feedback career factor.

Reference to the Fit choice model, Watt et al, (2012 p.3) is of the view that ‘high perceptions of task demand would deter people from a teaching career, although this may be moderated by perceptions of high task return’. The purpose of the scale used in this model was to assess people’s primary motive for the teaching career and was practically indicative to be sound psychometrically after being used on a sample of 1653 Australian teachers. Also, there

is a positive-negative outcome indicative of its variables in relation to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. In this regard, Watt et al, (2012 p.2) provide thus: ‘the motive that related most strongly to high career satisfaction included the altruistic-type motivations most frequently emphasised in the teacher education literature, the intrinsic value individuals attached to teaching, and self-evaluations of their teaching-related skills (Watt et al 2012)’.

The various elements contained in the Fit-choice model has been confirmed to convey similar meaning and perception with other common teaching career choice variables in literature like Anghel, (2020), Heinz (2015), Balyer and Özcan, (2014), Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014) and Moran et al, (2001). With this similarity, the three traditional teaching career motive namely; altruistic, intrinsic and extrinsic are in tandem with personal utility value, social utility value, self-perception, task demand and task return. Accordingly, personal utility value and task return identifies with extrinsic factors, while social utility value is identified with altruistic factors and finally, self-perception is identified with intrinsic factors.

While choosing a theoretical framework that identifies with this study was important to me, it is without doubt that the Fit-choice model has its own weaknesses. Particularly regarding this research, one of the weaknesses of the Fit choice model to this study is that it identifies with a positivist paradigm while this study adopts a social constructivist paradigm. The positivist paradigm is of the view that there is a universal truth that is separate from the object of study. This is falsified by the social relationship that exist between the object of the study and its environment as postulated by social constructivism. Despite this weakness, the model was chosen because it is exclusive to a teaching career therefore aligns well with the career context of this study as compared to other universal theories of career choice/development. Another reason for the choice of this theory was the belief that the professional motivation constituents is relevant to lecturing context in Nigeria given that aspiring lecturers and academics would be driven into the profession by some or all the factors explicated in the

theory based on their backgrounds and ambition for being in a career where they will derive satisfaction.

The Conceptual Model

Problems are immersed within the research questions and one of the processes through which they can be explored and/or solved is by conceptualizing the ideas that surround it. By doing so, it creates a bigger picture encapsulating different concepts, phenomena or variables that defines the problem(s). One of the benefits of this is that it connects various phases or components of the research. Considering the current study, the purpose is to investigate what predominantly motivates lecturers to the teaching profession and goes further to find out what they experience working in a Nigerian public university as a means of understanding the source of their satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The study explores lecturers' lived experiences using a phenomenological strategy aiming to contribute to knowledge and organizational practice by providing concerned management and policy makers with an up-to-date knowledge on lecturers' job satisfaction. This is to aid in the decision to promote satisfaction of teaching staff based on their predominant career motive and experiences explored in this study. It will in turn help improve learning and development in the education sector. In fulfilling the above research purpose, the conceptual model is designed to meet the following objectives:

1. To determine the pre-dominant teaching motivation of professional lecturers in Nigerian public Universities.
2. To find out what lectures experience working in Nigerian public universities.
3. To determine whether lecturers' professional motivation and experiences inform their job satisfaction

Figure 2. 7: The conceptual model.

This study adopts the conceptual framework shown in figure 2.7 focusing on job (dis)satisfaction as its central element. The conceptualization is conceived from theoretical elements and empirical literature on teaching career motivation and job satisfaction. In terms of teaching career motivation, the conceptual framework adopts a combination of elements from the Fit-choice model by Watt and Richardson (2007) coupled with elements of career choice from Anghel, (2020), Watt et al, (2012), Heinz (2015), Balyer and Ozcan, (2014), Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014) and Moran et al, (2001). This appears on the left-hand side of the diagram. This side of the conceptualization reveals the reason or motive behind lecturers' choice of the profession (professional motivation) which may influence their satisfaction if met or dissatisfaction if not met. Moreover, central to determining job satisfaction with these

teaching professional motives is using watt et al, (2012) provision that teachers with altruistic-type motivation are strongly satisfied. The three-core teaching professional motive, or reasons for choosing a teaching career in the conceptual model include intrinsic, extrinsic, and altruistic [Anghel, (2020), Heinz (2015), Balyer and Özcan, (2014), Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014), Moran et al, (2001)]. According to Moran et al. (2001) intrinsic reasons include factors like personal fulfilment, self-development, or career progression whereas extrinsic reasons include factors like pay, job security, the work environment, economic condition and family influence and altruistic reasons include the passion to make impact in people's lives or make a social contribution and the pleasure working with students. While regarding the Fit-choice model in figure 2.6, Watt and Richardson's (2007), teaching career choice involve an array of socialisation values. In general, its social utility value factors is the same as altruistic motive (passion to impact), while its Personal utility value and task return factor is identified with extrinsic motive (job security, pay).

On the right-hand side are some of the job satisfaction correlates/determinants suggested by Egbule, (2003) and Umaru and Ombugus, (2017) within the study context used as experiential factors. This is because these job satisfaction correlates is an embodiment of what lecturers experience in Nigerian public universities. The conceptualization shows that professional motivation and lived experiences (or systemic experiences) within the public university system could influence lecturers' job (dis)satisfaction. Following the various literature that was reviewed, it is evident that academic staff derive either satisfaction or dissatisfaction following certain work-related factors such as strike actions, education policies, salaries, promotion, organizational politics, and the work environment among so many others. From the perspective of their lived experiences, it can be said that Nigerian lecturers most likely derive dissatisfaction when their experiences encompassing the aforementioned work-related factors are negative causing them to show negative attitude towards work (Armstrong, 2006) hence the reason for the -negative/+positive signs. On the other hand, research by Armstrong,

(2006) has also shown that lecturers derive satisfaction when the work-related factors they experience are positive or positively affects their job for example good pay, promotion, good work environment. In essence factors affecting job satisfaction or dissatisfaction can be an embodiment of lived experiences.

Furthermore, there are some performance measures that could also result owing to the satisfaction or dissatisfaction of lecturers as seen in the outer part of the diagram. These include: student attainment, productivity, turnover intention and commitment. What this means in essence is that the more the satisfaction lecturers would derive from their experiences and motivation, the positive their performance will lead to high student attainment, increased productivity, low turnover intention and high level of commitment. On the other hand, the more dissatisfaction derived, the negative these factors would return. This is the reason for the negative and positive signs outside the diagram. For example: According to the study of Issa and Adebola (2014), The study shows that there was a high rate of turnover among lecturers because of dissatisfaction with the job among other reasons. Likewise, the study of Appiah-Agyekum, Suapim, and Peprah, (2013) who revealed that lecturer's retention is problematic as provisions that enhances their satisfaction were neglected and while this persists, uncommitted behaviours also remain on the high side (Amos, 2015 et al). These two studies show that there is a negative performance outcome or impact following job dissatisfaction. This is in opposition to the study of Gwavuya (2011) who provided that lecturers who were satisfied (with their chairman/dean) had stay-intentions which is on the other hand positive.

Furthermore, commitment to students in the context of tertiary institution is said to be a grounded idea of lecturers with high expectation of good performance from their student where their motive is for their students to achieve success (Yorke & Longden, 2004) hence the connecting link between lecturers' commitment and students' attainment. It can be said that lecturers' concentration on students' performance is a product of their motivation to impact so that their students can become successful perhaps lecturers that are more committed to their

profession would have a positive effect towards their teaching ability than those with less commitment to either profession, and students (Mustapha, and Bolaji, 2015). In essence, This can be an indication of prioritizing students' success following their own satisfaction to ensure that they are not just academically sound but also in society. Focusing on the effect of job satisfaction or dissatisfaction following these performance measures can therefore be phenomenal to academic staff in Nigerian university institutions hence achieving the former will result in positivity (example high commitment, student attainment and stay intention) while the later will result in negativity (example turnover intention).

Chapter Three

Methodology

Introduction

It is an essential part of a research process to examine the approach that is best suited for it as well as the perspective it will adopt to solve the research problems (Walliman 2011, Singh 2006). According to Wahyuni., (2012) this involves series of procedures, tools and techniques used to gather and analyse data. Its purpose is to structure the research in such a way that will reflect and support what was laid down in previous chapters in other to meet the purpose of the study. The purpose of this phenomenological study is to understand lecturer's professional motivation, their experiences working in a Nigerian Public university and how these influences their job satisfaction. This chapter of the study therefore takes into consideration such components as the Research design, Paradigm of enquiry, methodology, methods, data analysis procedures and ethics.

The Research Design

According to Baridam, (2001), research design explains the structure, plan, and fashion in which the research process and procedure would be, and the context within which such research would be put to play. Asita (2012) is of the opinion that a research design is a blueprint upon which a research strategy is mapped out, with the aim of objectively achieving its original purpose, in an accurate manner, and as economical as possible. He further maintained that, while conducting a study, information in form of raw data is collected, collated, measured, and analysed following the design for such study.

There are two broad types of Research design: Quantitative and qualitative (Marczyk, and DeMatteo, 2010). A quantitative research design gathers numeric data while qualitative research design gathers non-numeric data. Also, the former often follows a scientific approach

used for hypothesis testing unlike the latter that is used to understand peoples' experiences, perception, and behaviours regarding a phenomenon. This makes quantitative research objective in nature while qualitative is subjective.

Choosing a Qualitative Research Design

According to (Creswell 2007, p37), designing qualitative research ‘begins with assumptions, a worldview, the possible use of a theoretical lens, and the study of research problems inquiring into the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem’. This study adopts a qualitative research design instead of quantitative. The reason for the adoption of qualitative research design for this study is tied to my world view as shown in figure 3.1.

Basic Assumptions	Philosophical Questions	Quantitative	Qualitative	My worldview
Ontological Assumptions	What is the nature of reality or knowledge?	Reality is objective in nature, singular and different from the researcher	Reality is subjective, multiple and cannot be separated from the researcher	Qualitative
Epistemological Assumptions	What is the link between the researcher and what is studied?	Researcher is separate from what is studied	Researcher is part of what is studied through social inference.	Qualitative
Axiological Assumptions	What is the starring role of Value?	Value-free and impartial.	Value-laden and partial.	Qualitative
Methodological Assumptions.	What is the method adopted by researcher?	correlational; quasi-experimental; experimental; causal comparative; survey	phenomenology; ethnographic; symbolic interaction; narrative	Qualitative
	What is the technique of gathering data?	questionnaires, structured interview observations, tests and experiments	Unstructured interviews, participant observation, pictures, photographs, diaries and documents	Qualitative

Table 3. 1: Choosing my research design – Adopted from Creswell, (2017)

From table 3.1, my world view emerges as I answer to the philosophical questions of ontology, epistemology, methodology and axiology. These assumptions define knowledge and how it can best be acquired. From a subjective view, qualitative research design was most suitable for my research as the purpose of the study was to obtain meaning from lecturer's lived experiences through unstructured interviews. Other considerations for a qualitative research design include the theoretical lens within which this research is carried out. This study does not have any element that scientifically test the validity of any theory or hypothesis. Neuman (2014 p.176) noted that in qualitative research, researchers tend to capture people's experience and discover the meaning of the concept under review once they become immersed in the data. He further explained that qualitative research procedures are peculiar because analysis is done by extracting themes from evidence and organizing the data to represent a coherent and consistent picture comprising of clusters of meaning. In a bid to shade light on this, Neuman (2014 p.176) noted that most 'qualitative studies examine social processes and study interpretations or meanings in specific socio-cultural settings.

Furthermore, adopting a qualitative research design is to focus on the non-numeric phenomenal nature of my research question (Babbie and Earl, 2014). For instance, Neuman (2014) noted that instead of converting an active social life into variables and numbers, qualitative research allows researchers to borrow ideas and viewpoints from the participants and situate them in a natural situation. This guided the focus of my research towards capturing the responses and perceptions of the participants rather than trying to quantify any variable.

Also, the inductive orientation of this study sort to describe the complexity and meaning of social phenomenon by explaining patterns revealed through the data (Marshall and Rossman, 2006) rather than using the data to explain a predetermined theory. This investigative approach is to ensure rich detailed description that encapsulate lecturers' experiences on the job to capture how satisfied they are on the job. This qualitative method explores the depth of the phenomenon in order to present the reader with thorough understanding of the various

elementary components of the phenomenon experienced and allowing the researcher to probe for deeper meaning from participants.

The study is cross-sectional in nature. This is determined by the purpose of the research and the timeline for data collection, which is within a particular period in contrast to longitudinal study where participants are put under observation over a long period of time.

Research Philosophy

The main purpose of this study is to first understand why people choose lecturing as their profession and then to explore their experiences in order to understand how their drive for the profession and career experiences informs or influences their state of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In other words, assessing job satisfaction against prior motive for the teaching profession and career experiences. It is all about knowing how people construct meaning of their own lived experiences. Current literature within this research context is void of investigating the influence between these phenomena (professional motivation, experiences, and job satisfaction). It is therefore necessary to explore into this area using a phenomenological approach as an experiential enquiry. There is no doubt that understanding lecturer's experiences can help to understand their satisfaction hence also know the beliefs, views, and the assumptions they hold about the phenomena in question. Research philosophy refers to how knowledge is conceived. It deals with the source, nature, and development of knowledge (Bajpai (2011). According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, (2009), research philosophy is divided into four. They are: Positivism, realism, pragmatism and interpretivism.

Positivism

Positivism follows the tradition and processes of natural science (Saunders et al. 2009). It posits that only factual things can be studied with the aim of establishing scientific laws (Crossan, 2003). It follows that positivism only deals with empirical testing to find relationship and causation which is mostly adopted by natural scientists and quantitative researchers (Greener, 2008). With this aim, positivism tends to reduce the research problem into smaller factual elements to make it easier for analysis (Amaratunga et al., 2002). Positivism believes that valid knowledge are those that are objective in nature and that in order to get credible data only observable phenomenon should be studied hence during data collection, hypothesis are developed from existing theories and tested to confirm the validity of the phenomenon. One weakness of this philosophy is that it fails to acknowledge that not everything can be studied objectively therefore sees subjective data as insignificant.

Interpretivism

Interpretivism deals more with studying a phenomenon in its social environment (Blaikie, 2004). Interpretivists believe that gaining knowledge is based upon the fact that reality is socially constructed. Also, they believe that different realities exist that is construed in different context and perception of individuals within their environment. Interpretivism tries to understand human experience in a subjective way. Unlike the positivist philosophy where hypothesis are generated in order to test the validity of a theory, in the interpretivist philosophy theory does not precede research rather it is grounded upon the data generated from the research (Gray, 2018). That is, theory may come after data has been collected and analysed (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). In most cases, the data that is gathered is used to explain or support prior literature.

Pragmatism

Pragmatists argue that it is not possible to access the truth about the world through a single scientific method as posited by positivists, neither can the truth be credibly known by our association with the social world as claimed by the interpretivists. To them, there is no single paradigmatic orientation that is credible enough; rather, to determine truth, the researcher must aim at following a world view and combination of methods that are seen as most appropriate in studying the phenomenon at hand (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). The main purpose of this philosophy is to find the best way to answer the research question rather than tying the study to a specific philosophical orientation.

Realism

Realism is also known as critical realism according to Saunders et al. (2009). Critical Realists posit that what we personally see or experience with our senses as humans truly portray the world. In other words, 'they focus on what is seen and experienced in terms of underlying structures of reality that shape the observable events' (Saunders et al., 2009, p138). According to realists, reality is external and independent of human knowledge. This means that it cannot be directly accessed by human observation. One weakness of this philosophy is that it fails to believe that human senses can be deceptive when capturing what is believed to be a reality or truth. This is because sensation can be illusory. Illusion is a representation of what is real (Saunders et al., 2009).

Locating the philosophical underpinning for this Study

In social sciences we study human behaviour likewise in this study. Following this, the philosophy of how humans behave and how to know how humans behave can either be studied objectively or subjectively. It describes the nature or components of knowledge and how it is acquired. As the foundation of all philosophical position objectivist assumptions are identified with positivism, uses scientific method, views axiology as value free, sees the world and reality as measurable which can be described by natural laws and relationships. It is thus driven by quantitative methods; it uses experimentation and statistics; its questionnaires quantify attitudes and perceptions, and it looks to generalize via large samples. On the other hand, Subjectivist assumptions are identified with social construction, interpretivism, it believes there is no single reality, axiology is value laden, reality cannot be measured, it is reflexive, data are collected via interviews, narratives, stories which seeks the voice of individuals and does not generalize but rather looks for transferability.

Following the above two main paradigmatic provisions, this research is deeply subjective and identifies with an interpretivist philosophy for the reason of its social construction evident in the belief that knowledge is constructed out of the interaction between humans and their world (environment) and in the process transmitted within a social context that is subject to interpretation. The purpose of this research was to understand what drive lecturers towards the teaching profession and to explore their experiences within the context of the public university sector to determine their satisfaction. This shows no quantifiable element and suggestive that the method of data collection and analysis is through active interaction and interpretation however as the researcher, being mindful of excluding my inferences is paramount.

Paradigm of Enquiry

As the researcher, how I view knowledge or truth (researchers world view) strategically motivates this study. With this, it guided my thinking, beliefs, and assumption of how the larger society views the world around them (Schwandt, 2001) which is what social scientists refer to as a paradigm. It is simply the beliefs that people hold about certain knowledge. According to Chilisa and Kawulich, (2012, p1), paradigm is “a way of describing a world view that is informed by philosophical assumptions about the nature of social reality, ways of knowing, ethics and value systems”.

Numerous philosophers have contributed to the thinking, knowledge, and worldviews of what we refer today to as paradigms as portrayed by the different schools of philosophy. This is to say that in order to gain knowledge, people come to hold different views based on their understanding which is translated as their paradigm. In other words, when there is a paradigm shift, it means there is a change in the way people usually think. Flowers, (2009) suggest that it is the set of beliefs upon which research is conducted. According to sunders et al., (2009), it is the set of beliefs and assumptions that guides the perspective of the research with the aim of meeting its objectives. Adopting a paradigm for this research enable me make assumptions about the nature of the phenomena which helped to tailor the research to achieve its purpose (Holden and Lynch., 2004). Dash (2005, p.4) believe there are four basic questions one needs to ask when selecting a paradigm and methodology in social research. They are:

1. What is the nature or essence of the social phenomena being investigated?
2. Are social phenomena objective in nature or created by the human mind?
3. What are the bases of knowledge corresponding to the social reality, and how can knowledge be acquired and disseminated?
4. What is the relationship of an individual with her environment? Is she conditioned by the environment or is the environment created by her?

As the researcher, my belief of how knowledge can be achieved and developed informs the exploratory effort through which I made strategic decisions to choose suitable methodology and processes of collecting data and analysis for this study. In this regard, this section outlines my study's ontological, epistemological, and axiological positions.

My ontological position

Ontology is the believe we hold about what constitute the phenomenon that we study or what contribute to the knowledge we hold about the world around us. It demonstrates the characteristics and nature of the reality of the situation at hand (Kivunja, and Kuyini, 2017). Ontology embodies to understand “what is” and “what kind of knowledge are legitimate and adequate” (Gray, 2018, p21). In the light of my ontological position, I assume that the phenomena studied is complex in nature as it may be informed by two primary factors: personal and environmental. In my view, knowing what drives people to take a career (professional motive) and how they experience the circumstances surrounding the phenomenon (career) are influenced by (1) Their internal self and (2) external/environmental circumstances. These two come together to constitute experiential knowledge. Internal (disposition) and environmental influences tend to shape human perception with regards to their experiences and expectations and also give reasons as to why they exhibit certain behaviour, take actions or have certain experiences. Experiences in this case becomes tied to their interaction with the environment and becomes their reality. Chilisa and Kawulich, (2012, p10) says reality is “mind dependent” and a “personal or social construct” and that there are individual realities as well as group-shared realities. According to Dewey, (1958, p14), ‘It concerns the influence of habitual beliefs and expectations in their social generation upon what is experienced’. In this regard, the reality of what constitute knowledge is construed both by self and from the influence of the environment. These ontological positions enabled me to analyse the lived experiences and worldview of the lecturers and further conform my epistemological position with this study.

My Epistemological position

Epistemology defines how researchers know what they know. It refers to how knowledge is being acquired. Epistemology ask questions like; can knowledge be acquired straight away, or, is it something which has to be personally experienced? In this regard, Chilisa and Kawulich, (2012) posits that knowledge is subjective, because it is socially constructed.

In this regard, the basic believe about the means of knowledge acquisition that motivate this study evolves around my constructivist disposition. Whereas objectivists posit that knowledge is objective and exists independently of the subject of research, my constructivist epistemological believe is in contrast because if we live in the environment of the object then knowledge must be conceived through our perception and interaction with it therefore, I believe that knowledge exists within the consciousness and experiences of the subject (the participants). Crotty, (1998, p42) states that “all knowledge, and therefore all meaningful reality as such, is contingent upon human practices, being constructed in and out of interaction between human beings and their world and developed and transmitted within an essentially social context”. Furthermore, Moustakas, (1994) asserts that ‘To understand the objects that appear before us we must return to the self, to know and recognize ourselves in the experience that is investigated’. These assertions informed my belief that truth or reality is dependent on the subject researched and can only be construed through their social construction. This means that knowledge cannot be detached from the “Knower” hence it is not independent of the respondents who make meaning out of it based on their own perception (Kivunja, and Kuyini, 2017). Based on this, it is believed that phenomena under study have multiple realities that are captured through different capacities or positions of the respondents who experienced them hence my belief that there are always different sides to every experience.

Furthermore, my support for the constructivist epistemology is evident in the purpose statement which aim to explore lecturer’s professional motive and what they experience

working in Nigerian public universities as a determinant of job satisfaction. This articulates meaning from lecturers based on their own social construction or perception which they create out of their experience prior to as well as on the job respectively. From the angle of my constructionist disposition, Kivunja, and Kuyini, (2017) advocates that the researcher assumes a subjectivist epistemology to know the story behind people's experiences. This means that as the researcher, for me to understand the experiences of lecturers in this case, I have to construct knowledge socially through my conversation with the participants and describe or interpret it within the context it is said (Guba and Lincoln 1989, P45). By doing so, I make meaning of the data through my own thinking and cognitive processing of data informed by my interactions with the participants. This is what Kivunja, and Kuyini, (2017) refer to as subjectivist epistemology or constructivism. It reinforces what Braun and Clarke (2006) posits about researchers discovering themes as opposed to the belief that themes emerge from data. It also supports the second and fourth points made by Guba and Lincoln (1989, p83) as they provide that a constructivist-oriented study, emphasises that: (1) The researcher-respondent relationship is subjective, interactive, and interdependent (2) reality is multiple, complex, and not easily quantifiable (3) The values of the researcher, respondents, research site, and underlying theory undergird all aspects of the research (4) The research product is context specific. In all, they concluded that 'phenomenon can be understood only within the context in which they are studied' (Guba and Lincoln, 1989 p45). All these motivated my study having supported a constructivist school of thought.

Following the above specifications, the constructivist epistemological underpinning was fitting for my study as it practically placed lecturers' voices at the centre of my discovery and enabled me to acquire a rich description of what is being investigated (Briod and Manninig, 2002). This in turn guided the analysis of the data. As the investigator, I was conscious of the participants making multiple meaning around the same issue through the description of their experiences. The planned design facilitated my interactive experience with the participants who

emphasized on their stories and allowed me to shed light on what motivated them to the teaching profession and their experiences within their career. This helped me to determine their state of satisfaction.

My Axiological position

Axiology explains how researchers in the course of reporting a study make their values known in the study and actively report their values and biases on the information they disseminate. My axiological position as a qualitative investigator in this study is this; I believe that my interaction with the respondents is subjective and dependent on my cognitive understanding of their experiences. As a matter of fact, since I construct meaning through my own understanding of the interview data, it is likely to be influenced by my own values. According to Creswell, (2003), social enquiry is value-bound or value-laden. As a constructivist researcher I therefore admit the value-laden nature of qualitative research and have reported how my values may interfere with the result of the study however I tried to consciously bracket my presupposed knowledge about the subject and avoided bias through some reflexive practices which I adopted to ensure credibility and validity of my finding. This includes peer review of my data analysis, external audit of the entire research process, participants' view and modification of the interview data and setting triangulation. These are further explained down in this chapter under validity and reliability of the study.

Methodology

Strauss and Corbin (1998, p3) view methodology as 'a way of thinking about and studying social reality' and method as 'a set of procedures and techniques for gathering and analysing data'. It is to be noted that under qualitative research methodology are different methods with each having differing tenets and procedures which according to Creswell, (2007) is referred to as research strategy. This includes ethnography, grounded theory, narrative, case

study and phenomenology. (1) With ethnography, the researcher immerses her/himself into the environment of the participants to get full understanding of goals, challenges, cultures, motivations, and themes that may emerge in the course of the study. (2) Grounded Theory on the other hand is designed to provide a detailed explanation or theory to the events. It allows for building of theories through primary interviews and existing documents based on the data available. (3) Narrative tends to weave together a combination of events, usually from just one or two participants to form a cohesive story from an in-depth or detailed interview with the view of telling the story that would illustrate instances in larger life or society. (4) Case Study involves a deep understanding through numerous types of data sources. This method was popularized by the Harvard Business School. (5) Phenomenology tends to give detailed description of an event, activity, or a phenomenon. Here, a combination of methods which includes watching videos, visiting places, and events, conducting interviews, and reading comments, are employed so that the researcher can have a deeper understanding on the meaning participants place on the concepts or events being investigated. In this research design, interview is the most common method of data collection. For phenomenological studies, Creswell, (2007) recommends 5 - 25 interviews. Also, In the process of analysis, it seeks to identify common themes. This study adopts a phenomenological qualitative strategy.

My choice of Phenomenology.

As the research title reveals, this study adopts a phenomenological approach. I was thoughtful in choosing a research strategy that resonates with my study interest as phenomenology attempts to probe what people experience in everyday life. My choice for phenomenology was to help reveal meaning behind people's experiences of the phenomena (Creswell, 2007). In this regard, the phenomenon is concerned with how lecturers make meaning of their experiences working in a Nigerian public university sector and what motivated

them to choose a teaching career. This is then used to determine their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Edmund Husserl has been credited with the coinage and introduction of the concept of phenomenology in the 20th Century (Cilesiz, 2011; Larsson and Holmström, 2007). This qualitative approach was based on academic disciplines of psychology and philosophy, and it has become a widely accepted method used in the description of human experiences especially in sociology, psychology, health sciences, and education research (Creswell 1998, Norlyk and Harder, 2010). Through the research of Husserl, he advocated that despite the existence of objects, human experiences and observation of these object can be reliable and accurate when presented through a conscious perception.

With this strategy, one of my interests was to demonstrate how complex meaning can be extracted out of simple unit of direct experience (Merriam, 2002, p. 7). I chose phenomenology so I could obtain a comprehensive description of lived experiences from where general meaning emerged (Creswell, 1998). Following my realization that phenomenological approach was suitable for my study, some suggestions by Moustakas (1994) as cited by Creswell (2007) was taken into consideration and adopted into my design. This facilitated the procedure of my study to explore what lecturers experience within their career setting as well as their career motive. The design ensures that:

- A phenomenon of interest to study is identified.
- The researcher recognizes and specifies the broad philosophical assumptions of phenomenology.
- Data are collected from the individuals who have experienced the phenomenon.
- The participants are asked two broad, general questions; what have you experienced in terms of the phenomenon? what context or situations have typically influenced or affected your experiences of the phenomenon?

- Data analysis occurs through organized “clusters of meaning” and from these clusters evolves both textural and structural descriptions of the experience which leads to a composite description that presents the “essence” of the phenomenon.

(Creswell 2007, pp. 60-62).

Data Collection, Method and Procedure

At this stage of the research, the researcher thinks about how to gather data from participants to answer the research questions and meet the purpose of the study. While this is a generic and primary component of all research, phenomenological principles see researchers also as part of the participants and suggests that their position, experiences and values be declared coupled with other activities they go through such as gaining access, gate keepers and reflexivity. The former is to ensure that they do not bring in their own experience to the foreground (Finley, 2012). These experiences may include prior knowledge and personal view about the topic (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008). Some authors argued the necessity of excluding researcher’s preunderstandings or preconceptions from what is being studied [(Ashworth, (1996), Henricson et al., (2006); Kendall, (2006)] whereas others argue, however, that it is not possible to exclude such preunderstanding as it is an essential condition for understanding the phenomenon (Johansson and Ekebergh, 2006). They therefore suggested that a critical approach of questioning the researcher’s preunderstanding and preconception can reduce their influence. This include continues reflection and self-questioning. As an important part of the research process, the researcher explains their presence, experiences around the subject and preconception in the process of ensuring reflexivity which is part of their role as researchers (Gibbs, 2018) therefore explaining my connection, prior knowledge and personal views about the topic may reveal if my disposition is included in the discovery (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008).

Reflexivity and the Research Process

Finley, 2012 defined reflexivity as ‘being thoughtfully and critically self-aware of personal and relational dynamics in the research and how these affects the research’. Miles, Huberman and Saldana, (2014) provide that Selecting a suitable and convenient reflexive process must include introspection, peer critique or supervised reflexivity and in operationalising reflexivity, the below questions need to be addressed:

1. How has my personal history influenced the choice of topic?
2. What are my personal value systems that may influence the process of research?
3. How do my gender, culture and professional background influence my positioning in this topic and my relationship with the participants?
4. What are the alternate roles I might be called upon to play while interacting with the participant, apart from my primary role as researcher?
5. What are the possible advantages that I have in terms of personal history and professional competence?
6. What might be the barriers that my personal history and professional competence can create during data collection?
7. How are the emerging data assimilating with my prior knowledge; making me revisit an earlier stance?

In addressing these questions, Anderson (2006) and Finley, (2012 p.319) provides that ‘qualitative researchers must unravel their biographies and explore how these might intersect with interpretations of field experiences’ therefore my biography regarding this research is as follows:

As a young human resource management graduate, my personal motivation and interest has always been on career development so, seeing myself as well as other people excel in career and achieving satisfaction and fulfilment has been one of my great interests. Although with no

work or teaching experience in Nigerian university sector, I have a passion to contribute to the research and development of Nigerian education following my few years of study in a Nigerian university. From my experience as a student, I have had some basic understanding about the system which according to Johansson and Ekebergh, (2006) may be an essential enabler to understanding the phenomenon under study.

While I was a student, I got to know about some of lecturers' plights. For example, some lecturers have always disclosed how poor their salaries are. I also observed that many of them were keen persuading students to buy their textbooks for their own personal financial benefits. They also did not show much concern or commitment towards students' development and teaching as I expected them to. These behaviours are motivational issues and were known to be part of the system during my years of study, and these partly motivated my interest in researching what motivated lecturers to the teaching profession and their experiences within the public university sector in order to understand the source of their (dis)satisfaction. Based on my findings for this study, I seek to make recommendations that will enhance lecturer's experiences, job satisfaction as well as ways to develop the education sector.

Now that my biography and experiences of the university system is known from a students' perspective, my prior knowledge is believed to influence the research process such as my interpretation to issues hence the reason for taking some reflective actions to reduce the impact of my presuppositions (if any) on the research. By doing so, Miles, Huberman and Saldana, (2014) provides that the actions I took to ensure that my study is valid, reliable, and void of my presuppositions should be made known. These are explained in detail in the validity and reliability section of this chapter. It includes peer review of my data analysis to ensure that I did not misinterpret participant's statements at will. I knew my background, experiences of the study context (as a former student in one of the universities under study), my identity as a Nigerian as well as my values may influence my understanding of the data, therefore after coding, I subjected my data to be peer reviewed to ensure we have similar understanding

regarding the codes I have already extracted before writing up my analysis and interpretation chapters. I also subjected my entire research processes to an external auditor who had always given me feedback including my supervisor who guided me throughout the research process. Furthermore, I got participant to review and modify their interview transcripts in case they find any mistake or want to add anything and lastly, I carried out my study in two universities to ensure setting triangulation.

Data collection site

My aspiration to contribute to the improvement of education in Nigeria through research and development and my keen interest in universities in southern part of Nigeria was because I am conversant with the universities as they are situated within my state of origin. Apart from me studying in one of the university institutions, an additional consideration for choosing the setting was my relationship with few lecturers who taught me during my studies and from whom I believed information could be sort easily without much barrier to my data collection process. Furthermore, I believe that there is more concern about lecturers' job satisfaction in public higher institutions than private as evident in literature which is one of the criteria for my choice of carrying out the research in public universities. Investigating into a public sector institution, I believed will likely attract or receive government attention than their private counterpart considering the impact on educational and national development. In this regard, criteria used in purposively selecting my research setting (university institutions) were due to these reasons; Choosing universities from the south was inspired by my reasoning that there is more professional pursuit in southern Nigeria compared to non-vocational pursuits as is the case in the north and east. For example, in southern part of Nigeria (Port Harcourt) where this study was carried out, people pursue professional development more because they are highly educated compared to northern Nigeria (The Hausa and Fulani tribe) where people engage more in agriculture and petty trading as a dominant source of occupation and the east

(The Igbo tribe) where there is more of business and entrepreneurship pursuit than people would go for a professional career (Falola, 2001). Although there may be a sampling bias by focusing only on universities in the south however the essence of this qualitative research was to select participants who are more immersed in a professional lecturing experience and from a region that best represent the study in terms of professionalism in a teaching career. This however does not mean that only indigenes of the southern part of Nigeria were chosen to participate in the study, in fact participants' ethnic/regional identity was disregarded because it was not important for the study.

Gaining Access

The nature of this research requires that I understand what participants experience and attribute meaning to their experiences through an in-depth interview. Before I proceeded with the interview process, institutional consents were sort in other to carry out this study, I gave both university authorities prior notice through the help of my gate keeper. The letter which was written under my university letter head entailed my intention to carry out a research in their University outlining the purpose of my study and the kind of information I would require from participants. I was thereafter given a written consent from the dean of students prior to my data collection as I allowed enough time to seek this permission. These consent letters were received through my gate keeper and was presented to my project supervisor. Before I planned my data collection phase for this research, participants were directly informed by the gate keepers in both institutions where I carried out my study and they agreed to participate and consented that their contacts be sent to me. Upon receipt of their contacts, I sort to know their availability, and this was confirmed via email.

Selection of Participants

This study adopted purposive sampling. This was adopted because of the need to get reliable information from participants who are perceived to be relevant and knowledgeable about the study. Going by its criteria, Creswell (2017, p119) states that; “they must be individuals who have all experienced the phenomenon and can articulate their lived experiences”.

While I seek to understand the lived experiences of lecturers by answering the research questions, I needed to know how many participants will be enough to study to make my findings valid. This brought about the determination of sample size or selection of participants as it relates to a phenomenological study. It is a culture in phenomenological research to use a small number of participants as the aim is to learn about the experiences of individuals (Moustakas, 1994). Phenomenology challenges the traditional linear relationship between ‘number of participants’ and value of research. It retains an idiographic focus, with 10 participants at the higher end of most recommendations for sample sizes [(Reid, Flowers, and Larkin, (2005), Smith et al., 1999)]. Similarly, Smith, and Osborn, (2003) has argued the advantages of smaller samples. Smaller sample thus sacrifice breadth for depth. This is because if the sample size is large, the researcher become overwhelmed by the vast amount of data generated and are not able to produce a sufficiently penetrating analysis (Smith, and Osborn, 2003). Looking at the phenomenological analysis literature base, collectively, the mean number of participants involved in an interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) research to date is fifteen (Reid, Flowers, and Larkin, (2005). Examples of studies that adopted the same methodology and their sample size include Raheemson, (2016), Molnar (2018) and Schuemann, (2014) having 20, 12 and 10 participants respectively. The sample size was therefore decided purposively comprising of 12 lecturers across two universities in Rivers state, Nigeria who have been lecturing for at least five years. These two universities were chosen

primarily to best develop a sample where multiple perspective would offer both depth and diversity as a setting triangulation (Creswell, 2007). Male participants were dominant in the study (10 male and 2 female) because they showed more interest and agreed to participate than women, two of which made excuses because they do not have time. Those were later replaced with men in order to avoid delays. The number of participants were tested against do-ability of the project plus saturation and considered rich to be able to convey ideas that answer the research questions until no additional concepts suffice. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in any additional perspective or information (Locke, 2001). According to Strauss and Corbin, (1998, p. 212), proper saturation occurs when “no new or relevant data seem to emerge regarding a category, the category is well developed in terms of its properties and dimensions, and the relationships among categories are well established and validated”. This is normally attained with two to ten participants if using a phenomenological method (Boyd 2001). Based on my study which was designed to utilize a single round face-to-face interview with 12 participants, I intended that I was going to broaden the sample size by 2 additional participants from each of the university making it 16 in total only if further clarification of information was needed to attain saturation (Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

Phenomenological Interview

Proceeding further to collect my interview data, I found myself in a dilemma due to the coronavirus pandemic. I could not afford to travel to Nigeria as borders were closed to all international flights meanwhile universities were on temporary lockdown. I had to consider carrying out a video interview or Wait till the lockdown is eased and borders open to international travel. I had to analyse these options and the impact they would have on my study and my life before taking an informed decision.

Face to face interview was planned however, it was not possible due to the corona virus pandemic, so I proceeded with the option of carrying out a video interview on zoom. I also recorded the interview using a different device in case I encounter any technical issue however, throughout the process, no technical issue was encountered. Irvine (2011) suggests that despite the bottle necks in interview methods, its implications on data quality must be put into consideration before proceeding with an option. In order to achieve the equivalence of breadth and depth of interview data in a qualitative study and to overcome the disadvantages of telephone interview (example speaker dominance and shortness of interview length) as established by Irvine (2011), I decided to adopt what Burnard (1994, p70) suggested. He suggested that to overcome the disadvantages posed by telephone interviewing, the interviewer should ‘...make some more general enquiries about the interviewee to set him or her at their ease. Many people take a little time to ‘warm up’ on the phone and such general conversation is equivalent to the initial questions that are asked at the beginning of a face-to-face interview to make the interviewee feel more comfortable’. So I had some initial random conversation in order to break the ice and familiarize myself with the participants before the actual interview. This was not part of the interview and was not recorded.

Two days before the interview, I sent them an email reminding them about the interview. I also attached a participant’s information sheet to the email to assure them of confidentiality as well as demanding their written consent to participate in the study. The content of the participant information sheet included a confidentiality clause which states that their identity will not be included in the report. Part of what they were assured of was the confidentiality of the video record which was deleted after the interpretation chapter of the thesis was written. The clause also contained their right to withdraw from the interview at any point if they so wish.

According to Seidman, (1998, p 3), the very essence of in-depth interviewing is the “interest in understanding the experience of other people and the meaning they make of that

experience". Creswell, (1998, p65) recommends that a phenomenological study typically involves a long interview with up to 10 participants. Evidence is yielded from first-person reports of life experiences (Moustakas, 1994).

Before I started my interview, I ensured to capture the 5 basic elements recommended by Moustakas (1994, p97) within my questions. He suggested that if these elements are met, the respondent should be able to give answers that are rich, vital and a substantive description of their experience about the phenomenon. The elements include:

1. How the experience affects the participants and what changes they associate with the experience.
2. How the experience affects significant others in their lives
3. The feelings that were generated from the experience.
4. The thoughts that stood out for them
5. What bodily changes or states they were aware of at the time

In addition, Moustakas, (1994) suggest that in phenomenological research, the question should have both social meaning and personal significance. During the process of interviewing, participants were asked to give more explanation and reason to anything they said that sounded emphatic. This was important because it unveiled newer insight from the stories they tell. Also, during the interview, the questions asked were unstructured and open ended. My focus was not to limit participants' responses to the scope of the study. I was rather conscious of possible responses that seem out of context as this could imply new findings to the subject of research. While this was the case, the response I received from respondents prompted further questions and this made the interview experience more flexible and interactive as there was no exact wordings to all participants.

All the interviews were completed within 2 weeks following participants' differing schedules. After the interview, to ensure accuracy and transparency all the participants were

sent a copy of their transcribed interview to verify for mistakes and clarify any discrepancy or any further comments they needed to add.

Piloting my study instrument

According to Lumsden (2007), All data collection instrument intended to be used by a researcher must be piloted prior to data collection and any changes made must be incorporated and then repiloted again until considered valid. The above procedure was considered to validate my interview questions. The main purpose was to evaluate the content of the interview questions by people external to my study yet have a common knowledge of it to see if the instrument is valid before the main interview. This gave me the opportunity to check if the questions I constructed represented my research questions and captured the phenomenon under study and also to see whether there is any area that may be sensitive to my participants or likely to cause them harm. I carried out a semi-structured interview which means that I did not follow the exact pattern of the questions piloted, however it guided me on how to construct my questions following participants' response to ensure that I address the three research questions of this study. Other follow up questions were asked based on the response I received.

In the process of piloting my interview questions, I consulted a research expert who evaluated the questions and gave me feedback which was incorporated before submitting it to my supervisor for further review and approval. Part of his feedback was that I should carry out the first two interviews as a demo then evaluate it in terms of any shortcomings and make improvement in subsequent ones. After my evaluation of the first two interviews which lasted for 40 and 47 minutes, there was no major challenge that needed to be corrected.

Before this was done, I ensured the research expert I consulted was the right person to pilot my study with as Shaw, (2010) encouraged a "reflective approach" where research instrument should be piloted by people who share similar characteristics with the respondents in order to ensure accountability. I therefore chose the expert because he is a Nigerian, had

previously lectured in a Nigerian university and now a lecturer and research supervisor in one of the Universities in the UK. After their review of the nature of interview questions and tips on interviewing, I incorporated their feedback into the questions and later, the interview. I re-sent the questions back to them for further validation and this time, the feedback was positive. Table 3.2 shows some of the questions that were used during the interview.

Interview Questions	Link to Research Question
Can you describe your career experiences prior to lecturing?	1
What drove you into a teaching profession? What was your reason for becoming a lecturer?	1
What are the experiences you can think of at the time you were given the lecturing job? For example, think about the recruitment processes you went through and how you were able to get the job.	2
As a lecturer can you describe the things you experience working in a public university sector?	2
Is there anything you think stands out about your experiences in your university?	2
Now, what do you feel about the profession? Do you feel passionate about lecturing considering all the experiences you have spoken about? Why?	1 & 2
Please can you describe the things you find satisfying from your experiences as a lecturer in the university where you teach?	3
Describe the things you find dissatisfying based on your experiences as a lecturer.	3
Considering what motivated you into lecturing, do you feel you are satisfied or dissatisfied? Why? Overall, if you are to compare, which one would you say you are more satisfied or dissatisfied with: The reason that motivated you into teaching OR the various experiences you spoke about? Please give reasons for your answer.	3
What would you suggest can be done to better your professional experience and enhance your job satisfaction as a lecturer? Think about all you have told me.	Recommendation

Table 3. 2: Interview questions and link to research questions

Data Analysis

Burns and grove (2010) define data analysis as a mechanism for reducing and organizing data to produce findings that require interpretation by the researcher. In this study, I adopted thematic analysis whereby data were openly coded into clusters of meaning.

Moustakas, (1994) suggest that the procedure for phenomenological data analysis must first horizontalize the transcribed data. This means carving out relevant statements to the topic or research questions and attributing equal value to every subject carved out of the transcription. By doing so, meaning units can be deduced or induced and are further translated into common clusters of themes. Again, from the clustered themes, description of experience is developed then interpretation are constructed to reflect the phenomenon which according to Morse, (1994) follows three cognitive processes: comprehending, synthesizing and recontextualizing.

One important aspect of phenomenological data analysis is the way the phenomenon is described and/or interpreted. Finlay, (2012) suggest that phenomenological reduction should be utilized as much as possible to render the researcher uninfluential whereby he brackets all previous understanding and past knowledge about the phenomenon he describes. These provisions guided my data analysis for this study.

Demographic data	Gender, age, years of teaching experience, academic background, Department/faculty
professional motive	Lecturing drive and motive
experiences	participant's experiences within public university context (personal & collective)
emotion	Feeling about experience
expectations	Participant opinion/advice/recommendation
satisfaction	Satisfying situations in which participants shows great delight
dissatisfaction	Dissatisfying situations in which participants are discontented
No Color	Not fitting any research question or category (Discoveries outside subject of the study)

Table 3. 3: Colour coded structure for thematic analysis

The first step I took was to slowly play the video record of the interview repeatedly while I transcribed into writing using a verbatim transcription. I then cleaned the data to clear up mistakes. The interviews yielded 197 pages of data. After reading through the data to familiarize myself with it, I then created the colour coded outline in table 3.3 to organize the data and situate it into coded clusters of meaning based on the research questions and other

important meaning structures I deduced while I was reading through the data. This was adopted at the second stage of Braun and Clarke (2006) model for thematic analysis in table 3.4. This made it easier to locate similar ideas and statements across the data. From each individual's description of meaning and experience, I constructed a composite description of the meanings (consolidated theme) as identified by each colour code. This was done up to two levels before the main theme emerged (See appendix 5), I then integrated them into a universal description of experience that represents the group as a whole (conceptual categories).

The entire transcript was analysed and coded manually. Inductive descriptive coding was used which is data driven entailing no coding frame. Interpretative coding was adopted where description seems to be lacking in depth (King, 2012). The reason for manual coding was because (1) it helped me to familiarize myself with the data by being more aware and immersed in the data. The advantage is that I became more closer to the data than I would otherwise have been if I had used NVIVO software. (2) because NVivo software is programmed to analyse data based on textual meaning using key words. As a phenomenological researcher, using NVivo means that my data analysis would be lacking as I was not only looking out for literal textual meaning, but also interpretation deduced from participants' experience which goes beyond mere surface description hence the adoption of interpretivist philosophy. In essence, despite the advantages of using software for data analysis, Dollah, Abduh, and Rosmaladewi, (2017) conducted research on the use of NVivo software for qualitative data analysis, one of their findings was that it cannot interpret data as a key drawback. Their result extends debates on thematic analysis of data as the software only assist researchers to identify common key words in documents or in data, classifying key words into category, clustering words to see the relationships among the most frequent lexis and use it as key themes. This may not have captured what participants feel about the experience and may not also give deeper meaning regarding the experience therefore limited in analysing

experiential data. A sample of how I manually coded my data using colours to group similar ideas that eventually translate into themes can be found in appendix 6.

Transcribing, coding and thematizing the entire transcript was time consuming as it took me up to nine weeks to complete. After the data was analysed, I look across each colour codes in table 3.3 to develop consolidated themes. Throughout the process, I followed the six steps recommended by Braun and Clarke (2006) in table 3.4. According to Creswell, (2007 p11), ‘language is not transparent or value free’ however, I tried to bracket myself by not allowing any presupposed judgement or assumptions into my view of the data hence subjected my codes and themes to a peer review process in other to ensure transparency and reflexivity. This happened at the fourth and fifth stage of Braun and Clarke (2006) process. In this process, I altered some codes, renamed some while I merged some of the themes that appeared to have common elements to form a new one based on the peer review. This continued till I finally had a more consolidated theme that described participants’ experiences. This is displayed in appendix 5. Finally, I extracted direct quotes from the data to be include in my report while I relate it back to ensure that it actually reflects the themes and research questions before writing up my report.

Familiarising with data	Transcribing data, reading and rereading the data, noting down initial ideas
Generating initial codes	Coding interesting features of the data systematically across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code
Searching for themes	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme
Reviewing themes	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire data set, generating a thematic map
Defining and naming themes	Ongoing analysis for refining the specifics of each theme and the overall story that the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme
Producing the report	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and

Table 3. 4: Thematic Analysis. Source: Adopted from Braun and Clarke, (2006, p. 87)

Writing up my Findings

Writing up the data means presenting and interpreting the findings. Van Manen (2004) provides that a phenomenological researcher is not only required to write down the result but to consistently reflect in order to exclude his presupposed values and judgement while writing and reaching deeper meaning. It is therefore advised to be done immediately after the data analysis to keep the researcher's mind refreshed about the data.

I started writing up my findings after I analysed the data, twelve themes emerged. This was categorised under four main thematic categories, this includes: choosing lecturing as a career, experiencing sectoral challenges, experiencing flexibility of process and desiring positive changes in public education. Beginning from the first thematic category, I presented the sub themes one after the other and included direct quotes from participants. I used the colour codes to find corresponding quotes that fit into each context and themes. Although it became tedious at some point. Down to the discussion chapter, I explained each theme and linked their ideas to existing literature and theories some of which were covered in earlier chapters. Also, as can be found in the fig 4.1 and the revised conceptual framework in fig 6.1, new topics emerged from the data.

Validity and Reliability of the Study

As a researcher, it is important to establish the credibility of my study in order to gain confidence in its result or findings. According to Creswell, (2007), this is quite different from the method used by quantitative researchers to confirm the validity of their study. Moustakas (1994' p75) provides; thus, 'in accordance to phenomenological principles scientific investigation is valid when the knowledge sort is arrived at through descriptions that make possible an understanding of the meanings and essence of experience'. According to Creswell and Miller (2000) and Creswell, (2007), validity or reliability of a qualitative research can be

established using either one or combination of the following methods: (1) prolonged engagement on the field, (2) Triangulation of data sources, (3) thick description, (4) peer reviews, (5) participants' view and (6) external audits.

My study adopted three of the strategies mentioned above. First to ensure credibility, I subjected my data collection instrument (interview questions) and the entire research process to an external audit by a research expert; a lecturer and project supervisor in one of the UK universities who have published within the context of my study. This provided me with a balanced understanding following modifications from his feedback. In addition to this, my supervisor's comments and feedback were noted and incorporated throughout the research process. Secondly, participants were sent copies of their individual transcribed interviews to correct any mistake made and clarify any discrepancies before the transcripts were coded and analysed however only eight out of the twelve participants made some minor corrections which were added to the transcripts. According to Jones, (2002, p.469), This process helps researchers to "check their own subjectivity and ensure the trustworthiness of their findings". Thirdly, I knew my background, experiences of the study context (as a former student in one of the universities under study) and values may influence my giving meaning to the data so after coding, I subjected my data to peer review to ensure we have similar understanding regarding the codes I extracted before writing up my analysis and interpretation chapters. Sensitive information such as participants' names were deleted to avoid identification during the process. Following this, some codes and description of themes were modified as there were few discrepancies in our description of codes and themes. Lastly, setting triangulation was utilized whereby I collected data from lecturers of two different universities within the same region (Rivers state) in Southern part of Nigeria. This was an attempt to develop a sample where multiple perspectives would offer both depth and diversity known as setting triangulation (Creswell, 2007). All these were done to ensure credibility of the findings and reflexivity.

My Ethical Considerations

Gajjar, (2013) define ethics as ‘a method, procedure, or perspective for deciding how to act and for analysing complex problems and issues’. I was concerned not just about the interview process but putting the entire research process and result into consideration; The impact of my own actions on the result of my study was important to me. As such, the participants in my study and those who the research will benefit needed to be assured that I was going to be ethical in the way I carried out the interview and the entire study. Some of my basic concern was to ensure that my actions reflect ethical principles through confidentiality, Honesty, respect, and justice so as to promote trustworthiness of my research process (Walker, 2007). Following this, I considered a suitable site on the day of the interview which was in the comfort of my room devoid of third-party intrusion. The interview lasted for between 45 to 60 minutes and were video and audio recorded which the participants were informed earlier about. Again, in terms of confidentiality, the participants for this study were assured that all information provided will be kept strictly confidential. All Information obtained from them were kept safe and passworded in my computer and subsequently the interview records were deleted after the data was analysed and interpreted. It was also important to respect the views and decision of everyone who participated in this research. In ensuring that their choices are respected, all participants had the right to withdraw from participating in the research study at any point in time as they wish. Respect for intellectual property is also one of the ethical considerations that was duly observed throughout the research process as all intellectual materials used for this research were referenced accordingly using the Harvard referencing method as recommended by my university. Also, I was honest and open minded. I ensured that no information was obtained under duress. By this, all ethical protocols were duly observed during the data collection process. Their names were also not made known while writing up my report for confidentiality reason. Approval was sort were needed for example from the two

universities involved in this study. I was honest to my participants by unveiling all necessary information they needed about my study both by words of mouth and on the participant's information sheet which I sent via email. I also answered all their questions in an honest manner before the interview were carried out. Furthermore, I was bound not to commit any negligence by being careful with the research activities. I took integrity seriously by keeping promises and agreements, being sincere and ensuring that my thoughts and actions were consistent.

Summary

This chapter presented the methodological design and made known my paradigmatic and philosophical position. By this, I established my ontological, epistemological, methodological, and axiological beliefs to reveal the prevailing association of these beliefs in relation to reality on lectures experiences and professional. This was to establish that truth is ascertained through a current worldview. Putting all these into consideration, I aligned with a constructivist paradigm and interpretivist philosophy which was justified by the nature of my research. Also, I adopted a qualitative research procedure with phenomenology as my research strategy. This entails the quest to understand the lived experiences of people regarding the phenomenon and how these experiences influence their job satisfaction. My decision to use unstructured interview as the most appropriate method to collect my data was also justified and was linked to the nature of my research questions, methodology and what I intended to achieve. The samples were established purposefully and in the process of data collection, the right steps were also taken to ensure validity and credibility of my findings while I was also ethical throughout the research process.

Chapter Four

Findings

Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis of data which was collected through qualitative phenomenological interviews. Techniques common to phenomenological research and thematic inductive reasoning guided my data analysis. This includes putting aside measuring instruments as well as knowledge of prior research about the topic under investigation (Wertz et al, 2011) and moving from specific to a more general experiences of participants' (King and Brooks, 2016). Thematic analysis was used using inductive coding process (i.e having no predefined coding frame). Despite using description, interpretative coding was adopted where description appears to be lacking in depth (King, 2012). In this chapter, I use a high culmination of lecturer's voices (indented quotes) to focus on the perspective of their stories to offer richness of my analysis. I present this chapter in a way that equally reflects my own description and/or interpretation followed by samples of the participant's story. Although not certain that my presuppositions were completely excluded however credibility and transferability measures were taken to assure its internal/external validity and trustworthiness as discussed in the methodology chapter.

This study investigates what predominantly motivates lecturers to the teaching profession in Nigerian public universities. It goes further to finding out what they experience working in Nigerian public university and whether these inform their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. My quest to first investigate which career motive is predominant among lecturers in Nigerian public universities and their experiences working in these public universities makes this research unique from others. This is because their career motive and what they experience can be a source of their satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Significantly, this research will contribute to knowledge and organizational practice by guiding concerned

management and public university policy makers to make informed decisions concerning the design and implementation of strategies to promote lecturers' satisfaction and ensuring educational development. In turn, it will help improve learning and development specifically in Nigerian education and also serve as a career guide for potential lecturers.

In this chapter, I focus on the 12 lecturers which I interviewed from two Nigerian public universities who shared their professional motivation and their career experiences. Due to word restriction, each individual participant stories were not included in the report other than their profile and background. I presented a cross-case of the themes that emerged from the individual stories. Displayed in figure 4.1 is a thematic map from my analysis. The findings shown in this chapter flows out of the clustered codes in appendix 5 which I developed into this thematic mapping using its higher-level codes. It forms the basis of my findings in this chapter and discussion in chapter 5 where I link the various findings to already existing literature, theories and concepts.

Figure 4. 1: Thematic Mapping showing four main thematic categories

Participants' Profile and Background

1st participant was a male lecturer who has spent 6 years lecturing in the department of Art. He studied business administration in the same university where he is currently lecturing. Regarding his career, he never intended to go into lecturing however he accepted a lecturing job following many unsuccessful job applications in other industries which persisted for over 5 years. He is aged 37.

2nd participant was a male lecturer who has officially spent 9 years teaching in one of the universities in Southern Nigeria. He studied mathematics and computer science and majored in mathematics. He has been tutoring way back from his secondary school days and officially got employed as a lecturer immediately after his master's degree. He shows much passion about teaching as according to him he wouldn't have afford to choose any other career path. He is 35 years of age.

3rd participant was a female lecturer with 12 years of experience in one of the government owned universities in Rivers state. She studied business administration and taught the department of social sciences. She has a master's degree in human resource management. She falls between the ages of 40 -50 years.

4th participant was a male lecturer. He is 48 years old. He has been lecturing in one of the public universities in Rivers state for 10 years. He teaches in the department of mechanical engineering. He obtained his PhD in material integrity and instrumentation. He started his career as a technician in an automobile firm before he decided to go into teaching. As a workshop coordinator, he stayed there for about 2 years plus before he applied for a lecturing job while he was studying for his PhD.

5th participant was a male lecturer with 7 years of teaching experience. Before his career at his present university, he had a teaching experience in an adult education centre for mature students. He is 39 years old and has a master's degree in mass communication and a bachelor's

degree in linguistics and communication studies. He currently teaches in the department of linguistics and communication studies.

6th participant was a male lecturer in one of the public universities in Rivers state. He has 5 years of lecturing experience. He teaches strategic management in the department of business administration. He has a master's degree in educational management and a bachelor's degree in business education. He is 35 years old. He identifies himself as a disciplinarian and committed to his career, a goal-oriented person with a proactive attitude. He started his lecturing journey immediately after he obtained his master's degree in 2014.

7th participant was a male lecturer in one of the universities in Rivers state. He identifies as a molecular scientist. He has 5 years of teaching experience. He has a bachelor's degree in biology and a master's degree in molecular Science. He teaches in the Molecular Science department. He is 51 years of age.

8th participant was a female lecturer who lectures in one of the public universities in Rivers state. She has been lecturing for 7 years and she is 42years old. She has a bachelor's degree in science laboratory technology and master's in health science. She is currently undergoing her PhD (as at 2020) in the same university where she works.

9th participant was a male lecturer in one of the public universities in Rivers state. He has 10 years of lecturing experience. He studied medicine and surgery and he is currently a medical doctor. He has previously been working in the hospital but later switched to a lecturing career. He self identifies as being very passionate about saving lives in any way possible and research oriented. He is 52 years of age.

10th participant started his lecturing career in 2015 in one of the public universities situated in Rivers state. He has previously taught in secondary schools before his PhD. He enrolled for his PHD in 2013 and eventually was employed as a lecturer in the same university. He teaches in the marketing department. He self identifies as a Christian and appears to have a strong Christian religious value. He is 43 years old.

11th participant was a male lecturer with 10 years of teaching experience in one of the universities in Rivers state. He studied banking and finance and holds a master's degree in accounting. He teaches in the accounting department. He worked in the banking sector for 2 years as an accountant after his master's degree and thereafter came into the education sector as a lecturer. He is aged 50 and self identifies as an educationist who has passion for education and aims to contribute to improving lives.

12th participant is a Naval architect, he lectures in one of the public universities in Rivers state Nigeria. He has five years of lecturing experience. He teaches in the department of architecture, and he is aged 40. He self identifies as someone who loves to give back to society hence the reason, he left the offshore field to the classroom as a lecturer.

Findings - Cross cases

My study was to investigate the predominant motive that drive lecturers into the teaching profession (professional motivation), what they experience in their career working in a Nigerian public university sector and whether these inform their state of job (dis)satisfaction. In this subsection of this chapter, I focused on the cross-case analysis of the themes that emerged in my findings as seen in table 4.1. This contains the interviews I carried out with twelve lecturers from two public universities in southern Nigeria who shared their professional motives, their career experiences and what informs their (dis)satisfaction respectively. In table 4.1, the themes that emerged were linked to the initial conceptual framework and their satisfaction or dissatisfaction was indicated against their career motive and each of what their experiences entailed.

Themes across twelve interviews

	Themes	Participants												Link to conceptual framework	Source of Satisfaction	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
1	Choosing Lecturing as a career															
a	Passion to make an impact on students	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-Passion to impact	Yes
b	absence of personal & career expectation	x	x							x	x				- Economic condition - Work environment	No
2	Experiencing Sectoral Challenges															
a	Salary issues	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-salary & funding	No
b	Corruption	x	x	x	x								x		New	No
c	Lack of development	x	x	x									x		-Work environment/ -infrastructure	No
d	Poor working condition, facilities & environment	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-Work environment/ -infrastructure -Promotion	No
3	Experiencing flexibility of processes and work															
a	Employment process flexibility	x	x	x											New	No
b	Work process flexibility			x	x										New	No
4	Desiring positive changes in public education													Not applicable		
a	Increase pay, funding and pension	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
b	Government support		x		x				x		x					
c	Improving work environment/conditions	x		x	x						x		x	x		
d	Implement policies & develop education					x								x		

Table 4. 1: Themes across twelve interviews

In the process of my analysis, choosing lecturing as a career is the main theme (conceptual category) under which there are two sub themes. The first is; Passion to make an impact on students. This depicts how people choose the teaching profession for societal impact, the second sub theme is absence of personal and career expectations depicting that because of not having what one wants makes them go for a lecturing career. Passion to impact the lives of people stood out to be the core and predominant reason people cited as the reason why they considered lecturing as a career while the second sub theme is a secondary teaching motivation.

Furthermore, the second conceptual category is experiencing sectoral challenges, this implies the generic negativities that lecturers experience across public universities in Nigeria as a sectoral disadvantage. There are four sub themes that emerged under this main theme, it includes: salary issues, corruption, lack of development and poor work conditions, facilities and environment.

The third category of themes emanate from the experiences lecturers find to be positive and motivating to them. It is Experiencing flexibility of (employment) processes and work. The sub themes under this include employment process flexibility and work flexibility.

The last category of themes appears as lecturers' quest for a change or career expectations based upon their negative experiences working in the public university sector. It is Desiring positive changes in public education. This includes increase pay, funding and pension, government support for research and development, improving work environment and conditions, and implement policies & develop education.

1. Choosing Lecturing as a career

a. Passion to make an impact on Students

Following participants' stories, Passion to impact the lives of people emerged as the predominant theme and motive for the teaching profession. During my interview, all twelve participants said something that connects to their intention to make an impact in the lives of students through impartation of knowledge. They also show how passionate they are about it. Each participant mentioned at least three of the following nine sub themes: Imparting knowledge, impacting students, social impact, moral impact, discovering potential, academic assistance, enlightening people, Passion to teach and love for teaching. These nine sub themes had several repetitions by the twelve participants of which its repetitiveness was used as a

determinant or dominant factor of the main theme (passion to impact) and considered the predominant motive for the lecturing profession or career.

The passion to impact represents a common description of participants' drive in choosing a teaching career. The words "impart" and "impact" were used quite often across all the cases to describe their desire to teach and add value to others which is relative to their "passion" being the level of intensity of which they so desire and enjoyed teaching. In other words, it shows that they exhibit the quest to contribute to people's lives through teaching. From their description, I deduced that their intentions for lecturing were mostly internally driven, this is because they were not primarily dependent on external circumstances or influences that they may have faced or are currently facing for example unemployment however, the circumstances under which they got into employment as lecturers differ although with few similarities across cases which will be discussed as I proceed.

Regarding the passion to impact, for example 1st participant explained that he did not only intend to go into teaching just because of his love for the profession but because he wanted to impact lives by way of building people's morals and contributing to their knowledge.

If I say my love for teaching it will be an understatement, actually my love to impart in people, knowledge wise and morally.

8th participant also demonstrated that what brought her into the career is to impart into people.

Being able to impart what I have to the next person and generation has always been a motivation to me.

3rd participant's story also reveals that she has passion for teaching irrespective of the fact that the profession does not come with so much motivation in terms of pay and the work environment when compared to other white-collar jobs. For her, passion was what drove her. She has this passion because she derives an inner satisfaction from teaching and advocates that people need to come to the knowledge of what is trending and this can be achieved by being a channel through which they acquire such knowledge.

Actually I wanted to be a teacher from the beginning though it's not so motivating based on salary and work environment because each and every one of us wants to have the white collar job, jobs like the oil firm jobs...but I really desired to teach and I had and still have the passion for it. This actually was the first thing I considered when I thought of going into this career.

According to the 7th participant, his motivation towards the teaching profession was driven by his passion. Passion to teach and leave an impact in the lives of people is what he has always thought of achieving. The same thing applies to 4th participant who followed his passion and zealously to impact people and went into lecturing. From 4th participant's story, he showed the amount of impact he has contributed to people's lives. He said in his department of mechanical engineering alone, he can account for students whom he has personally mentored through to their career and they are all currently successful.

So I went into teaching because I had the passion to always want to impart knowledge....Yeah over time in our department Mechanical Engineering I've been able to produce very good students, 3 or 4 times during graduation in Uniport. I currently have 4 best students from mechanical engineering and 2 which I can boldly say I personally mentored into their career and till today they are doing so well

Also, 2nd participant who has been tutoring right from his secondary school days said he knew he was going to be lecturing. With the main purpose of impacting the lives of people, he started developing himself from secondary school. This is because he needed to change the psychology of students who have a phobia for mathematics being his subject area. To him, imparting knowledge requires that you first change the psychology of people about how difficult the subject is which he has been able to achieve over the years.

professionally I saw that lecturing was for me right from secondary school. I'm lecturing because it's something I decided to do long ago... I'm impacting, knowing that I am here to change the psychology of students when it comes to my subject area.

It is also evident that participants' initial career aspirations were majorly not in line with lecturing as their commentary suggest that it was born out of realization. Many of the participants indicated that they never aspired to take a career path in teaching but it was rather something they realized that they could do during their undergraduate studies in the university. Six out of the twelve participants started picking interest in lecturing during their graduate level and started harnessing the idea by tutoring others. Just like in the case of 10th participant who started building his teaching capabilities in the university, many others also did the same. 10th participant said;

But honestly speaking teaching was never my goal while getting into the university, it was while I was in the university that I saw that there is a need for me to remain in this part.

Subsequently, findings following participants' career aspirations also revealed an uncommon trend and differences in their employment history irrespective of their career motive. What this means is that while four out of the 12 participants including 1st participant, 2nd participant, 5th participant and 6th participant confirmed having lecturing as their first job, others did not. In addition, one of the participants (9th participant) said that his aspiring to choose this career path was also based on his family's educational background because his parents were in education and in order to keep the trend in the family going, he too decided that it would be a good idea to take the same career path.

I'm from an academic background, my father and my mum so I've always looked out for an opportunity to be on the same path to impact on young people. Though originally, I loved the aspect of coming into academia to teach but at the same time I needed to go into the industry first...

One significant aspect of participants' career motivation is that many of the lecturers I interviewed express the importance of being in a career that adds value to them. However,

lecturing is the opposite because it is not as prestigious as other careers. The 6th participant believe that teaching is one of the most undervalued careers or professions in Nigeria and because of this, it is not attractive to young folks. he contended:

There's practically nothing to admire that will make you want to be a teacher tomorrow but when you go to the bank, the law firm and other places you see nice clean cars owned by these persons you want to be like them so when lecturers are almost neglected in the society they don't have anything to make the profession enticing, you find it difficult that young folks wouldn't want to come in

On the contrary, the 4th participant said something different from many other participants. He believes that many university lecturers resort to the teaching career not for the love for it as they say but rather due to not having any other choice of career because of unemployment and in some cases, not having the kind of job they initially desired such as working in oil companies. He said:

As a matter of fact, keep the salary aside, many go into teaching as a result of frustration because unemployment is real, probably they were expecting to be in one wonderful oil company earning millions and when they look left and look right and can't find themselves in one of these companies they fall back to teaching and so teaching to some lecturers was the last resort so we find out that many of these lecturers don't go into teaching because of the love and flare for it but because of frustration and trust me what you do out of frustration you can't do the best out of it. Because you are in teaching out of frustration you always tend to lash out your frustrated mind on the students. You didn't go into teaching for the love and so when you see students greed check many of them it's actually because those big companies that they were aiming out for didn't call out for them, so they go into teaching as the last resort

b. Absence of personal and career expectations

Out of the twelve participants interviewed, four of them described some element of lack which literally indicates the unavailability of what they initially wanted or expected leading them to a career in teaching. Under this theme one participant spoke about being idle and bored following years of unemployment, one spoke about poverty and the other two spoke about the monotony of their previous job routine. All these they attributed to what made them choose a lecturing career.

From the aspect of idleness, 1st participant added to this theme when describing his employment experience which evolved around his lack of employment (inability to secure a job after his undergraduate studies and national service). From the description of his experience, 1st participant took the lecturing job out of boredom after years of staying at home upon completing his NYSC and three years' post- master's graduation. By then, he had already applied to several jobs in different industries, but none was successful, and it was very worrisome for him as he felt idle doing nothing through these years. When he eventually applied to a lecturing job in one of the universities in the southern part of the country, he got called for an employment and based on the fact that he had no other job he accepted to go with lecturing.

I wasn't doing anything actually before I went into teaching I was idle which as a matter of fact not the best for anyone but that was where I found myself.... So I had to cease the lecturing opportunity when it came.

The 2nd participant also contributed to this theme as part of his story indicated that he lacked financial resources meaning that he was driven by poverty into the teaching profession. Poverty indicates lack of finance to take care of basic human needs. Beginning from when 2nd participant was in secondary school up to university, his parents were not buoyant enough to pay for his tuition fees. He said he struggled through school to cater for himself and through this process one of the things that helped him was that he arranged for tutorials with students

with the sole purpose of gathering money to sponsor himself through university. Being a bright student also helped him to achieve this couple with his love for teaching.

I have been tutoring back from secondary school. The passion all grow from lack of basic tuition fees. In fact I would say that was the beginning and why I drew my passion for teaching. At that time it was really difficult to pay my fees so I tutor junior students and they pay me for it and that was how I managed to pay my tuition fees. This continued till my university days and by God's grace I graduated. After graduation, I ventured into lecturing and that's how I started. how long I can't say specifically because it all started from Secondary School, but I loved teaching....

From the totality of 2nd participant' story about his professional motivation, it can be said that his motive for becoming a lecturer was driven by a combination of his love for teaching as an intrinsic factor and the need for financial resources to pay his tuition fees which is an extrinsic factor. Firstly, he nurtured a career in teaching because he was money driven even though his drive for money was not intentional but rather to enable him to pay his tuition fees. This does not mean that he did not have a genuine desire and passion for the profession.

Furthermore, 9th participant and 8th participant opine that they ventured into the teaching profession because their previous job routine lacked variety. This lack of variety stems from the repetitive operational pattern associated with their career which they needed to change to another career that will enable them to explore and grow without sticking to a particular work routine. This called for a job that is challenging in nature and has variety to give them a sense of satisfaction which they found in teaching. According to 9th participant;

Basically, as a medical doctor before teaching I was basically involved in the routine of seeing patients, routine because it's what we do virtually every other time,...so it became too monotonous and I'm from an academic background my father and all that... And so prior to my teaching experience is the routine thing we do, there is no difference, there is no future in it .But in the teaching profession here now you have a future, you

go into research I'm a research person too I like teaching I want to see generations of doctors coming through me and I see my students become doctors and they are doing well.

From their stories, they both were in the medical profession. 9th participant was a practicing medical doctor while 8th participant a health scientist who spent all her time working in the lab. According to 8th participant, her daily job was repetitive and she didn't have the opportunity to learn new things. As a result. The work was boring for her, this made her consider teaching because it allows her the opportunity to learn new things while she impacts lives. From both stories, adding value to oneself becomes one significant characteristic and a driving force of the lecturing profession not only to students who do the learning but lecturers like 9th participant and 8th participant desired to also learn in the process hence the reason they quit from the job that lacked variety.

...I found out that it is kind of repetition of same process like every other day you go to the hospital, same thing you did yesterday you are going to do it today same procedure and so it was quite boring along the line for me I needed something of an adventure like something I don't really know what is next so that is what made me go into lecturing.

An aspect of lecturers' stories that carved out a new niche of meaning of what drove them into the profession is the context and circumstances in which their desire to teach occurred. In general, they advocate that the passion to impact lives was a motivation for their career choice; however, analysis of their different context reveals other intentions. For example, 12th participant realized that there is a deficiency of lecturers who has direct industry experience in the education sector and so he felt that it will be necessary to fill that gap since he has a wealth of industry experience to transfer into the system. This partly ignited his quest to go into teaching as he asserts;

I went through the university of course and I knew how terrible and amazing some lecturers were and I realized that the difference between both was the industrial experience. The lecturers that were struggling and boring had never had any experience in the industry in that particular field so I decided that with my experience let me give back, let me make lecturing interesting, let me train more people you know that's it.

2. Experiencing Sectoral Challenges

a. Salary issues

This theme emerged as participants discussed what they experience within the lecturing career in their various government owned universities, all the participants said something that connects to the poor salary structure that is prevalent within Nigerian public universities and also extends to all careers within education. The tune of their voices and the emphasis they place on salaries when discussing this subject shows disappointment and indicates that pay is one of the most important need to them. As part of this theme, the 1st participant opined that sufficient pay is a problem in Nigerian public universities. Consequently, participants provided an established connection between this issue and other financial limitations found within the education sector, for example funding of education; They believe that because of deficient funding, there is not much financial circulation within the education sector which then affects salaries. Lecturers receive insufficient pay and there is a wide disparity when compared to what other professionals are being paid in other sectors. From their stories, they also reveal that they experience strikes as a result of government delay in salary payment among other issues. As part of this theme, 1st participant asserts that:

The salary rate are not constantly growing. Day-to-day you see some other sectors and administration tend to grow they tend to increase but those of us who are lecturers those in the teaching field their salary most times are just in the base for the past 10 years no salary increment. at the end of the day we begin to experience strike here and there, students who are supposed to finish by 4 years now begin to graduate 5 or 6 years wasting most of their precious time in education.

Similarly, 2nd participant also expressed disappointment in the fact that lecturers' salaries do not meet up with some other industry professionals such as bankers, doctors, including politicians.

It's quite unfortunate that in Nigeria lecturers are among the lowest earners. yet all other professionals pass through us like bankers, the senators, doctors, lawmakers and all the politicians so to speak yet they earn far more than what they give us. It is quite unfortunate.

The 11th participant on the other hand also commented on the huge disparity in the payment structure within the public sector of which he believes that lecturers are poorly paid. He added;

you see those of them in government they are making huge amount of money, some of them do not even have their first degree but they are making hell out of this particular money but we lecturers are being treated as if we have no place in the society

The 3rd participant also added that in spite of insufficient pay, payment delays are common in the public universities whereby staff don't get paid sometimes for up to 3months

We are being paid even if sometimes the payment delays and even when we know there's room for increment they will delay it and sometimes this takes up to three months.

In regard to the issues of salary which they face. 4th participant acknowledged that although low pay is one of the disadvantages they face however, he believes that when passion becomes a primary motivation and prerequisite for the career, it helps people not to be too keen about the low salary rate.

Another thing is that the payment is not too satisfactory however if the passion is there the pay will just flow.

On the contrary, 6th participant does not think that with the poor salary rates and other salary issues they face that passion alone can be a motivator to him. According to him there are instances when he does lack motivation to even go to lectures because he doesn't feel moved by the salary, he is being paid which does not last till the next month and notwithstanding the difficult encounters some students give.

In our universities lecturers are poorly paid and it's not motivating us in any way to even go to lecture because when you go into the classroom you will go home with little or nothing and your salary can't meet the next month.

Yet 8th participant, being the only female lecturer that was interviewed, believes that job security is a consideration for her being in the university sector despite the low salary rate and associated issues she faces. She cited an occasion where she rejected job offers due to the fact that they were less secure than lecturing and that it would have been easier to loose them. And for that reason, her experience with the issues of salary has not been a deterrent from loving her teaching profession.

...If I had taken the jobs in Intels or in Diamond Bank then by now I would have been gone I wouldn't have had any job irrespective of the fact that the pay then was lucrative so you see permanence in the lecturing job is important, being in this profession even if I am being poorly paid I don't want to leave because one; I love the profession and secondly my job is permanent.

Still on the salary issues 7th participant also assert that for seven years there has not been any salary increment till recently when the government increased lecturers' salary with an insignificant amount and in spite of this, there is lack of transparency as to what exactly was the amount added due to several ministerial protocols.

For 7 years it has just been same salary base, same grade, same level it's just recently that a pinch was added just a pinch from the pocket of the government was added to the salary which we really don't know because we are all expecting the 30% minimum wage but just a pinch was added so nobody could calculate the exact amount that should have been added to our main salary.

As a result of the salary issues they face, it is common to see lecturers contracting with different universities to teach as freelancers in order to boost their income or resort to owning petti businesses to augment their salary alongside their permanent lecturing job. 9th participant said:

Like I told you there are many options. It's lucrative in itself because you could be a freelancer going into as many institutions as you want to if you have the strength and the capacity to do so. For me I have other investments I have, other things I'm doing which for safety sake I will not mention in this interview so people wouldn't think I have all the millions in the country so there are other things I do all because the salary they give us is too small.

Generally, from their stories when asked, they believe that the poor salary rate in the education sector is as a result of the lack of funding by the government as there is not much financial circulation to run the education sector which then affects salaries.

The kind of funds they are getting to run the system is one of the reasons for the ridiculous pay rates we are given so that actually make the body ASUU to take certain decisions. That's why sometimes we go on strike for 1 month, 6 months and even a year.

Participants' views on the recurring salary issues, indicates that proper funding of the education sector is lacking therefore many of them suggested that if the government can properly fund the education sector, then some of the issues including that of salaries will likely be tackled.

So if government can properly fund at least the education system, we'll get the best out of it.

(b). Corruption

Corruption is one of the common experiences lecturers are exposed to within their career in the public university sector. Participants described different situations and forms in which corruption exists in their universities and within the education sector. Ideas emerging through analysis included participant commentary regarding four key areas of corruption. This includes nepotism, bribery, tribalism and politics and political influence. There is a consistent thread in this area that indicates nonconformity with organizational practices and procedures and depicts that those who are in power or higher positions choose to do things their own way without being questionable. participants' commentary depicts that the entire four categories of corruption exist at the management or organizational level including tribalism, nepotism and politics and bribery while at the lower operational level involving lecturers and students, only bribery is seen to be common.

There is corruption in the system, students giving bribes to lecturers or lecturers asking students to give bribes and all that.

One of the common names participants mentioned when describing bribe received by lecturers in their Nigerian parlance is "sorting". One participant captured this when he said;

Yeah...before I forget, most lecturers also take sorting like I know some of my colleagues who do take sorting, but for me I don't.

Participants' stories also reveal that within their career in the university, most things are done based on man-know-man, a term used to describe favouritism in the system based on who you know (nepotism). One participant said lecturers contract out their jobs in exchange for part of their salaries and in some cases such arrangements are made with the employer. This does not happen if they do not have some personal contact. He said there are situations where in order to secure a lecturing job, people make payment to bribe those in charge of the recruitment process and in some cases, they request to be paid monthly as soon as the beneficiary receives their salary.

In fact, in this sector, its mostly about 'man-know-man'. Yeah you must know somebody and then the person in most cases will ask you to bring something to cover your back, I mean someone taking all your lectures and you give them certain percent of your salary monthly. In fact, one of my friend who is teaching in....., he got the lecturing job and at some point he had to quit, he was asked to give part of his salary and after running it for some time he had to quit because the thing was no longer in his favour.

Another participant added to this theme by saying that in addition to performance criteria, indigenous differences and man-know-man are considerable criteria in his university when it comes to lecturers' promotion. Based on this, they (management) decide who they will promote and who shouldn't be given promotion.

...then, sometimes in most cases for you to be promoted, the ranks and files in the system, the management do it based on man-know –man, indigenous differences will come in and all that.... The bottom line is that we see this corruption everyday

Another participant finds this very worrisome as he asserted that nepotism is used to make decisions for promoting lecturers;

The promotion aspect in Nigeria is based on man-know-man, so you must know somebody to get to the position you want which is very worrisome.

One participant explained that he was pained due to management using tribalism as one of the core criteria for promotion and certain position in the university during recruitment. According to him, he is among those who experienced discrimination on the basis of not being an indigene. This level of tribalism is displayed by the university administration in situations where certain employment and promotions are given to indigenes of the state where the university is situated even though he sees himself to be more qualified and disciplined for such role but because of indigenous difference they wouldn't consider other tribes who are not indigenes of the state.

In the aspect of administration of the school institution it's quite challenging because we find situation where some employment and some promotions are given based on indigenous criteria's and you find people in positions and teaching some courses that ordinarily they are not disciplined or have the tutorship to teach and if you find such persons teaching such courses probably because of certain incentives that comes along with it and you begin to have this pain as a non-indigenous lecturer because you know you are probably more qualified and better off but it doesn't come to you because you find yourself in situations where such opportunities are given to indigenous lecturers from that state or vicinity.

A participant's commentary also reveals that corruption in the education sector in Nigeria exist in terms of politics and politicizing academic positions where partisan affiliations are used to appoint higher positions within the university. According to one of the participants, he said:

Our education system is so corrupt that it is constantly being used as a political tool for greed, partisan and the rest of it.... we shouldn't have someone lead a particular school as a result of political parties.

The 10th participant also made the following assertion that he believes that the management are trying their best to tackle corruption however it requires a joint effort in terms of one goal and vision to achieve result:

Coming to the management of the school well it's quite unfortunate that there are a lot of politics here and there we are in a system whereby tribalism actually springing up in every social environment so the management are actually doing their best but sincerely speaking I think we just need to have one mind, one goal and vision in whatsoever thing we are pursuing so we can get the best out of it.

All six participants who mentioned corruption admit not being involved in these corrupt practices however they share their stories on how it affects them as lecturers. One of the participants said he first had a difficult time accepting and blend into the system. He said that most mass failures in students' examination emanate from their believe that lecturers are always there to take "sorting" and because of this they refuse to read their books and in turn, it has a resultant effect on the lecturers in such a way that widens their responsibilities going back to lecture and remarking examination scripts of those that failed earlier and having much more larger audience during lectures.

some students no longer read their books and sometimes you see mass failure everywhere because they believe that if they sort other lecturers, it wouldn't be difficult to do the same across border for them to pass all their courses and this is what is killing our education system....of course you would have more students added to your register because those who failed would always carryover the course and then your classes will be like sardine ...you will have over populated students in one class.

Another participant who identified as having core Christian value said that colleagues have tried to rebel against him when advising against corrupt practices and which has also led to them calling him names because he tries to stick to his Christian values while speaking against corrupt practices. While some people blame those that engage in these corrupt practices,

others lay blame on the government saying that the level of corruption within the system is as a result of the government failure to carry out their responsibilities and not having any value for education in the country.

(c). poor working condition, facilities, and environment

All twelve participants described characteristics associated with their career environment and the university system showing that the conditions under which they work are not as conducive as expected. Under this theme, participants complained of not being provided with the necessary structures, instruments and environment needed to carry out their jobs. Their experience of this theme ranges from issues of promotion, implementation of pension policies, an unconducive environment with dilapidated structures, office space, learning facilities among others which they see as discouraging and not happy working in such an environment. Interviewee 7 reflected on the work environment and offered that there are no good offices while classrooms are not good enough to contain many students during lectures and as a result causes congestion and learning process.

We don't have good offices, and also no good classroom for example i have a class that is supposed to contain about 100 students but the school allocates that class to more than 300 students there you will see congestion here and there, for some lecturers they don't care what they teach, they will just pass the message, teach and whether the students will be able to grab it or not he's not even bothered.

The 4th participant described the effects of the poor conditions under which they work leading to a series of strikes. He stated that because of these issues, lecturers are unwilling to teach, they rather engage in bribery all because they want to meet their satisfaction due to poor work environment and salary conditions.

...sometimes we go on strike for 1 month, 6 months and even a year without considering that lives of millions of Nigerians are at stake....lecturers find other means through which they can get their satisfaction met, that's why some don't mind taking sorting, some don't mind attending 2 classes instead of attending all which actually isn't the best because if the environment was conducive and the salary satisfactory, I think some of these things wouldn't happen

Interviewee 2 said he always feels bad seeing the poor state of the university structures and facilities like the library not being well stocked including salaries of academic staff.

look at the poor structures of the universities, look at the laboratories, looking at the payment of the lecturers the academic and non-academic staff, it always makes me feel bad imagine what our education system has become.

Following up with the availability of basic teaching equipment, the 5th participant expresses his dissatisfaction explaining how some of the machines needed to teach his students are not being provided and as a result, searching the internet has not been the best way to get students exposed to what they are being taught.

...not seeing lecturers get the basic equipment they need to teach the students ,these are basic equipment especially in my field ,basic machines that you should have in your department/faculty but you can't find them and you begin to teach students by describing, you begin to teach the students by browsing the internet and showing them but these are things that they should be supposed to when they go into the workshop.

One of the female participants sees a safe work environment as one of her major concerns considering the location where her university is located. She said she feel scared going through the bush to get to the university and advocate that government should do something to ensure that lecturers are safe in case of crises

...I'm trying to look back; you know most of our schools are situated close to the bush that you are scared may be crisis will come up one day and you know you can be killed

in that bush and nobody will know... to be honest my university is not in a good environment and...in fact the government need to do the needful, they should provide a good working environment not an environment that is scary.

Another participant also added to this theme by mentioning her experience working in a tight workspace which is even more pleasant than some lecturers who do not have offices at all.

Most of us have offices that we pair, just a little space but we squeeze ourselves, some people just teach and go back home because already they don't have where to put things together and all that

Furthermore, four participants' commentary revealed that unimplemented pension policies and promotion are some of the things that are commonly experienced within their career in the education sector. This is evident in cases where lecturers retire without having nothing to fall back on as pension and situations where they are told that their promotion has been reviewed without proper implementation of pay rises.

...some of my colleagues and I, we know how much we were being paid, most of them are still earning that same amount till today. My dear you won't understand what we are going through in this system, even when you are due for promotion and finally you get promoted with the paper work and everything, they still won't implement it till after some time. So that's why you see that average Nigerian says they don't like teaching job, just because of the way people are being treated not necessarily that the job is not good.

One of the participants mentioned that this is a new trend because it wasn't common some years back. Back then academic staff were not only promoted based on merit but also by years of experience. He also told me about his personal plan that due to the poor pension policies, he has long been into businesses to get him covered at his pensionable age in order to avoid the same disappointment that some pensioners do experience.

...There was good pension scheme and people get promoted not only based on merit but also based on years of experience. but looking at today, the whole story has changed. ...Not just that, the pension scheme is so poor that if God do not intervene you will have nothing to go home with when you retire. This is how bad it is my dear. but..well, for someone like me, God has blessed me that this is not my only job, I have other freelancing jobs and a little business that I do, so I am planning not to make the same mistake most pensioners and even our fathers made.

(d). Lack of development

Lack of development is one of the themes that emerged under this study. All twelve participants revealed that the education sector lacks development in areas related to academics such as curriculum improvement, teaching and learning development and infrastructure. Under this theme, participants showed that the curriculum they use in their universities are outdated and that the universities in Nigeria make little or no use of technological processes to advance teaching and learning. This keeps the system backward in terms of development when compared to other developed countries.

Participant 3 hilariously submitted that the education system has not improved in terms of teaching and learning.

In this system currently, in the system permit me to use the word arcade because everyone is creating a new way to impart knowledge but ours will not let you in itself. we are still doing things in the same old way and manner that same way like a song will go; the old rugged cross. No improvement in teaching and learning because the system is just interested in pushing out people without pushing out content.

Coming to curricular development, the 3rd participant also added that the same curriculum that they were taught during their undergraduate studies in the university is the same one most lecturers still use till today.

..From the curriculum I found out that over the past years the curriculum I met in teaching are the same ones that have been in use for the past 15 years even before I met them. You can imagine how underdeveloped the system is and some of these things are annoying.

The 5th participant also added that the curriculum is deficient and lacking as it is not being updated;

There are fields in Mechanical Engineering that are not in our sphere, not even in our curriculum because we are probably still using curriculum of 20, 25 years ago and trust me a child of 20 years ago and a child of 25 ago are different in their vocabulary development and all the amenities they have around them.

The same participant confirms this by telling his story of how the same lecturer who taught him many years ago is currently still using the same lesson notes and exactly the same teaching pattern in his university.

...Since many years ago he taught me but the old guy still using that same lesson notes, I'm telling you, no changes, nothing...

Participant's comments, shows that there is no evidence of appropriate academic review and implementations within the university sector due to the ambiguous processes and procedures involved in curricular review in public universities.

I'm speaking from my point of view as a lecturer , a learned person in the society will appreciate someone that graduated from a government school than someone that graduated from a private school , the only difference is that most of these private schools tend to review their curriculum from time to time more than we do

here because it's owned by one man so he can just gather his staffs together and they review their curriculum often but in our school because its government procedures and processes involved in reviewing this curriculum are ambiguous so we find it difficult to review.

Furthermore, lecturers' skill development is one of the lagging areas in the public education sector. Participants show that they are not exposed to technological advancement in the area of basic technology used for teaching and learning. Based on their story, participants blame the government for not providing advanced equipment nor an avenue to improve on intellectual development of lecturers through training.

we just have to manage with the situation we have and do the little we can do in our own sphere. For example I lecture in the mechanical engineering department and personally I've tried to develop myself technologically and in any way I can impact my students but I cannot do everything I need to do on my own, why is because the government has their own part to play and that support is not there to improve us. There are some equipment you can not afford to buy except the government provide...

One participant claim that lecturers are not exposed to using advanced technology as the Nigerian education system is not technologically friendly unlike in other industry.

I remember when I was with the auto-mobile company every 2,3 months we are being taught how to use different equipment...., but here, we have lecturers that don't know how to use the computer properly and right now when you need to teach remotely it's going to be difficult for a whole lot of lecturers even though such equipment are not in place yet

There are however cases where participants claim that the curriculum is currently undergoing improvement and that there is beginning to be both educational and professional

revolution in Nigerian education in terms of technology and advice that young people need to begin to come into a career in education. According to participant 12, he said;

You can't compare the educational system we have now to the ones our fathers had in 1960s and 1950s and thereabouts. Things are actually changing so there's a future in our education system, even though they are still introducing these technology of a thing. we now need a lot of young people to come in...

Similarly, another participant admitted to the fact that new things are being added to the university curriculum which were not part of it before, for example ICT. He asserts thus:

...also today we are teaching ICT in the university curriculum. It wasn't there before.

Despite the lack of development in the public universities another participant also noticed that in his university, there is beginning to be a well mapped out plan that gives both students and lecturers good teaching and learning curve. Although this is a recent development especially in his department of marine engineering. Basic technological equipment and program are now being provided to aid students in learning and this he finds very interesting as it makes him enjoy his teaching.

it's just recently that things are improving like in our department we have various simulation apps, stimulation software that help give students an experience, for example a 400 level student of Marine Engineering is supposed to have visited the sea at least 4 times before he graduates so we are gradually trying to bring that to pass

3. Experiencing flexibility of work and processes

During the interview, ten out of the entire twelve participants showed that the work environment within Nigerian public universities is to some extent worker friendly considering two different areas. This includes Recruitment process flexibility, and work flexibility implying low level of accountability.

(a). Recruitment process flexibility

Participants described some flexible experiences they had during their recruitment. They said they were appreciative of the fact that they did not find it difficult getting their lecturing employment. While some tried to put in their best during the recruitment, most people did not go through the formal recruitment process like others. Their stories showed that some were formally interviewed, others were employed through mere recommendation and experience depending on their different circumstances. For example, participant 7 narrated how the university vice chancellor promised all first class graduate automatic lecturing employment saying he was among the beneficiaries. The vice chancellor also showed a friendly attitude towards students when he invited them for a dinner.

while I was graduating from my final year the very then Vice Chancellor of the university Professor.... made a proclamation that all first class students will be given automatic employment, so we had a dinner, all first class students, we had a dinner with the Vice Chancellor and he mentioned that same promise at the dinner that all first class students will be given automatic employment after their youth service so when I finished my service I came back to the Vice Chancellor's office on the basis of that promise...

According to him, he ended up not getting the job under the said VC's tenure in office however, it was upon his promise that he finally was given employment after obtaining his

masters degree without needing to go through the required formal employment processes. Although this could be considered prejudice whereby his getting employed as a lecturer was principally influenced for other reasons, however, it can be argued that such employment was given under the capacity of the vice chancellor as a way of rewarding excellence as much as a recruitment strategy to attract the best candidates for lecturing in the university. From the participants' perspective, he was happy to have such an opportunity claiming that getting a lecturing job in the public university is flexible and the process is worker friendly.

Another participant also explained how he got the job as he did not go through straining interviews because the university at that time needed his expertise as a result of a newly established study area in the university, he got called and was offered an employment to co-establish the university medical school where he presently lectures without any rigorous recruitment process

For me it was just an easy thing, prior maybe God searches our heart and He knows I'm more of an academic person and so for us here I had to take up this responsibility, we were invited to come over here. We were asked by the vice chancellor and sitting vice chancellor then because they wanted to start the college of medicine, they asked a lot of us that had additional qualifications beside the medical degree, the MBBS degree to come in so it was an easy seal, I never went through any stress. I came in because I was properly fitted to start the medical School that was how I came in and I'm happy medical School is fully established and things are going on well. I didn't go through any rigors in recruitment getting the job.

On the other hand, the 11th participant was more reserved when I asked him; What are the experiences you can think of at the time you were given the lecturing job? For example, think about the recruitment processes you went through and how you were able to get the job? He mentioned that the process was smooth. I went further to ask him how? And he said that he

applied for the job and was called up for the interview which was in two stages; oral and computer based. According to him, he went through both stages and passed without any resort to personal connection or networking.

I applied for the job and was called for interview, there were two stages of the interview then, we had the computer based interview if you didn't know how to use the computer you automatically logged yourself out because you will not know what to do we were given 3 questions to answer, one on Microsoft Word, one on PowerPoint and the other was...eemmh, Which other application was there? I can't remember now. And if you didn't pass that stage you will not qualify and you will not be called for the second stage of the interview. Now we attended and I had the grace I passed and that was it.

(b). Work Process Flexibility

Flexibility within the work process is also common to lecturers across Nigerian public universities. To add to this theme, five participants showed that their job is flexible with a low level of accountability found within the system whereby they enjoy freedom from rigid supervisory structures and directives. According to the 9th participant, lecturing in the public university has been a pleasure to him because it is the most flexible job he has done. He said he likes the fact that he is not answerable to anyone. He said as a lecturer, his job enables him to solely make decisions regarding his work duties unlike other regular corporate settings where one needs to go by their supervisor's rules. He opines thus:

...I have times I teach, the other time I do research, I'm not answerable per say to any boss, I love the way the system is structured that the public university system is democratic nobody can wake up tomorrow and sack you unless you are involved in misconduct...

Similarly, the 6th participant also confirm how flexible he finds lecturing and the reason why he sees it as a spectacular and unique career is because he is able to combine it with other jobs and engagement, he said:

...so it doesn't take anything away from my lecturing profession that's why the profession is very spectacular and unique, I can combine with other things so being a lecturer did not stop me from owning a consultancy firm around my field, besides that I am also a crypto currency analyst.

Furthermore, another participant also mentioned experiencing some element of work-life balance working as a female lecturer within the public university sector. she added to this theme by saying that her experience having a flexible work setting impacts her life as a female lecturer. She said she appreciates being able to carry her family along with her lecturing career. In essence, It does not give her much concern about having time to take care of her family because she can decide to call her HOD to excuse herself from work at any time she feels like in order to attend to her family. Also, she does not have to go to work every day, only when she has lectures. She also decides to leave early enough after her lectures in circumstances where she has a pressing issue to attend to at home. To her, this is the essence of having work life balance which she was struggling to get in her previous career as a medical personnel working in a hospital environment.

Well, being a female lecturer has no difference with the male counterpart, in fact I even see some advantage because it is flexible for me. Well, its not just about being female but the university work setting is the main thing...like other white collar job example bankers, you wouldn't have such time that I have for yourself let alone your family but I thank God because I am able to have maximum time for my family while still a lecturer.... I don't go to work every other day, I can call my HOD and tell her that I'm not coming the following day. in fact to me this experience is great. I am just so elated

about how flexible the career is for me. Even sometimes, I come for lecture and the next minute after my lectures I'm gone...

The 9th Participant's narrative also shows that despite the friendly and flexible work environment, that the lecturing job itself is tasking. As part of his reason, difficulty in dealing with students is evident.

Yes working in a university like mine, I would say is somehow flexible in terms of your schedules and no too much of supervision and all that. In fact your HOD doesn't even have time for you, not every day. The only thing is that it's tasking you know getting students to really understand... there is difference between knowing something and making the next person get to know it from you too. So it's quite a tasking job...

4. Desiring positive changes in public education

(a). Increase pay, Funding, and Pension

Pay rise was one of the most important concerns to lecturers during my interview with them because of how much they all emphasized the poor salary rate they receive. They all show dissatisfaction with their salary being very poor notwithstanding other pay related issues that they face including payment delays. This can be said to have had an adverse effect on them wanting to have other income sources including multiple businesses and relying on students for bribes (sorting). The entire twelve participants advocate that the government should increase their pay rate including other pay conditions such as pension. One of the ways they expect this to be done is for the government to also increase education funding in order to accommodate their pay rise. This was the comment made by the 9th participant:

The government needs to put more funds into research, infrastructure and our salary both the academic and non-academic staff. They need to be given maximum attention

so that we can continue to have the passion to teach. That's why today everybody wants to go into politics, even the highly educated ones that could have come into the education system not because they have the passion to serve the people but because nothing is in teaching for them, so we need a good salary structure in the universities.

Similarly, the 11th participant also submitted thus:

yes it's difficult saying that persons you trained or taught, burning candles in the midnight is out there earning fabulous salaries in 7 and 8 digits while you are here getting peanut so yes the paid package of lecturers should be reviewed and looked into to also help us live a comfortable life.

The 6th participant expects the government to increase education funding and benchmark it to the United nation's recommendation. To him, this is one of the ways he believes salaries can also be increased.

Lecturers need to be given a fair pay, if this is done every other thing will fall into place. Therefore, first and foremost funding in the education sector must be taken very serious. If as a developing country we can't do the 25% budget by United nations ,we can do the 15% what is the percentage of the budget even when the government has to cut down because of COVID19 they had to cut down on education but there are irrelevant ministries that they didn't cut down on their budget.

According to the 3rd participant, pay is at the core of lecturers' dissatisfaction therefore the government should provide good pay so as to take care of their families

...What I expect of the government is to let us have a good pay, this is at the core of our dissatisfaction in this sector, that is where everything starts. They are not the only people who likes money, we too have families to take care of...

Similarly, another respondent also supports the idea of increased funding and advocating that the government should listen to ASUU on negotiations surrounding it

What ASUU is saying is fund the universities. Is the investment in education really worth it? You members of the society can now answer can we do without proper education in our country? We can't and how do we get to that place we want? We have to fund education. Lecturers' pay are not taken care of, the laboratories are not functioning, we don't blame the VC of our university and the management, it is the federal government. Since 2009 or so they are fighting with ASUU over an agreement signed way back then but we have money flying here and there, why not invest this money in the university system, even the polytechnics, college of education are underfunded so this is my earnest expectation

Aside from increasing lecturers' salary rate and funding the education, another area lecturers expect improvement is pension. For many years, retired teachers and lecturers do not always have the entitlement to their pension and this has made them become sceptical thinking that it will continue. Three of the respondents mention that they know people who did not get their pension after many years of teaching in secondary school as a result of either process bureaucracy or improper data/record keeping during claims and this led to their denial. They also mentioned embezzlement of the pension fund by top personnel in the education ministry. As a result of this, retirees always go home with nothing. Therefore participants are advocating that the government review their pension scheme to enable them get their pension when they retire.

We are still hoping that something be done about the pension scheme, even you you will not be happy seeing your father after over 30 to 40 years of service retiring and when he goes to claim his pension you will see someone from somewhere saying they cant find his name or details among the list they have, even me I can faint if I hear that, so I

think government should look into our retirement scheme so when we retire we can have something to fall back on rather than starting all over again.

(b). Government support

One of the expectations lecturers mentioned is having support from the government in areas such as research and development. For example, it is a basic requirement in Nigerian universities, to have proof of several research and publications to be considered for promotion. While this has proven over the years to be a yardstick for promotion even to a professorial level, lecturers have seen this to be challenging as most people do not have the funds to personally embark on certain research required of them. For this reason, there is a gap in research and development and less chances of getting desired promotion. As a result, lecturers expect that the government should provide support for them in terms of funding research. This was the position of the 4th participant:

...the second part which government should improve on is; in our career part we have to grow for a re-promotion you have to have certain number of publications and a particular degree. Now getting this publications need money, financial effort and most at times it's not easy to get grants and support to do this research for higher degrees and publications. This is where our government should come in to support, So there could be investment into research and provide grants and scholarships for both lecturers and students alike to improve the knowledge base of the whole system in the country in general . So the part that is not really going down well in the system is the part that lecturers have to spend almost everything they get to build themselves at the position of being able to get there desired promotion.

Similarly, the 9th participant is also of the same opinion. According to him:

A lot of times it's my personal fund I use in research, I've never had any research grants, I publish a lot of papers it's my personal funds and these funds are tied to my legal salary as a lecturer. So, these areas all challenges with the system which the government need to meet. It will encourage people like me to go into more research, even things will be developed and we will add to the society.

(c). Improve work environment/conditions

One of the common experiences the participants mentioned in this study is working in an uncondusive environment and having poor working conditions. This includes lack of office spaces, overcrowded classrooms, no regular electricity within the university campus among others. Seven out of the twelve participants said they need the government to provide a good work environment to enable lecturers to work in their best capacity. This they expect to be done in order to improve teaching and learning experience and also enhance their satisfaction. Like the 1st participant said:

...One of the greatest strategies we can use to enhance lecturer's job satisfaction is to have good working condition, do you know some lecturers don't have good offices where they use? Also, if you have a class that can contain just 50 students the school allocates it to more than 100 students so this is what I'm talking about, the congestion here and there makes you sweat like a he goat. So, I expect the government to improve our work environment, the work condition should be favourable, the environment should be favourable for lecturers to teach...

Furthermore, the 4th participant also mentioned being concerned about the work environment and advocating that the government provide a good work environment including materials needed for teaching.

Our teaching and learning environment has been bad. I wish the government can provide all that lecturers and the students need because in a situation where students are not comfortable, how will they understand what you are teaching? That's why the failure rate in our universities today is so high. So let them make the teaching and learning environment conducive, give us what we need to teach them, the labs and all that...

(d). Implement policies & Develop education

Policy implementation is another area some of the lecturers spoke about and expecting a change. In this regard, they advocate that policies be reviewed and those that will be in favour of the education sector be implemented. This follows postulations that some educational policies are not implemented. For example, the 9th participant's expectation is for the legislature to implement a policy, imposing a ban on international education such that will deter government agencies from sponsoring students on a scholarship abroad while the Nigerian education system is underdeveloped and lacking, He therefore advocate that these funds be put into the education sector for development.

The legislators must get to work, they must begin to make laws that are favourable to the education in Nigeria. Maybe put a ban on foreign studies, Let politicians all their children study here in Nigeria. Yes, and the huge sums of money they spend sending people to study abroad need to stop when our education needs development, lecturers are crying for salary. if that kind of law is enacted in Nigeria and they are implemented it will be favourable to us all, so for me they should develop our education using those money they spend sponsoring students abroad...

Similarly, the 5th participant mentioned educational policies and general minimum wage laws not being implemented. His expectation is that the government will implement these policies:

..the government they are not actually following the law, the laws are there and once the government starts implementing the laws things will change to be better, okay now look at the minimum wage how many state governments have implemented it? Even in Rivers State here have they totally been implemented? No, it's not just for us lecturers but every sector is involved in this one. The educational policies which ASUU have been fighting for...they just write them on paper but still don't implement them. So I really wish the government would do something, they should implement these laws including the several education policies that they agree with ASUU yet do nothing about.

Another participant is also of the view that the policies for appointing and imposing powers on the university governing council be reviewed so as to avoid conflict of interest or personal interests.

Okay now concerning the educational system generally I think the policy of the school also needs to be checked, for example now there is a governing council for all the universities, these are the people that make policies for the universities, we understand that personal and selfish interest has always being there but let it not override the reason why we are in the university.

Determining Lecturers' Job Satisfaction

The third research question was to determine lecturers' job satisfaction and whether their professional motive and experiences inform their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In answering this question, it is important to highlight my philosophical and methodological underpinning which guided this analysis.

As a phenomenological researcher embracing constructivist interpretivism, my interpretation is based on what participants say about the phenomenon and their lived experiences around it. This enables me to discover their reality with regard to their job satisfaction. Adhering to my methodological tenets exempted me from measuring satisfaction based on statistical interpretation that is embedded with predetermined criteria. This is because it would rather restrict the scope of findings by confining and predefining factors and indices of measurement hence putting my participants in a box (Shaw, 2010).

Based on the above explanation, I present participants' stories based on what they said regarding their satisfaction and/or dissatisfaction. The twelve participants were asked if they derive job satisfaction or dissatisfaction putting their career experiences and career motive into consideration and why. They were also asked to mention specific work areas, systems, structures, issues or circumstances where they derive satisfaction and dissatisfaction and what they think would ensure their satisfaction within the public university sector.

Participants revealed their professional motive as well as the wide range of experiences entailing what they see as common within the university sector where they work. From their stories, all participants admitted that they are satisfied because they feel fulfilled impacting the lives of people. Their being satisfied did not have any connection with what they experienced in their job and therefore can be said to be a constructed reality not because they cannot derive job satisfaction from their impact on students but because such satisfaction is not informed by their everyday experiences on the job instead it is predetermined by their prior motivation into the teaching career which sound aspirational. In fact, their stories revealed that they have high

job dissatisfaction because of the negativities surrounding their job and the work environment in the public education sector. Their reasons for having job dissatisfaction are attributed to systemic inadequacies found within the Nigerian education system or sector. This includes in general terms four of the emerging sub themes discussed earlier such as salary issues, corruption, lack of development and poor working conditions, facilities and policy. From this evidence, it can be deduced that only lecturers' professional motive informs their job satisfaction because the fulfilment they derive is a product of the impact they claimed to have made in their lecturing career and that was their predominant motive for choosing a teaching career in the first place even though it could be a constructed believe without much credible and realistic evidence. Hence they achieved their career motive which brings them job satisfaction. The below participants' stories supports this findings:

According to the 1st participant, he expressed being satisfied with his career. Firstly, he said he derives job satisfaction because he is able to achieve his motive as a lecturer. In his statement, he expressed being satisfied and happy whenever he sees students that he has impacted their lives. From my understanding, his satisfaction is intrinsic/altruistic as it tends to come from within rather than being subject to the work conditions and environment. This means that he has personal fulfilment impacting the lives of people and not what his job offers hence his satisfaction is informed by or linked to the achievement of his motive for choosing a teaching profession which was to impact lives. He said:

one thing that satisfies me most is seeing the students or those people that passed through me becoming something in future...

...because what drove me into the profession was to impact in people so focusing on that I think I am happy.

However, he also communicated aspects about his career that gives him concerns and dissatisfaction when asked. He expressed dissatisfaction in other areas of his career and the

system. One of the areas he mentioned is the promotion system. Not only is there lack of promotion but also from his assertion, the bureaucracy in the process is overwhelming and also nepotism as he earlier mentioned.

..talking about dissatisfaction, hmmm...like I said I have been lecturing in this university for the past six years...since I got this job I haven't received any promotion. I mean a normal promotion. The level I started is still the level I am till today... if not the fact that they added some chicken change to our salary recently, ...to get a promotion in this job still boils down to you knowing somebody so I am really dissatisfied about working in such a system.

...sometimes in most cases for you to be promoted, the ranks and files in the system, it's based on man-know –man, indigenous differences will come in and all that.

Other areas of great dissatisfaction to him also include low salary and retirement schemes. He says the government needs to take action to ensure that people have good retirement schemes. From his statement I noticed that one of the reasons why he feels dissatisfied is because his career does not guarantee him a secured future considering the fact that retirement/pension schemes are partially implemented within the education sector.

...Yeah I'm very dissatisfied with the low salary income and the way retirement scheme is implemented in this country. I think government should look into the retirement scheme of lecturers so that when we retire, we can have something to fall back on rather than starting all over again.

On a whole, this participant says he has a lot of job dissatisfaction than he is actually satisfied. This is his assertion:

..So those are some dissatisfactory situations in fact, they are too many to mention.

Another participant's comment also reveals that his professional motive informs his job satisfaction as opposed to his experiences working in the public university sector. The 4th Participant reflected on his personal experience and offered:

Majorly the most satisfactory aspect I've experienced as a lecturer is seeing my students graduate and do well in the society. I remember one time in Edo state one professor I met was saying one governorship candidate was his student and he was so proud of him, I think the same applies to me. Imagine when you train up these students and you go out in the society and see them doing well, impacting in the society positively, nobody will want to train up a student and see them on the road with guns or on the road begging. You will be happy when you enter a bank for example and you see your students in the bank you feel so happy because that person is there as a result of those disciplines, trainings and teachings you gave them. So my fulfilment as a lecturer is to see the students better the society.

On the other hand, this participant feels dissatisfied with the administrative and governance system in the education sector. He also said he feels dissatisfied not seen basic equipment to aid teaching and a good environment all of which the government has refused to provide:

I have great dissatisfaction with the administration and governance in the education sector, but my major dissatisfaction in my practice as a lecturer is not seeing lecturers get the basic equipment they need to teach the students, there are some basic equipment especially in my field ,basic machines that you should have in your faculty but you can't find them and I just wonder, you teach students by describing, you browse the internet just to show them but these are things that they are supposed to go into the workshop and use these machines. So, my major dissatisfaction is these aid are not provided to help the students learn. These should be provided to also help the teachers teach to give students a competitive advantage.

Furthermore, from the excerpt of the 11th participant when asked about his job satisfaction, he said that he is satisfied based on the happiness and fulfilment he derives from the students he impacted and still impacts. Although he sees pay as a challenge however, his satisfaction in his career is irrespective of his salary since getting higher pay is not achievable for him. He cited one of the instances when he met his ex-student whom he happened not to recognize and from their conversation, he felt satisfied having taught him in the university.

..there was a time I was going out and somebody I taught in school, a graduate, he called me and told me that I taught him when he was in year one. Although I've forgotten, I was like do I really know you? After everything, in fact that alone gave me so much satisfaction despite the fact that we don't have much pay but when you look at people you've imparted knowledge in, that alone can give you joy and it might overcome the pay even though the pay is small.

When I asked him what he finds dissatisfying about his career he mentioned poor salary rate and work environmental issues as some of the basic concerns that gives him dissatisfaction.

Summary

Chapter four presented my findings of the data I collected from the twelve participants. The individual stories were not discussed due to word limitation. A cross-case analysis of the themes that emerged was presented to answer the research questions. The first research question was to determine the predominant teaching motivation of professional lecturers in Nigerian public universities. My findings show that it is their passion to impact the lives of students. The second research question was to determine what lecturers experience working in a Nigerian public university, my findings reveal that what lecturers experience were mostly

negative. This includes salary issues, corruption, lack of development, poor working conditions, facilities and environment and flexibility. Lastly, the third research question was to determine whether lecturers' professional motivation and experiences inform their job satisfaction. For this research question, it was found out that lecturers' job satisfaction in Nigerian public university is mostly influenced by their professional motive because all participants claim that their motive for choosing the teaching profession was to impact lives following this, they feel satisfied using their position to impact the lives of many students. On the other hand, their experiences imply that they are dissatisfied and therefore they expressed disappointment with the negatives that comes with working in the public education sector.

Chapter Five

Discussion And Interpretation

Introduction

This is a phenomenological study which aims to investigate lecturers' career motivation, in other words why they choose lecturing as a career and what they experience working in a public university sector to determine the sources of their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. I was interested in the stories lecturers would tell as to why they chose a teaching career and from their experiences working in the public sector, what they would attribute to having job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. My intention was to use a different approach for my research (examining lived experiences) rather than the commonly used quantitative measures for job satisfaction based on predefined criteria which I consider having certain limitations unsuitable for my study. This is because it limits participants response to certain scope by confining and predefining factors and indices of measurement hence putting the participants in a box (Shaw, 2010)

The lived experiences of 12 lecturers from two public universities in Rivers state, southern Nigeria were therefore studied through a face-to-face video interview and findings were reached using thematic analysis. My understanding of Participants' job satisfaction and dissatisfaction was also established based on the themes that emerged. Therefore, this chapter discusses the findings and their connection to literature or theories.

Theme 1: Choosing Lecturing as a career

(a). Passion to make an impact on students

The below table 5.1 summarises my findings in relation to this theme and how it links to predefined and new literature. This indicate that the study either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with these literatures.

Theme 1	Sub Theme (A)	Link to initial literature	New literature
Choosing lecturing as a career	Passion to make an impact on students	Akinbote, 2009, Ladebo, 2005, Watt et al, 2012, Moran et al, 2001, Victor and Babatunde, 2014, Heinz, 2015, Anghel, 2020, Balyer and Ozcan, 2014. Wong, Tang, and Cheng, 2014.	Aluko, 2002, Muhammad, 2010, Mustapha and Bolaji, 2015, Keskin, and Oral, (2020)

Table 5. 1: Theme 1, sub theme 'A'

The predominant theme (Passion to make an impact on students) presented in the study relates to lecturers' professional motivation. It explains the primary reason that drives them to choosing a career in teaching specifically within a Nigerian university context. Impacting people's lives is seen as the most common and primary reason why people choose to be in a teaching career not just in Nigeria but across the world. From literature and in this study, many people show that they have passion to teach, and this choice is not only based upon the fact that they love teaching but also that they derive fulfilment and satisfaction for adding value to the lives of people through teaching hence contributing to the society. In other words, they are motivated as they contribute to the success of students, which is what all participants in this research spoke about. Several research has shown that those in a teaching profession feel very satisfied seeing their students succeed or having the sense that they are making a social contribution. This is considered an altruistic motive in most teaching career literature. In this

study, it is the motivation to contribute to students' lives not just academically but also morally and socially. My findings confirm watt et al (2012) who provides that the motive that related most strongly to high career satisfaction included the altruistic-type motivations. It also contributes to the research of Akinbote, (2009) and Ladebo, (2005) who revealed that primary school teachers in Nigeria chose the profession because of their love and passion to contribute to the lives of children. It also agrees with many of the factors listed by the studies of Watt et al, (2012, p,12) whose findings provides thus: 'The highest rated motivations for the choice of a teaching career were consistently intrinsic value; perceived teaching ability, the desire to make a social contribution, to work with children/adolescents, and having had positive prior teaching and learning experiences'. Although intrinsic value which is a construct of the Fit-choice model used by Watt et al (2012) is identified with altruistic factors in studies like Anghel, (2020). Likewise, Moran et al, (2001), whose findings implied that people are attracted to the profession largely for intrinsic reasons. Although the context and methodology of both studies differ from this study. Also, other studies deal with either entry teachers or primary school teachers, however the content of teaching profession is the same irrespective of academic level where it is carried out or years of teaching experience.

Regarding my study, all participants mentioned that their motive for choosing the lecturing career was because they want to make an impact. This became the predominant theme as they mentioned many other things connoting their motive to impact the lives of students. This includes imparting knowledge, social and moral impact, rendering academic assistance and enlightening people. The 2nd participant mentioned his motive into this career path. He said he wanted to impact students through teaching even before he got his lecturing job. There was a burning desire in him to change things around his subject area. He said as a mathematician, he realized that mathematics is difficult for many students to comprehend and following this, he had had the ability to simplify it and changed the psychology or perception of students about mathematics. He was able to make people who hated mathematics love it and

as a matter of fact have received many compliments from students over the years about how much he has impacted their lives with his knowledge and has been given an academic award. Also, the 6th participant's story shows the same passion to impact lives. According to him, he does teach with ease and following his discovering his abilities at a younger age partly prompted him to go into education. Likewise, 4th participant who shows zealousness for the teaching profession. He said that he had passion for the teaching profession and that his ultimate motive is to impact lives. 4th participant also showed the amount of impact he has contributed to people's lives within the mechanical engineering department where he lectures, he said he has personally mentored students through to their career many of whom are successful. However, in his opinion, most Nigerian lecturers and other careers within academia have an ulterior career motive. He said they are either driven by money or frustration for not having a job of their choice because of unemployment in the system which is the main reason why most lecturers take a lecturing job as their last resort:

Following the 4th participant's opinion, Labedo, (2005) confirmed that teaching professionals with higher qualifications or degrees in Nigeria are into teaching because of prevalent unemployment in the country which is an indication of feeling of apathy – a feeling of indifference regardless of job dissatisfaction. Aluko (2002) and Muhammad (2010), have also explored the subject around lecturer's motivation in Nigeria and found that motivation for teaching professionals don't only focus on student's achievement but also towards enhancing their own satisfaction. In affirmation to this, Victor and Babatunde, (2014, p158) stated that 'many faculty members give minimal time to university work and seek one or more income-generating activities to supplement their academic salaries'. What this means is that lecturers prioritise their own personal satisfaction over students' performance. Evidence from Aluko (2002) found that only 29 percent of lecturer's time is spent on teaching which is also the case in this study as six out of the twelve participants mentioned having other businesses which they do to augment their income. In opposition to the evidence provided by the aforementioned

studies and the 4th participant's opinion regarding lecturers' drive for money (own satisfaction) over the career itself (students performance), the position of Yorke and Longden, (2004) however suggest that lecturers' commitment is relational to students success, an indication that lecturers do not prioritize their own satisfaction over students' performance or impact rather, the later occurs as a result of the former.

Again, this brings about the question as to whether they are truly motivated by teaching for their student's success/impact as suggested by Mustapha and Bolaji, (2015) or by financial gain as opined by one of the participants in this study and supported by Victor and Babatunde (2014, p158). In as much as lecturers engage in other complementary sources of revenue to support their salary from teaching, which many participants complained to be very poor, it can be said that lecturer's motive goes beyond teaching for the sole purpose of impacting lives even though a recent study by Keskin, and Oral, (2020) suggested that teachers are devoted to their teaching career without any primary expectation of financial gain for the duties they carry out.

A major target of the first research question was to determine which of the three career motives namely intrinsic, extrinsic, and altruistic drive university lecturers in Nigeria and whether it influences their job satisfaction. According to empirical literature on teachers' professional motivation, for example Heinz, 2015, Anghel, 2020, Balyer and Ozcan, 2014, Wong, Tang, and Cheng, 2014, Intrinsic motivation covers factors such as enjoyment of teaching, job satisfaction and creativity, altruistic covers the desire to impact lives and contribute to society while extrinsic covers pay level and job security. Going by this description, the passion to impact lives being the predominant motive which the participants in this study described is a cross motivational factor falling under both intrinsic-altruistic motives depending on its description by different studies. Therefore, this findings is consistent with many other research on the subject for example: Moran et al (2001) whose research was conducted in Ireland to examine why people choose a career in teaching and found out that they were attracted to the profession largely for intrinsic reasons. In the context of Turkey, the

study by Balyer and Ozcan, (2014) revealed that people are attracted to the teaching profession mainly for altruistic-intrinsic reasons however this was seen to have a bearing on the female gender as they submitted that the male gender were motivated into the profession for extrinsic reasons. Research by Balyer and Özcan, 2014 also gave the same result. They suggested that intrinsic career value indicates that lecturers have an instinctive passion about teaching and genuinely enjoys it. In a similar vein, all the participants mentioned having passion for teaching.

The idea of John Holland Theory of Career Choice (1959) and the Fit-choice theoretical model by Watt and Richardson, (2007) are significant in lecturers' choice of career in this study. With Holland theory, career choice is seen to be influenced by or subjected to six personality traits that include: investigative/ thinkers, artistic/creators, social/helpers, enterprising /persuaders, conventional/organizers, and realistic/doers. Among the six personality traits, John Holland identified careers that fall under each of the categories. He identifies teachers/lecturers to fall under the category of people who have a social or helpers personality trait. This is because as teachers, their personality type helps them to engage and train people while creating lasting relationships. As a matter of fact, they have good communications skills and are happy to support people (Holland 1959).

Following participants' story, the passion to impact the lives of people which stood out as their predominant motive for the profession emerged from the combination of some coded meaning clusters which tend to identify with Holland's social/helpers personality traits. This includes desiring to help in making a social impact, passion to teach (train people), love for teaching, academic assistance and helping students succeed. In fact, the 6th participant's story of why he chose the teaching profession is attributed to his passion for teaching which according to him, he does with ease as he discovered that he has the abilities since he was a little child. The 3rd participant also shared her story about how her passion for teaching to impact people came because of her realization that she has the skills from her many years of

being a Sunday school teacher in the church. In addition, she said that she had always liked to gather people to let them know of current happenings to keep them informed which is one of the skills Holland theory is hinged on for social/helpers. Importantly, this theme will further be discussed in relation to its linkage to job satisfaction in subsequent section of this chapter.

(b). Absence of personal and career expectations

The table 5.2 below presents this theme and relate it to initial and new literature that either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with these literatures.

Theme 1	Sub theme (B)	Link to initial literature	New literature
Choosing lecturing as a career	Absence of personal and career need	Anghel, (2000),	Giancola, (2011), Leontieva et al, (2017), Gottfredson (1981)

Table 5. 2: Theme 1, sub theme ‘B’

Organizations and society do not always provide us with the career opportunities we want and sometimes certain jobs don't meet employee’s expectations. Two out of the four participants whose stories were linked to this theme were from medical background: one a medical doctor and the other a lab scientist. They both were previously working in a hospital setting. They complained about their job not having variety and not giving them the opportunity to learn new things. It was part of their profession to have a consistent work routine every day and to them this was a boring process because it was not what they wanted from a career. They opted for another job that would offer them more challenge and variety that they needed. According to the 9th participant, practicing medicine in a hospital environment is monotonous because of the repetitive operational pattern associated with it. Having to do the same thing every day was not his kind of thing he said, as he identified to be more of an academic person who loved to do research, teach and to contribute to development in theory as much as

practicing medicine. Following this, he did not see himself completely practicing medicine soon. This led to his interest in a career that is challenging in nature and has variety such that will enable him to research and develop the field which he found in lecturing.

The fact that both lecturers in the medical field have similar perception about the repetitive nature of healthcare work routine is indicative that job variety that allows them to face challenges and learn other skills outside their core professional duties were important to them. It is therefore important to design lecturing job such that its content embraces more research and flexibility as its practical side especially for core professional fields like medicine.

Similarly, the 8th participant being a lab scientist asserts how she felt that her job was repetitive because she does the same thing every day. She mentioned that the job did not allow her to learn new things as it was boring and monotonous. It was not the best for her meanwhile from her story, she used to be a Sunday school teacher for some years and already has teaching experience; something she had always loved to do and very skilful at. She then decided to go for a lecturing career as it will give her the privilege to impart her practical knowledge as well as learn new things. Both stories go against one of the findings of Anghel, (2000) who provided that not being comfortable in a field where one was trained for is a least and insignificant reason people give for taking a teaching career. In this case, it was rather part of their core reason for changing career from medical field into lecturing. Following from the stories of these two participants, it is important that those with the responsibility of designing academic career responsibilities are aware that lecturers are keen about enriched and challenging work design that enable them to learn new things for instance through research. This becomes one significant characteristic and a driving force for career choice which led the 8th and 9th participant into lecturing hence the reason they quit their professional job that lacked variety as well as being challenge deficient.

According to Giancola (2011), human resource experts submits that one of the reasons why employees are dissatisfied is the nature of their job. He provided that a significant number

of employees do complain about a boring repetitive nature of job that offers little challenge. He concluded that when the job itself is enriched, it leads to productivity and employees' satisfaction. In such circumstances, they will have little or no intention to leave for a similar job. On the other hand, a study by Leontieva et al, (2017) revealed that 40% of respondents who were medical doctors are ready to be involved in educational activity in future hence the career motivation for educational activity was expressed by approximately one third of medical staff who are oriented towards professional and creative growth.

Furthermore, in this study, poverty and idleness also emerged as some drivers to career choice in teaching which is indicative of the absence of personal/career expectations. Under this theme, Poverty is conceived out of a participant's story of having considered lecturing due to his financial lack whereas the other was because of idleness due to unemployment having spent many years at home. With the 1st participant, he took the lecturing job out of boredom after two years of staying at home upon completing his NYSC and three years' post-graduation. To him lecturing was just an alternative to joblessness. By then, he had already applied to several jobs in different industries, but none was successful, and it was very worrisome for him as he felt idle doing nothing through these years. When he eventually applied to a lecturing job, he got called for an employment and because he had no other choice at the time he accepted to go into lecturing. This is significant to the idea of Gottfredson (1981) who highlights the compromising nature of individuals regarding career choice. He asserts that in circumstances where choices are slim, there is a formation of a preference structure, this helps the individual to develop perceptions of job accessibility based on observed barriers and opportunities. At this point, an individual may adopt a certain group of careers based on barriers and opportunities that are observable at that given point in time. According to Gottfredson (1981) this is referred to as 'range of acceptable occupational alternatives' which is sometime dependent on external factors out of the control of the individuals.

Theme 2: Experiencing Sectoral Challenges

(a) Salary Issues

Table 5.3 below presents this theme and link it to initial and new literature. The provisions of this theme either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with the below literatures which are discussed further down the section.

Theme 2	Sub theme (A)	Link to initial literature	New literature
Experiencing Sectoral Challenges	Salary Issues	Adelabu, (2005), Lope (2004), Victor and Babatunde, (2014), Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014), Ekundayo, and Ajayi, (2009), Offem et al. (2018)	Ebuara & Coker (2012), Aluko (2002), Aina, (2007), Afejuku (2021), Famurewa (2014), Odozobodo (2015)

Table 5. 3: Theme 2, Sub theme “A”

As much as pay is one common work motivator to many people, inadequacies around the area of pay has proven to cause work demotivation and in this study, it is counted among what lecturers experience working in the Nigerian public university sector. All the twelve participants in my study affirm to have experienced and still experiencing salary issues including poor salary rate, delay in payment of salaries, outrageous disparity in lecturers’ pay compared to other careers within the public sector, strikes resulting from government refusal to implement certain pay policies. In the study of Ebuara and Coker (2012), they found that workers in the education sector experienced unequal treatment in terms of their salary, compared to employees in other public sector institutions despite similarities in their academic or professional qualifications. In terms of payment disparity and delays, this study also confirms Adelabu, (2005) who revealed that teacher dissatisfaction in Nigeria is because of the disparities between the teachers’ pay and other professions with regard to the time and mode of payment of salaries, fringe benefits, promotion prospects and working conditions. In

contrast, Udoji commission of 1972 which claimed to have ‘harmonized the public sector pay by bringing all public sector personnel under one unified salary scheme and it also ensured that teachers enjoyed comparable salary status with other key public sector workers’ (Adelabu, 2005, p4).

Furthermore, in Nigeria, professionals within the education sector including lecturers and professors have been counted among the least paid professions. This confirms the study of Lope (2004) who revealed that low salary is one of the factors that leads to low motivation of teachers in Nigeria. The 6th participant in this study gave an example affirming this fact, he provided that even professors in his university with their wealth of experiences are not being paid more than four hundred thousand naira. As at the time of my interview with him, this amount was equivalent to seven hundred and fifty pounds. He gave this as the reason many lecturers engage inside businesses and even do lecture in two or three universities as freelancers just to have other means of income to solve their financial needs. He compares this to the overwhelming salary of local government chairmen as one of the lowest political offices who earns far more than lecturers and professors put together. In the study of Victor and Babatunde, (2014, p158) they stated thus: ‘many faculty members give minimal time to university work and seek one or more income-generating activities to supplement their academic salaries’. This is evidenced in the study of Aluko (2002) who found out that only 29 percent of a lecturer's time is spent on teaching whereas a higher percentage of their time is spent on other means of generating more income. When considering a career with such a poor salary rate, Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014) provided that people stay put in a low paid job like teaching not because they love teaching but that they choose to stay in the career in the face of a stringent job market. This is consistent with the study of Ladebo, 2005 conducted about schoolteachers’ quit intention in Nigeria

Aina, (2007) confirmed the poor financial funding of Nigerian education in her study titled *Alternative Modes of Financing Higher Education in Nigeria and Implication for*

University Governance. Many participants in this study believe that education funding in Nigeria is very poor hence, the reason why their salaries are never attractive nor regularly paid. The 3rd participant mentioned this saying that despite insufficient pay, payment delays are common being something he experience most of the time. In the public universities, staff don't get paid sometimes for up to 3months he said. Ekundayo, and Ajayi, (2009) also researched into the effective management of university education in Nigeria and asserted that funding remains one of the biggest issues faced by Nigerian Education. They made the following recommendation for meaningful development in the university system: 'the government must be ready to address the issue of funding the system adequately. The government should as a matter of national importance review upward the pay-package for academics; give consent to the university autonomy being clamouring for by the academics.

Furthermore, some participants' assertion about this issue of salary is the fact that it has always been escalated into strike actions by the academic staff union of universities (ASUU). The 1st participant mentioned that he was part of those that the strike which was initiated by ASUU in 2016 and lasted for four months greatly affected. The main reason he gave for the strike was issues relating to salary payments. He said that the government is never ready to commit to the terms established by ASUU regarding some stringent work conditions which was inclusive of pay. As a result, strikes last longer than expected. My data correspondingly suggested that lecturers understood and felt bad to be experiencing poor conditions of work around payment. This is indicative that they are working for an employer that does not take cognizance of their concerns and do not place much value on educational development hence the incessant strike actions. The statistical data by Afejuku (2021) reveal the strike trajectory of academic staff in Nigeria universities, as evident from the year 1999 to 2020. He provided that, the strike in 1999 occurred for a total duration not less than a month. The situation escalated in 2001 when the strike lasted for 3 months before its decline in 2002 with the strike happening for 2 weeks. Other strike statistics for lecturers in Nigeria by

Famurewa (2014) further affirm that there was a strike by the academic staff in 2006, which took 7 days, in 2007, the strike lasted for 3 months, whereas in 2009, the academic staff in public universities were on strike for 4months. The strike by lecturers in 2010 took 5months and 7days, in 2011, the strike lasted for 3 months, while the number escalated to 5 months and 3 weeks in 2013. Subsequently, Afejuku (2021) captures the most recent and continuing trend of the strike by academic staff providing that ASUU issued a strike warning to the government and relevant organisations recently on the 9th March 2020 before proceeding on an industrial strike for an indefinite period which commenced on 23rd March 2020 while issues of corona virus was raging on the other end.

Also, Offem et al. (2018) explained the factors leading to the incessant strikes which he attributes to delayed salaries/emoluments, issues of political interferences in the education sector, lack of sufficient funding for the universities, poor and unfavourable work conditions for the academic staff, lack of career development avenues, and problems of formulation of educational policy. Similarly, the statistical data by Odozobodo (2015) is consistent with the results of Offem et al. (2018). The study disclosed the agreement between lecturers (ASUU) and the government of Nigeria relating to the disbursement of some 1.5trillion Naira ranging between 2009 and 2011, which remains unenforced. The neglect of the academic staff by the government is evident in the non-disbursement of payments and a relatively limited margin of increase for the overall budget set aside for the development of academic staff, as reflected in 20% for the duration of the year 2000 to 2020 (Afejuku, 2021). In affirmation, the 7th participant also asserts that through his five years as a lecturer there has not been any salary increment until recently when the government increased lecturers' salary with an insignificant amount and in spite of the increment, there is a lack of transparency as to what exactly was the amount added due to several ministerial protocols.

(b). Corruption

Table 5.4 below presents this theme and links it to initial and new literature. This means that the provisions of this theme either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with the below literatures which are discussed further down the section.

Theme 2	Sub theme (B)	Link to initial literature	New literature
Experiencing Sectoral Challenges	Corruption	Ekundayo and Ajayi (2009)	(Ezenwa, and Osayi, 2013), Asiyai, (2015), Heyneman, (2011), Ademola, Simeon and Kingsley, (2012) and Altbach, (2005). Raheemson, (2016).

Table 5. 4: Theme 2, Sub theme “B”

Research conducted annually by Transparency international and Gottingen university revealed that Nigeria ranked highest in the corruption perception index study for 1996, 1997 and 2000 (Ezenwa, and Osayi, 2013). In my study, six participants explained that this is applicable to them who work in the public university sector. Experiences of corruption appear in different kinds. Not only that, it has become a normal phenomenon in the entire Nigerian society from the government to corporate organizations to the common man; It is not only applicable in the university education sector alone, it also cuts across other sectors hence it has become difficult to prevent it. Findings by Raheemson, (2016) provide thus: ‘many Nigerians encounter bribery on a daily basis because of the following reasons: they were encouraged by a perceived culture of greed, a culture of impunity, a culture of impropriety and a culture of no accountability’. Participants in my study mentioned their experiences of corrupt practices in their university including nepotism, bribery, tribalism and political inferences and interference. Many participants have had prejudiced experiences where their fellow lecturers were given preferential treatments based upon personal relationship with people in higher positions. For

example, the 3rd participant shared her experience; she was interested in heading her department following an internal opening, she has spent 11 years in the university and met all the person's specifications for the post; however due to politics, she was told that there was a directive to assign the post to another candidate. This came as an instruction from a higher authority which influenced the university senate against her despite meeting all the requirements, she felt very disappointed to have been working in such a corrupt system. Following the research by Ekundayo and Ajayi (2009, p.345), they provide thus: 'It has been observed that universities these days are not totally free from the hand of politics outside the university system. Government of the day, most especially in the state-owned universities, interfere a lot in terms of selection and choice of the chief executive, deans, departmental heads, directors of programmes and above all the selection of vice-chancellors'. This is in confirmation to the plight of the 3rd participant who was vying to be a departmental head.

Many of the participants in my study also described bias and favouritism within the university management. As factors of corruption, their concern regarding this is that lecturers are not being given equal opportunity by the university management in terms of promotion whereas recruitment and selection are subjected to tribal differences or favouritisms. This applies to indigenes of the particular state where the university is situated (Rivers state) as they have always been given preference over non indigenes. This makes it difficult progressing in a lecturing career within the public university sector for those who do not have connection and are not indigene of the state where they work. This is termed man-know-man, a term most participants use in describing favouritism in the system based on who you know (nepotism). From a general perspective, promotion is problematic and subjected to tribal consideration in the public sector at large. This is because policy implementation is at the mercy or directives of those in higher positions within the ministries hence when things are not done in accordance with their terms and directives, the person concerned may be displaced. Therefore, for the fear of this, this level of corruption such as tribalistic consideration for recruitment and promotion

thrives in public sector organizations (Ademola, Simeon and Kingsley, 2012) and becomes a criterion for promotion yet not formalized.

One participant provided information about the influence or interference of the university management in such corrupt practices. He said lecturers contract out their jobs in exchange for part of their salaries and in some cases such arrangements are made with the management. There is always someone in such position that serves as a channel. This happens in situations where they require flexibility to go about their other jobs or businesses whereas there is no such rule anywhere that one can sell out his or her job to another in exchange for money. There is a belief that this does not happen if the people involved do not have some sort of personal connection with people at top management positions who cover their back and approve such arrangements. In a similar vein, there are also other situations where to secure a lecturing job, people bribe those in charge of the recruitment process and in exchange for employment, the beneficiary agrees to offer part of their monthly salary or their body to service the agreement. According to Asiyai, (2015), ‘an issue that seems to be threatening the attainment of quality education in Nigerian universities is corruption. Corruption tends to be dragging the university education system in the country to public ridicule’. Asiyai, (2015) provides different categories of which corruption in Nigerian university exists. This includes financial corruption, admission related corruption, sexual corruption, teaching, learning and research related corruption. These are all spoken about by my participants. While Asiyai, (2015) findings attributed causes of these corrupt practices as greed, society moral decadence, pressure from colleagues, get rich quick syndrome, lack of fear of God, Poor management, desire to pass exam without working hard, on the other hand, Heyneman, (2011) provides that in terms of corruption for personal gain, the categories of victim and perpetrators are generally students and faculty as the faculty members uses their position as lecturers to exploit students for sexual or other favours. The 3rd Participant mention having witnessed a case of sexual

harassment among a female student and a lecturer and when this was investigated the lady confirmed to have been using that to sort for higher grades in.

Two of the participants I interviewed also explained that they were favoured in the process of their lecturing employment. Although to them it was seen as a favour other than corruption. Ademola, Simeon and Kingsley, (2012) and Altbach, (2005) confirmed this to have influenced university management and administration giving opportunities to those who do not meet teaching qualification while rendering many qualified youths unemployed. Following this, the organizational practices, procedures, and core values can be questionable on such grounds where recruitment procedures and defined structures are not being adhered to and in some cases can be termed corruption if proven contrary. Asiyai, (2015) described the application of core values in academic activities in Nigerian university sector and submitted that core values such as justice and fairness are jettisoned for corrupt recruitment practices rendering its related activities and processes short chained (Asiyai, 2015, p161).

Furthermore, the 9th participant who is medical personnel explained being employed based on such ground. He was practicing in the health sector when he got called and was given an opportunity to co-establish the university medical school and commence teaching. During my interview with him, he submitted that he did not do any interview meaning there was no formal recruitment procedures met. My investigation shows that he was close to someone who knew him to have so much experience and have the capabilities to contribute to the university's medical school. This is partly because the medical program had just been introduced into the university then. To him, it was like a favour factor to get such a stress free opportunity and position without any rigorous recruitment process whereas on the contrary, many other participants in my study reveal that they went through some stringent recruitment screening processes from face to face interview to technical tests and online exams of which their employment was not subject to any personal connection, personal contact for favours, nepotism or tribal consideration.

On the part of students, studying hard is very difficult across Nigerian universities. Students engage in corrupt practices just to ensure that they pass their exams and are given higher grades. Knowing this, some lecturers provide avenues for payments in order to give students the grade they want. This is termed “sorting” in the Nigerian parlance. Many Of my participants mentioned that sorting is common across Nigerian universities. Although none affirm to have been personally involved however, Asiyai, (2015, p161), confirm that it is a category of corruption in Nigerian public universities involving student-lecturer bribery for getting higher grades. Similarly, Raheemson, (2016 p148) provides that lecturers ““offer” help to some lazy students who resort to “sorting” (finding ways of purchasing high and unmerited grade mark from him to enhance their grades at the final examination)”.

(c). Poor Working Condition, Facilities, and Environment

Table 5.5 below presents this theme and link it to initial and new literature. The provisions of this theme either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with the below literatures which are discussed further down the section.

Theme 2	Sub Theme (C)	Link to initial literature	New literature
Experiencing Sectoral Challenges	poor working condition, facilities and environment	Adamu, 2011, Adeniyi, 2001, Ekundayo and Ajayi, 2009	Udu and Nkwede, (2014), Adewole, 2020, James, (2017), Saint Hartnett and Strassner, (2003, p.15)

Table 5. 5: Theme 2, Sub theme “C”

In Nigerian public universities, work and study is carried out in an environment that is mostly not conducive. Teaching and learning is said to be carried out under a high level of negligence on the part of the government in terms of providing a conducive work environment

and facilities to aid lecturers in teaching. There is a common perception among the participants that those in political positions, heads of ministries and policy makers who make decisions affecting the education sector and through which government resources for educational development are channelled are the ones behind the poor infrastructure and work conditions in the university. The belief is that they do not use those funds assigned to develop the universities infrastructures for the purpose they were assigned. When asked why, some participants said that the rich and those in political positions who make decisions and influence the education sector have their children in foreign universities abroad therefore put no interest in the infrastructural development and working conditions of the university education in Nigeria as their children do not share in the poor learning experiences and environment. This is confirmed by the study of Udu and Nkwede, (2014).

For the lecturers I interviewed in this study, working in the university sector is associated with issues of Poor work environments, such as dilapidated buildings, lack of office space, lack of learning facilities, and overcrowded student population in the classroom. It is not uncommon to see that much literature conducted within Nigerian university sector addresses several of these problems and seeks for educational and infrastructural development for example Adewole, 2020, Adamu, 2011, Adeniyi, 2001, Ekundayo and Ajayi, 2009. The 7th participant felt perplexed about the work environment and offered that he has been teaching in a classroom that should contain about 100 students, but the school allocates that class to more than 300 students and as a result, there is a lot of congestion, and some lecturers don't care about what they teach because they just pass the message and whether the students grab it or not they are not bothered. Adewole, (2020) confirmed the dwindling situations lecturers experience in Nigerian universities saying that the massive dilapidation of facilities and resources in the universities leave lecturers to work in overcrowded classrooms, inadequate office space and lack research facilities to work with. According to Adewole 2020, he said: 'the conditions in most classrooms are less conducive to learning compared to what they used

to be 40 or 50 years ago. School buildings are dilapidated, equipment is out-dated and old fashioned, teaching resources are mainly blackboards with white chalks still being used, there are no improvements in teaching and learning, as teaching methods remain predominantly archaic'. He continued by saying a primary school teacher recently told me: "We still use blackboard and chalk up till now. The classroom environment is very poor. We sometimes have more than 200 pupils in a class. Some sit under the tree to receive lessons. The classrooms are already old and unpresentable. Most of the schools need renovation".

To show that infrastructural development is a problem in Nigerian universities, Lecturer's access to library equipment, research materials and classroom accommodation are grossly inadequate. Research shows that in Ebonyi State University before TETFund, the university was housed in three different annexes, inherited from existing secondary school premises in the state. Structures in these annexes were severely dilapidated and the University Management as at then, had to renovate the said annexes to a usable standard using internally generated Revenue which came from students' tuition fees (Udu and Nkwede, 2014). Findings in the study of Udu and Nkwede, (2014, p121) have revealed that the extent to which students are zealous for learning is determined by the amount and quality of resources and Infrastructures that are available to them. Based on this, the availability and adequacy of physical infrastructure, are not just necessary if minimum standard is to be attained but also an essential part of a conducive learning environment. If facilities do affect the learning process and lecturers, school administrators, planners and policymakers are not taking this into account, it may frustrate the outcome of the process.

It is also not uncommon to see lecturers in Nigerian public universities working and not getting what they worked for in terms of specific financial benefits not being implemented or partially implemented; pensions and salaries are examples. The implementation of lecturers' pension policy is not far-fetched. It is one of the things that comes with working in a Nigerian

public university sector which is seen to be negligible by the government. The participants in my study evidenced cases of lecturers who are retirees who have nothing to fall back on after their many years of work in the public university sector. Some of the participants, while making reference to this fact, also imply taking caution to invest wisely and having multiple sources of revenue so as not to be dependent on the illusory pension which they claimed that past retirees most likely don't receive. According to James, (2017), there has been some hindrances in the implementation of the contributory pension scheme in Nigerian public universities which is a major concern to lecturers. These hindrances were attributed to many factors among which is the non-remittance by the government and the inability of the government to fund the guaranteed minimum pension (GMP). In terms of salary condition, every employment contract entails therein the details of financial remuneration, the process and time of payment and if there will be any perceived default, this will always be communicated across to the employees since salary is seen to be one basic and most important consideration for employment. With reference to Nigerian public universities, payment of salaries is one of the defaulted work conditions which lecturers have negatively experienced. They are sometimes paid very late. They have experiences where salaries are not paid for some months going against their contract of employment. According to Saint Hartnett and Strassner, (2003, p.15), There is a “destabilizing influence of unionized staff militancy over salary issues”. One of their common experiences in relation to this is the outcome of the delayed payment which often leads to ASUU calling for strike. The 1st participant stated that sometimes he does not get paid for over four months and this always leads to ASUU strikes.

(d). Lack of development

Table 5.6 below presents this theme and link it to initial and new literature. The provisions of this theme either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with the below literatures which are discussed further down the section.

Theme 2	Sub Theme (D)	Link to initial literature	New literature
Experiencing Sectoral Challenges	Lack of development	Adewole, (2020) Saint, Hartnett and Strassner, (2003), Subair, Okotoni and Adebakin, (2012),	Clark, (2001), Adeyanju, and Olatunji, (2021)

Table 5. 6: Theme 2, Sub theme “D”

Educational underdevelopment is an implication of many factors inherent in Nigerian public universities. In this study, nine participants identified characteristics of working in a less developed system where there is lack of curricular advancement and where lecturers’ skill development is lacking. They complained that the curriculum they use in their universities are outdated and that their universities make little or no use of technology to advance the teaching and learning process. This is not university specific as participants generalized their experiences with outdated curriculum implying that it is the state of reality across all public universities in the country. This is evident in the declining trend established in the second chapter of this study hence driving the system backward in terms of development when compared to other developed countries. The third Participant hilariously submitted that the method of teaching and learning is archaic as they are still using chalk and blackboard in the classroom. He also mentioned that lecturers are not expose to things that improve their intellect because they still do things in the same old ways and manner as it was many years ago. For example, they use the same lesson plan for several years without any addition or subtraction

and this does not expose lecturers to doing research and updating themselves to meet up with global trends and development in academia.

Following participants assertion, development in relation to tertiary teaching and learning in Nigeria public universities has two dimensions: curricula and pedagogy. In other words this can be regarded as the content of what is being taught or learnt and method of delivery. Saint, Hartnett and Strassner, (2003, p12) revealed that, the university curriculum in Nigeria lacks quality. Being in a global economy where knowledge is competitive and updated regularly, curricular development cannot be undermined. Researchers have acknowledged that university education need to develop their curricula every two to three years so as to allow the content of what is being taught to reflect the ever-changing frontiers of scientific knowledge. In pedagogical terms, Clark, (2001) provided that there should be an extended involvement and high rate of participation in knowledge acquisition such that intensifies academic capabilities, motivation and interest among both lecturers and students. In the case of Nigerian universities, because there is no development in teaching and learning as a result of the non-applicability of quality standard in traditional curricular requirement, this can be said to have contributed to the gap in labour market assessment and absorption of low-quality graduates in Nigeria. Today measuring up with global advancement and competitive performance as well as industrial development indicates that Nigeria is far behind due to educational underdevelopment most of which is pedagogical. This is evidenced in the weak technological skill and development in Nigeria therefore requires changes in learning and teaching such that will increase the curricular emphasis from staff teaching to student learning as it is in today's 21st century education.

Following from the need to develop both curricula and pedagogy. The 2nd participant emphasized that the system is adamant to old processes, no advancement in technology, curriculum is old fashioned, and it is frustrating because the same curriculum that he was being taught about 13years ago is the same thing most universities allow lecturers to teach till today.

Consequently, for lecturers, working in such an environment is less challenging implying lack of research and development. Evidence from this study has shown that academics are motivated by challenging tasks, this was the reason the 8th and 9th participants in this study attributed for quitting work in the hospital environment and chose a lecturing career because of the lack of variety being on a job that does not challenge them to learn new things. In this case, the challenge of doing consistent research can be considered an avenue for lecturers to become pioneers for developing new frontiers for scientific knowledge thereby helping in spotting curricular areas that need changes and development. However, when such avenues are lacking in an institution of higher learning, it causes a downward trend in intellectual development and can lead to a decline in intellectual property of a nation while job satisfaction of those involved is inevitable because they are not developing themselves. One participant's comment shows that there is no evidence of appropriate academic review and curricular implementations in his university due to the ambiguous processes and procedures involved in curricular review in public universities.

On the other hand, their working in a public university is embedded with lots of pedagogical inefficiency in terms of the government's provision of resources such as well-equipped laboratories/facilities for faculties that require them as well as skills development for lecturers required technologies. One of the participants spoke about many other lecturers not knowing how to use a computer properly such that if there were any need to teach remotely during the pandemic they wouldn't be able to. The fact remains that they are not exposed to working with advanced technology. lecturers' skill development is quite low as one of the lagging areas in the public education sector. Participants show that they are not exposed to technological advancement in the area of basic technology used for teaching and learning in spite of non-provision by the government. Based on their stories, it is true that the blame is on the government for not providing advanced teaching and learning equipment and avenue required to develop education.

On the contrary, two participants in my study who work in the same university provided that curricular development and the use of technology is gradually returning to the universities. They both cited an example of having ICT as part of the university curriculum and having implemented recruitment procedures to be carried out via computer. However, it can be said that providing such peripheral computing development is still very much deficient in tackling the inefficiencies of educational and pedagogical development in the country without proper use of artificial intelligence required for today's competitive technological world. On the contrary, Adewole, (2020) opine that; 'there are no improvements in teaching and learning, as teaching methods remain predominantly archaic. No application of computer technologies except in affluent private schools'. On the other hand, an earlier study by Saint, Hartnett and Strassner (2003) provided thus 'The present government has aggressively addressed these identified problems through a series of policy changes. For example, It has returned to university senates the power (previously held by the NUC) to determine curricula and to initiate or terminate courses. It has also established reference points for quality improvements and begun to develop academic benchmarks based on demonstrated student competencies. Government statements also promote the need for university service and partnerships with the private sector'. This provision shows that technological and curricular development is still not taken seriously by the government in developing Nigeria's tertiary education considering the year of their publication (2003) and the current educational status as revealed by this theme.

Theme 3: Experiencing Flexibility of processes and work

Table 5.7 below presents this theme and link it to initial and new literature. The provisions of this theme either confirms (fully or partially) or disagrees with the below literatures which are discussed further down the section.

Theme 3	Sub Theme	Link to initial literature	New literature
Experiencing Flexibility of processes and work	Employment process	None	Akpan, (2016)
	work flexibility	None	Omotoso, (2013)

Table 5. 7: Theme 3, Sub theme “a” and “b”

This theme demonstrates that there is a flexible process of employment for those who work in the public universities in Nigeria. This is an experiential factor that is identified across both public universities under study amidst the several challenges lecturers spoke about during my interview with them. Some of my participants were happy at how flexible and easy their employment journey was, having been employed without going through a difficult recruitment process, procedures, or requirements. They also enjoy freedom from strict work accountability which places them in a position of less supervision and enable them have time for themselves. This makes their work process flexible. In addition one of the participant mentioned having work-life-balance because of the less demanding work pattern and timings. She is a female participant who asserts that she is able to balance her lecturing job with family.

The 7th Participant described how flexible employment experience can be in public universities using his story as a pointer. It is the fact that he was employed as a lecturer without going through a formal recruitment process and interviews. He narrated that the university vice chancellor promised all first-class graduate automatic lecturing employment which he was among the beneficiaries. According to him, he ended up not getting the job under the said VC’s tenure in office however, he was still granted the job upon that promise after obtaining his master’s degree without needing to go through the hassle of interviews and other required formal employment processes. Although this could have been considered prejudice whereby his getting employed as a lecturer was principally influenced for other reasons, however, it can

be argued that such employment initiated under the capacity of the vice chancellor was a way of rewarding excellence as much as a recruitment strategy to attract the best candidates for lecturing in the university. From the participants' perspective, he was happy to have such an opportunity claiming that getting a lecturing job in the public university is flexible and the process was friendly for him. On the contrary, a normal lecturing candidate would not have had such privilege. This flexibility may therefore be questionable as to whether the vice chancellor is vested with such duty to award jobs based on academic performance of graduating students and whether it is a sustainable practice that do not tamper with the university's recruitment procedures or policies.

According to Akpan, (2016), recently employment into Nigerian public universities has proven to have been mostly tailored towards sentiment and intense discrimination instead of merit which is indicative in this study. The implication from the 7th participant's story reveals that the employment process was rather flexible because it gave him certain employment advantages over others based on his high academic performance, many lecturing candidates did not go through formal recruitment procedures in circumstances where they have a close relationship with someone in a position of influence or power and where they show high performance or experience in the field they are being recruited for. Nonetheless, concerned participants consider it a flexible system, while some are employed through such influence, others who go through the formal recruitment process because they reported not having such contact or connection still find the interviews easy and are able to pass their interviews and get employed. Many of them rather proved to have been employed based on their own personal effort. For example, the first participant mentioned that the process was smooth. He said that he applied for the job and studied hard for the interview when he was eventually called. The interview was in two stages; oral and computer based. According to him, he went through both stages and passed without any resort to personal connection or contact.

Although these differing employment experiences, proves that there is evidence of underlying disparity and non-uniformity of recruitment procedures as revealed through the different participant recruitment experiences. This can be proven to have led to less qualified lecturers than expected and leading to low quality delivery in the university despite being a positive experience to those participants involved. Akpan, (2016, p5) Provided that quality service delivery and employee's performance in the Nigerian public university sector has not been attainable because there is neither established nor strict adherence to realistic, applicable recruitment and selection policy and procedures. According to him: 'Uniform human resource management policy and procedures should be formulated to guide actions and decisions of public universities management, especially, with regards to employee recruitment and selection' (Akpan, 2016, p5). It is also not uncommon that when recruitment and selection exercise is monitored it enhances quality service delivery. In this regard, Akpan, (2016) says that Nigerian public universities adopted a more regulated recruitment about two decades ago, where staff employment was subject to procedures that first identified areas of need which were sent by heads of departments to the university registrar. In the process, job advertisements were widely made and after sorting the applications, they were sent to relevant departmental heads who determined which candidates to be shortlisted and thereafter sends it back to the registrar for further approval and subsequent appointment after the vice chancellor has also been consulted. Following these, appointment was also dependent on the approval by the university council and upon going through these processes, whoever scales through the various stages is given a probation to start work for a period of one year. After this period, successful candidates are expected to attend a regularization interview and upon further success would have their appointment regularized and finally confirmed to be a full-time lecturer within their second or third year in the university. This sequential processes in staff recruitment into public universities helped to sift and select quality candidates without applying any unjust and differing procedures from one candidate to the other as reflected in this study. It is arguable as

to whether this can be regarded as been flexible. Akpan, (2016) opine that people who were willing to work in the public university sector those days were very few due to phobia of humiliation following the rigorous processes. He submitted; thus, 'Interestingly, many of those who passed through the employment procedure of public universities were individuals who could beat their chest to proclaim a high level of competence in the discharge duties'.

Two participants who work in the same university also reveal that lecturing in their university is enjoyable because of the low level of supervision involved. They are free from strict work accountability which they believe is common in other careers. Being an academic staff, they are not being supervised on a frequent basis and this makes accountability level very low. According to the 9th participant, there are times when he dedicates more effort towards teaching or other things and vice versa and he is not answerable to any boss. This is because the university is very democratic such that nobody can wake up tomorrow to sack you unless involved in gross misconduct. In support of this, a respected academic, Prof Ladipo Adamolekun, while commenting on the systemic failure of public institutions in Nigeria have submitted that public sector institutions such as higher institutions of learning lack transparency, accountability and professional ethics leading to the difficulty in achieving quality enhancement and performance (Omotoso, 2013). This is no exception regarding the public universities under this study as the cases of flexibility reveal that there is a very low level of accountability within public universities.

Furthermore, as part of this theme, one of the female participants also indicated how lecturing enables her to have a work life balance because it is not so demanding. Part of the things she experienced as a female lecturer is a flexible work pattern that allows her time for her family unlike many white-collar jobs which she has turned down for the reason of flexibility. It is therefore deduced that while work flexibility in this study positively influences the participants, on the other hand, the employment flexibility is an indication of recruitment bias, nepotism and ununiform recruitment procedures adopted by Nigerian public universities.

Determining Lecturers' Job Satisfaction

How lecturers' professional motive and experiences inform their satisfaction:

All twelve participants of this study described circumstances that shapes and affects their satisfaction having worked in the public university sector for more than five years. While their personal experiences which are based on realities around their academic career indicates that they are dissatisfied, all twelve participants show that their satisfaction emanates from the professional motive they conceived for entering the teaching profession. This is how: Their predominant professional motivation is the reason they chose lecturing as a profession or career path, the main purpose of which was to impact lives. Interview from all twelve participants evidenced that they derive job satisfaction following their impact on students. Seeing students they have impacted over the years succeed is their greatest source of satisfaction. There is consistency regarding this feedback across all participant's stories which shows that they cherished students' success and are satisfied by this. For example, the first participant opined that he derives satisfaction seeing students that passed through him become something (successful) in future. The 2nd participant also made an assertion that when he sees his students doing so well because of the part he played as a lecturer to contribute to their advancement in life makes him feel so elated and satisfied. This is consistent from the 3rd through to the 12th participants and this partly confirmed the study of Ladebo, (2005) which was carried out in Nigeria and Cockburn (2000) which was carried out in England regarding student teachers and Watt et al (2012) across Australia, United States, Germany, and Norway. Watt et al (2012) submitted that altruistic-type motivation is the teaching career motive that related most strongly to teachers' job satisfaction. Although they all have few intrinsic motivating elements but, in this study, teaching career choice is majorly altruistically motivated. Significantly, this means that student success is a predominant antecedent to lecturer's job satisfaction as it is the product of lecturers' impact (their professional motivation). It positively influences their satisfaction as

opposed to the several negative sectoral challenges experienced by lecturers in Nigerian university sector.

There is a suggestion that lecturers in this sector are not happy nor satisfied with the education system which leaves them displeased following bad conditions of work and the overwhelming systemic issues of corruption, salary issues, underdevelopment, and poor working conditions and environment all of which emerged during my analysis. Locke (1976 p1304) described job satisfaction as a ‘pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences’. In this study, participants’ emotions were not quite pleasant as they appraised and described negativities associated with working in a public university sector in Nigeria. They show high level of disappointment in the education system yet do not show any sign of exiting or leaving their job. Like the 2nd participant mentioned, he is concerned about the education system. He expresses much dissatisfaction about how the education system works in Nigeria and assert that the whole system is frustrating due to poor structure as nothing seems to be working well. He believes that things are not the way it should be when compared to overseas universities; ranging from payment to promotion to retirement scheme among many others. These are some of the factors that cause him dissatisfaction.

Despite the high level of dissatisfaction experienced in the system, they find it difficult to quit considering the economic conditions such as high unemployment rate in the country (reference to the story of the second participant). This confirms the study of Ladebo, (2005) who found out that teaching professionals with higher qualifications or degrees in Nigeria are into teaching because of prevalent unemployment in the country which is an indication of feeling of apathy – a feeling of indifference regardless of job dissatisfaction (Ladebo, 2005). This is similar in China according to the study of Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014) who provided that in China, people stay put in a low paid job like teaching not because they love it but because they choose to stay in the career in the face of a stringent job market. While Johnshrud and Rosser (2002) stated that salary has never been shown to be the staff primary influence for their

decision to leave or stay, Ping et al. (2010) study on academic staff in China came up with the findings that overall job satisfaction levels were close to average, with salary and benefits receiving the lowest level of satisfaction which in reference to this study is a bit similar in the sense that participants laid more dissatisfying emphasis on salary issues compared to any other theme.

Similarly in the current study, lecturers are found to show the highest concern for pay dissatisfaction, many of whom mention reasons why they venture into multiple sources of income alongside their lecturing job and which may also be the cause why financial corruption is dominant in the sector. Their primary reason is that the career on its own is not lucrative; they are not being paid well hence they use the flexible opportunity to seek other sources of income. In fact, financial concerns is one of the repeated and primary bones of contention complained about by the participants and the most frequent reason they mentioned for being dissatisfied in this study. This do not confirm the findings of Ladebo (2005) who found out that teachers' satisfaction was characterized by satisfaction with pay and benefits, and intrinsic satisfaction.

With satisfaction regarding pay, it can be observed that this has high significance in Nigerian education due to the issues of inadequate funding and poor salary structure. One of the literatures that support this fact is Arikewuyo, (2009, p17), who reported that Nigeria spends a little amount of its GDP on education averaging 1.1% whereas smaller neighbouring countries like Ghana spends 3.6%, Kenya spends 6.2%, and Zimbabwe spends 9.5%. With this fact, lecturers' pay dissatisfaction has a strong bearing on the lack of financial benefits they get due to lack of funding. On the other hand, Herzberg's theory (1959) is of the opinion that pay as a hygiene factor is not a satisfier and cannot improve job satisfaction. While this is partly true in this study because lecturers derive dissatisfaction from their poor salary rate, it however tends to lose its meaning following the findings within the theme – "salary issues". This is because if it is not a satisfier, majority of the lecturers wouldn't go about looking for other

sources of income to augment their poor salaries and even get involved in sorting (bribery). In a nutshell, It can therefore be submitted that in this study, job satisfaction is a product of lecturers' professional motivation whereas their experiences working in the public university sector is dissatisfying as a result of issues of salary, corruption, lack of development and poor working conditions, infrastructure and environment.

Linking Findings to the Theoretical Context

The theories that underpin this study are career development theory and job satisfaction theory. With reference to John Holland Theory of Career Choice (1959), career choice is seen to be influenced by or subjected to six personality traits that include: investigative/thinkers, artistic/creators, social/helpers, enterprising/persuaders, conventional/organizers, and realistic/doers. John Holland identified careers that fall under each of the categories. He identifies teachers and lecturers to fall under the category of people who have a social or helpers personality trait. This is because as teachers, their personality type helps them to engage and train people to impact them while creating lasting relationships. In addition, teachers have good communication skills and are happy to support people (Holland 1959).

Following this study, the passion to impact the lives of students which stood out as lecturers' predominant motive and source of satisfaction emerged from the combination of some meaning clusters which tend to identify with Holland's social/helpers personality traits in lecturers. This includes desiring to help in making a social impact, passion to teach (train people), love for teaching, academic assistance and helping students succeed. the 6th participant's story of why he chose the teaching profession is attributed to his passion for teaching which according to him, he does with ease because he discovered the abilities at a very young age. The 3rd participant also shared her story about how her passion for teaching was realized because she has had the skills from her many years of being a Sunday school

teacher in the church. In addition, she asserts that she had always liked to gather people to let them know of current happenings such that will keep them informed as one of the skills Holland's theory is hinged on for social/helpers.

On the other hand, Herzberg's theory (1959) is of the opinion that pay as a hygiene factor is not a satisfier whereby its absence brings job dissatisfaction, but its presence cannot improve job satisfaction. In my study, this seems to be in support of my findings because all participants experience poor salary issues partly because of poor remuneration which is one of the sectoral challenges experienced and which Herzberg says its absence brings dissatisfaction. In this study, lecturers are dissatisfied about their salaries not being equitable. However, from another perspective, there tend to be an ambiguity in the applicability of the theory in relation to this study in the sense that if good pay is not a satisfier as Herzberg says (i.e lecturers would not derive satisfaction from good pay whether present or not), majority of the lecturers wouldn't go searching for other sources of income to augment their poor salaries and also get involved in bribery (sorting). The reason behind their quest for extra financial sources could be because it brings them satisfaction. The hygiene factors of Herzberg theory therefore call for more debate as its applicability seem ambiguous irrespective of context. In a nutshell, this study reveal that job satisfaction is a product of lecturers' professional motivation other than their experiences because their experiences working in the public university sector is dissatisfying.

Summary

This chapter interpreted and discussed my findings based on the data I gathered during my interview. It linked them to existing literature and theory. The first set of my interpretation in this chapter deals with the first research question; the predominant teaching motivation of professional lecturers in Nigerian public universities. While the second part discussed what lecturers experience working in Nigerian public universities. Linking both elements to

lecturers' job satisfaction, revealed that lecturer's job satisfaction is influenced by their professional motivation (passion to impact on students) whereas lecturers' lived experiences bring them dissatisfaction due to sectoral challenges they experience. Both parts were presented with their emerging themes.

Chapter Six

Conclusion And Recommendation

Introduction

My study is centred around the career experiences of a group of teaching professionals (lecturers) from two public universities in southern Nigeria. Their stories developed into a foundation for knowledge surrounding people's motive for choosing a teaching career in Nigeria and what they experience working in a public university education sector. The purpose was to understand the sources of their (dis)satisfaction. It is from the description that emerged from their stories that I based my conclusion about the sources of lecturers' job (dis)satisfaction which includes implications and recommendation for practice. Referring back to the early chapters of my project, I stated the significance of this study outlining that it will be of benefit to certain group of people including public universities' management, lecturers, university students, government and educational authorities such as the NUC, academic researchers and policy formulators in human resources management. Lecturers' stories as expressed through their lived experiences and current realities has always been the foundation upon which I explored the phenomenon in this study, and it is also the source of my revised conceptual framework, implication, and recommendation. Because lecturers are the custodians of knowledge in university organizations, they are the central or focal group through which the university achieves its purpose as a knowledge organization. Therefore, investigating their professional motivation and what they experience within their work setting in Nigeria to determine their job satisfaction was essentially at the core of this research. I was interested in researching this unexplored and disjointed void in scholarly literature to make meaning of it and by doing so initiated three research questions not just to aid me in following procedures but to search and discover meaning or themes. Now that the themes from participants' stories have been developed and interpreted, this chapter will answer the research questions and their

contribution to knowledge, establish practical implications of the findings, outline the limitation of the study, reconceptualize a new framework and make a case for future research.

Answering the research questions and their specific contribution to previous studies/ knowledge

In this section, I answer the research questions linking them to academic literature and how they contribute to knowledge.

Research Question 1: What is the predominant teaching motivation of professional lecturers in Nigerian public universities?

i. Passion to make an impact on students

This reinforces findings that the primary reason why people choose a teaching profession is for altruistic purpose. This entails the passion to make an impact in the lives of people. It means that lecturers' primary career goal is to indirectly contribute to society through the students they impart. This partly confirms the studies of Watt et al, (2012, p,12) whose findings provides that "The highest rated motivations for the choice of a teaching career were consistently of intrinsic value; perceived teaching ability, the desire to make a social contribution, to work with children/adolescents, and having had positive prior teaching and learning experiences". in essence, intrinsic value according to Watt et al, (2012) is a combination of altruistic and intrinsic factors. Although the context and methodology of the study differ from this study as Watt et al (2012) was conducted across four western countries including Australia, United States, Germany, and Norway. The context of my study was in Nigeria therefore there may be some cultural implication on people's motive for choosing a teaching career and by implication the satisfaction they derive from it. However, Watt et al (2012, p14) stated that "the fact that contextual country features did not produce greatly

different patterns of motivations raises interesting questions such as whether there are “core” motivations shared by those who are attracted to a teaching career, or whether certain personality types are more likely to choose teaching”. This can be considered a perspective for further/future research.

ii. Absence of personal/career expectation

This finding entails that job characteristics are a significant factor in career choice. Although this is a secondary motive some participants gave for deciding to quit their previous career for lecturing. it confirms the study of Priyadharshini, and Robinson-Pant, (2000, p100) who investigated why people change career to teach and came up with the finding that ‘dissatisfaction with the nature of their previous career’ was the most cited factor that made them decide to quit their previous career to teach. On the contrary, this disagrees with one of the elements in the findings of Anghel, (2000) which explained that: “not being comfortable in a field where one was trained is the least and insignificant reason people give for abandoning their previous job and taking a teaching career”. In this regard, my study confirmed that two medical professionals changed their career to lecturing because they felt their previous job was monotonous, having a repetitive work routine. This was far from their career expectation and as a result they desired another career that would give them the opportunity to learn new things which they found in lecturing. More so, from my finding, there is an implication that job variety is a basic employee’s expectation needed for their satisfaction which was lacking in their previous employment. This is in line with the Hackman and Oldham Job characteristics model (1974) and also the study of Katsikea (2011) whose findings suggest that job characteristics involving variety positively influences job satisfaction.

Research Question 2: What are lecturers, experiences within a Nigerian public university?

i. Salary issues

Lecturers experience salary issues. This finding entails that poor salary rate, strike actions resulting from salary negotiations, payment delays and pay disparity are predominant problems experienced by lecturers in Nigerian public universities. It confirms many literatures within my study context including Victor, and Babatunde, (2014) where 60% of the respondents agreed that there was a lack of provision of regular payment of salary and other remuneration. On the contrary, it contradicts Adelabu, (2005) whose findings suggest that lecturers' salary in Nigeria has been improved despite being carried out before the aforementioned study.

ii. Corruption

Lecturers experience corruption in varied situations. This is a new finding. It confirms and advances knowledge that corruption is a major problem and experience across many public sectors in Nigeria [(Raheemson, (2016), Asiyai, (2015) Ezenwa, and Osayi, (2013)]. This includes financial corruption (bribery), tribalism, nepotism, and prejudice especially during recruitment. It confirms the study of Akpan, (2016) that employment into public universities and other public offices is not free from tribalism and nepotism.

iii. Lack of development

Lecturers have experience of using outdated and underdeveloped curricular. This add to literature around pedagogical (curricular) and technical development being lacking in public universities in Nigeria – [Subair, Okotoni and Adebakin, (2012), Saint, Hartnett, and Strassner, (2003)]. It supports the findings of Subair, Okotoni and Adebakin, (2012) that the quality of technological infrastructure in selected Nigerian universities are in a poor state. This is because

there are no facilities for effective practical learning for the students in most courses, especially in the universities of Technology that require a lot of intensive training in terms of students' usage of hi-tech equipment. It also contributes to the findings of Saint, Hartnett, and Strassner, (2003) who found that there is a high level of curricular underdevelopment in Nigerian higher education as it lack quality and regular reviews.

iv. Poor working condition, facilities, and environment

This contribute to the study of James, (2017) who confirm that some work conditions are negligibly poor and partially implemented such as promotion and pension scheme (James, 2017). It also points out the unconducive environment for teaching and learning in Nigerian universities by confirming the study of Adewole, (2020) who provide thus: 'The condition in most classroom is less conducive to learning compared to what they used to be 40 or 50 years ago. School buildings are dilapidated, equipment is out-dated and old fashioned, teaching resources are mainly blackboards with white chalks still being used, there are no improvements in teaching and learning, as teaching methods remain predominantly archaic'.

v. Employment process and work flexibility

This finding is controversial as the majority of lecturers' story under this theme entails that they find it advantageous to have benefited from a flexible and favourable recruitment process despite not being in conformity with uniform recruiting procedures. This contribute to the study of (Akpan, 2016) who outlined that 'recruitment and selection practices in Nigerian public universities is devoid of concomitant staff quality checks especially at the verge of recruitment and selection exercise' because of lack of uniform recruitment and selection procedures.

Research Question 3: Does lecturers' professional motivation and experiences inform their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction?

Firstly, lecturers' professional motive influences their satisfaction, as they all report to be altruistically motivated through their impact on students. This confirms and contributes to Watt et al (2012). They assert that 'the motive that related most strongly to high career satisfaction included the altruistic-type motivations' (Watt et al 2012 p.2). In terms of its contribution to knowledge or practice, Heinz, (2013) provided that teachers' professional motive can determine the strategy to ensure their satisfaction therefore, this particular finding can guide university recruitment initiative in recruiting lecturers that are altruistically motivated, as a way of managing lecturers' job satisfaction in the future.

Secondly, lecturers' experiences working in the public university sector informs their dissatisfaction following the negative sectoral challenges. This includes issues of salary, corruption, lack of development and poor working condition, facilities, and environment. It therefore births a totally new factor (corruption) as a determinant of lecturers' job dissatisfaction – a contribution that is unrelated to any of Egbule, (2003) and Umaru and Ombugus (2017).

Essentially, it can be said to extend Egbule's twelve determinants of lecturers' job satisfaction which include pay/salary, job security, achievement/recognition, opportunities for promotion, boss leadership style/attitude, physical work environment, staff development programmes, academic freedom, responsibility at work, supervision, university autonomy. Also Umaru and Ombugus' six determinants which includes interpersonal relations, regular salary payment, promotion opportunities, work environment, attainment of work goals, opportunity to growth and development. In other words, elements of lecturers' career experiences as depicted in this study cut across some significant satisfaction determinants by Egbule, (2003) and Ombugus, for example salary and physical work environment are common across the three studies.

The Revised Conceptual Framework

The Initial conceptual framework was presented in chapter two which displayed the various ideas following reviewed literature. In this chapter, the revised conceptual framework is based on my findings. As displayed in figure 6.1, it maintains the same structure but now contains the various themes that emerged during my analysis with additional or new insight. The structure is in three parts: lecturing Professional motive, experiences working in a public university in Nigeria and career expectations. The subsequent paragraphs explain the first two and their influence on lecturers' job (dis)satisfaction as displayed with the arrows in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6. 1: The revised conceptual framework

Lecturing Professional motive and job satisfaction:

Following figure 6.1, the primary and predominant motivation lecturers attributed to their career choice is to make an impact in students' lives; this is displayed in green text on the left side of the diagram. This is an altruistic motive revealing that people who find themselves in a teaching profession in Nigeria choose to contribute to the society by impacting in students and ensuring that they are successful in their endeavours. In this regard, lecturers assert that they have passion in imparting knowledge through teaching with the aim of making social, moral and academic impact. This is considered the predominant motive why participants choose to be in the career. On the other hand, few participants showed some external but secondary reasons why they went into teaching. This is as a result of the absence of their personal or career expectations which includes unemployment, poverty and job variety (left hand side of the diagram). It was devastating for them such that led to considering teaching even though it was initially not their choice of career. It rather was chosen out of compromise. Also, part of this extrinsic reasons are financial lack and change of job as a result of lacking job variety in previous employment and desiring to face new challenges. All things considered, from figure 6.1, job satisfaction is influenced or informed by lecturers' professional motive (in green arrow), a phenomenon that all participants attested to having impacted students' lives and therefore feels satisfied only because of that.

This part of the conceptualization has some empirical significance or validation from the teacher career-choice literature of Watt et al (2012) and Heinz (2013). Reference to these studies are the factors Influencing teaching choice (FIT-Choice model). This model represents some psychological mechanisms called socialization influences which are involved in the choice of a teaching career and of which people attach value. This includes intrinsic value, personal utility value and social utility value. Personal utility value is identified with job security, time for family, and job transferability. Social utility values include shaping the future

of children/adolescents by making a social contribution, enhancing social equity and love working with children and adolescents. Regarding this revised conceptualization, the social utility value factors resemble the altruistic factor (in green) as lecturers described the passion to make an impact in students' lives and contributing to their success been the reason for their choice of the lecturing career and which brings them satisfaction. Furthermore, under the personal utility construct, job transferability can be linked to the reasons cited for job variety in my study which occur because of the absence of career expectation causing people to transfer from their initial career (medical) into lecturing. This was the case with the 9th and 10th participants, and it is considered an extrinsic motivation although have no influence on their job satisfaction.

Although "time for family" did not emerge as a reason for lecturing career in my study which is reflected as part of the fit choice model under personal utility value however, "time for family" was cited as part of work flexibility as a theme deduced out of lecturers' experiences (shown on the right-hand side of the conceptual framework). In a similar vein, job security under the personal utility value is likeable to the fear for unemployment as an element in my study where people are not willing to quit their lecturing career despite the sectoral challenges. This means that they believe lecturing is secure for them. These two factors (time for family and job security) are therefore seen to be inherent in lecturers' career experiences rather than an underlying factor for their career choice.

According to Wat et al, (2012, p2), The FIT-Choice framework taps both the altruistic-type motive, personally utilitarian motive, intrinsic motive, ability-related beliefs, and individuals' perceptions about the reward aspects of the teaching profession, and all contains a measure of job satisfaction. Out of these items, only altruistic-type motive, and ability-related beliefs (indicating that lecturers show relative skills and passion for teaching) stands out in this study. Out of these two, participants only link their job satisfaction to the altruistic-type motive which is impacting students' lives.

Although there appears to be significant differences between my study and Watt et al 2012 and Heinz 2013. First are the methodological differences and second is cultural and contextual differences. Although the model was developed and validated in an Australian context however, Watt et al, 2012 carried out their study across international context in Australia, United States, Germany, and Norway and they used a quantitative methodology. On the other hand, Heinz 2013 adopted it in an Irish second-level education with a quantitative methodology. My study is purely qualitative, and my context was in Nigerian tertiary education which provides a new insight to compliment the forgoing western centric studies and opens a debate within a Nigerian context.

Experiences working in a public University and Job Dissatisfaction

While lecturers' impact on students' lives brings them satisfaction, on the other hand, the systemic experiences they go through working in the public university sector are the reasons they cited for their dissatisfaction. These experiences include the first conceptual category; experiencing sectorial challenges (texts in red) which emphasizes salary issues, lack of development, corruption and poor working conditions, facilities, and policies. With salary issues, participants show disappointment and dissatisfaction as they experience poor salary rate, delays in salary payment as well as high level of disparity in lecturers' pay when compared to those in other public sectors including an incessant strike action resulting from the payment issues (Afejuku, 2021). In terms of lack of development, they find themselves working in an environment that lacks basic technical infrastructures including curricular underdevelopment which they also cited to influence their dissatisfaction. For corruption the participants complained about experiencing tribalistic treatment, nepotism, prejudice, and financial bribery. Adewole, (2020) and Yetunde, (2018) confirms that these challenges are facing public education in Nigeria. Also, ten of the participants have the perception that there is much

flexibility in the university recruitment process and five felt that it is flexible working as a lecturer in a Nigerian public university. This adds to (Akpan, 2016). Moreover, many of the themes that emerged based on lecturers' experiences support Herzberg's hygiene factors as it relates to job dissatisfaction. Herzberg provides that the absence or lack of hygiene factors in a job (pay, work environment/condition, company policy, supervision) brings about job dissatisfaction.

Lecturers' Career Expectations

Following figure 6.1, under this theme are four sub themes that explain lecturers' quest for a positive change in the public education sector in Nigeria. First is Increased pay, funding and pension, second is government support in relation to research and development, third is Improving work environment and work conditions, and lastly Implement policies & develop education.

Implications for practice and Recommendations

While I explored lecturers' professional motivation and experiences working in Nigerian public university sector to determine their satisfaction, it was deduced that they derive satisfaction from making an impact on students which is relative to their predominant reason for choosing the profession - To impact lives. This imply that job satisfaction is altruistically motivated not based on tangible professional achievement from one's job but from the level of influence and footprint one leaves in the lives of their students. Contributing to such footprint and having such influence can otherwise be seen as an intangible achievement to them. By implication, this means that lecturers would like to be in a position of direct influence in order to derive satisfaction in their career. It is therefore recommended on this note that public university lecturers be given an avenue where they can have a direct influence on students as

well as in decision making. This may require the establishment of a university-wide mentorship programme that enable a one-on-one mentorship access with lecturers (especially to poor performing students). Also for them to have a say in making vital decisions that give them a sense of involvement and influence. This will create an enabling environment for direct impact and will in turn influence high students' performance both academically and in society. On the part of the government and authorities hiring lecturers and public universities' management, the implication for this finding is considered in the light of lecturers' recruitment initiatives; it is advised to align the university recruitment strategy to the reason people give for deciding to become a teaching professional – to impact lives. Therefore, lecturer's recruitment initiative should employ such persons who are altruistically motivated. This will help in effectively managing lecturers' job satisfaction and retention in the future. On the other hand, it will help to easily align organizational goals and staff's career needs/motivation as part of the university's academic development strategy.

The second finding (theme) under lecturers' professional motive is the absence of personal and career expectations. The reason why many people go into a lecturing career is not only centred around impacting lives. This finding revealed that there is a high rate of unemployment in Nigeria. To two other medical participants, lack of previous job variety and learning opportunity was evident. Implication from the latter entrust universities to design academic job characteristics that are particularly suitable for different professional domains. On the other hand, the former has an implication to implement an employment initiative for unemployed university graduates in order to curb the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria.

Furthermore, lecturers' job dissatisfaction is significant in this study due to their experience of several sectoral negativities, for example poor salary, payment delays, strike actions, disparity in pay, corruption, poor work environment such as dilapidated building, overcrowded classrooms, lack of office space and lack of teaching equipment among others. It implies that all things being equal, turnover rate would be high considering the high

dissatisfaction lecturers expressed working in this sector. Again, due to the high rate of unemployment (33.3% according to Bloomberg, 2021 statistics) they do not seem to quit the career despite negative experiences. I recommend that the government set up an employment/business support scheme and opportunities for young graduates who could not secure a job after graduation. It is obvious from this study that people alter their life's plan based on career challenges. Those that never intended to go into teaching now find themselves lecturing because they do not have any other choice nor control over the high unemployment rate.

Furthermore, as aforementioned, my findings when examining lecturers' experience revealed that the public university system and work environment involves an array of negative experiences ranging from salary issues to corruption; tribalistic treatment, nepotism, lack of development, poor working conditions, facilities, and environment and feeling of a worker-friendly and flexible recruitment process. First, regarding salary issues, evidence showed that poor salary rate and delay in payment are a consistent occurrence. This has on several occasions resulted in an unresolved financial concern and dispute among academic staff union of universities (ASUU) and the government and has in turn led to strike actions lasting for so many months of which many people including researchers attribute to poor education funding by the government. This issue of salary has also revealed a corresponding effect on the level of financial corruption prevalent in the education sector as evidenced in this study. It implies that the government is turning a deaf ear and blind eyes to the issues and plights of the academia. It is recommended that the government through its education agencies such as the NUC should with immediate effect, manage these issues throughout the country before it gets worst. In 1962, the government of Nigeria established the National Universities Commission (NUC) as an advisory agency aim at promoting quality higher education in the country and looking into all education affairs, therefore the NUC need to review all pay related policies, practices and conditions in regard to university education in Nigeria and come to term with

payment policies that will equally be favourable to both academic staff as well as the government using other public sectors' salaries as a benchmark. The legislative arm of the government on the other hand, and those who are responsible for reviewing budgetary expenditures should benchmark educational budget against international standards such as those recommended by the United Nations to curb some of these issues. Last but not the least, the ministry of education through whom the education budget is disbursed also needs to identify bottlenecks to salary payments and strictly monitor the process through, with a mechanism in all state's ministry of education and responsible financial institutions. Doing this will help to promote checks and balance any gap found to ensure that late payment of salaries and budgetary misappropriation are resolved.

Lack of pedagogical development and poor work environment and infrastructure are common problems experienced by lecturers working in public education. My study indicates that some infrastructures in public universities are dilapidated leaving room for overcrowded lecture halls, unavailability of office space and lack of technological teaching aid and using outdated academic curriculum. All these imply that teaching and learning is poor and the quality of graduates that are produced from such poor system cannot meet global competitiveness nor solve overarching industrial problems when pushed into the labour market. I therefore recommend that the government have a major responsibility to ensure that the country's education is developed by providing necessary infrastructures, the government also need to implement strict sanctions for individuals, educational bodies and other entities found misappropriating government funds that are meant for developing education whereas in terms of curricular development, the NUC, university senate and other responsible bodies should implement a periodic curricular review and update accordingly while consistently monitoring its progress. One way of monitoring progress or KPI is by carrying out random and unannounced academic inspections involving departments, lecturers, academic staff and students to check for curricular updates ensuring that they are implemented at all levels.

Students' interviews will be helpful in tracking scope and quality of lecture delivery and while this is carried out, the process should be automated in order to be corrupt free because corruption is a major problem in the country.

This phenomenological study offered views on corruption as part of lecturers' experience working in the sector. Lecturers complained about experiencing nepotism, tribalism both in the administrative processes, among top management personnel and lecturers. They explained to me how the criteria for recruiting certain positions and promotion in the university is based on indigenous differences whereby those from the state are being given preference over non indigenes. Also, favouritism and prejudice for promotion; being subject to influences from people in high positions as experienced by the 8th participant as well as "sorting" among lecturers and students and other financial bribery which many participants mentioned. This implies that there is no sound monitoring system in place for academic and administrative affairs across public universities in the country. As a society, It is everybody's responsibility to promote administrative justice ensuring that everything is done meritoriously to avoid tribalistic treatment nonetheless, this needs government sanction to get those who are involved in these corrupt practices prosecuted. I recommend that a whistle blowing mechanism be implemented for corrupt practices and secondly; to have a decentralized law enforcement agency responsible for sectorial crime across the country for easy implementation just like the economic and financial crime commission (EFCC) is designated for financial and economic crimes.

Lastly, the feeling of recruitment process flexibility is another theme that emerged in this research. Lecturers explained that their employment experiences were very smooth. While this was the only positive theme emerging from what they experienced and indicative of a good recruitment process and friendly work environment, many of their employment experiences were seen to go against justified recruitment processes and uniform procedures. This implies that the public university system have a malfunctioning HR department and recruiting

initiative. It is therefore recommended that a uniform and bias-free recruitment be implemented, monitored and controlled. The university's human resource department or recruiting agencies is at the centre of this equation, they can find responsibility to give equal opportunity to all job candidates.

Implication of lecturers' job satisfaction on educational development

Job satisfaction is the central idea around which this research revolves. Findings from this study reveal that lecturers' professional motive is to impact lives. This informs their satisfaction because it aligns to what gives them satisfaction; especially as they see themselves contributing to students' success. This contrasts with what they experience within their career setting (in public university sector) as they complained about various systemic negativities causing them dissatisfaction. As the core human resources in the university sector, experiencing salary issues, corruption and lack of pedagogical and infrastructural development may have a resulting effect on lecturers' commitment and their intention to leave. Ingersoll (2001' p501) stated that in the teaching profession, '...the overall amount of turnover accounted for by retirement is relatively minor when compared to that associated with other factors, such as teacher job dissatisfaction and teachers pursuing better jobs or other careers. Central to these issues are the implication of poor educational management and governance which is currently affecting productivity across Nigerian education (example students failure rate is on the high side) and in turn have stalled educational development. To improve on lecturers' job satisfaction while achieving educational development on the other hand, it is recommended that the education governing body such as the NUC needs to review and revolutionize the different areas that are of concern to lecturers being the core educational resource. This shows how important lecturers/teachers are to bring about both national and educational development if they are satisfied with their job. According to Watt et al. (2012, p.1) "teaching appears to be

an occupation considered central to a country's development and well-being" therefore the importance of lecturers' job satisfaction to educational and economic development cannot be overemphasized.

Financial Implications of the study and the need to finance Nigerian education

Significantly, all four sub themes under lecturers' negative experiences working in the public university sector; Experiencing Sectoral Challenges appear to be money centric as they are all financially influenced. Therefore, the importance of financial role both in ensuring job satisfaction and development in Nigerian universities cannot be overemphasized. To buttress this point, issues of finance are found to be common across many of the experiential themes and was emphasized upon by all the participants, this includes issues of salary, corruption, Lack of development, Poor working condition, facilities and environment. Upon this note, the study confirms that pay is one of the most important things that lecturers show very keen interest about in their career. The absence of reasonable pay rate in the university sector can be attributed to the reason why lecturers engage in financial corruption otherwise known as "sorting". It is also considered one of the key elements which participants are devastated about during my interview with them. Furthermore, pay rise and increased funding are also among what they advocate for and expect the government to do for them. This is not only exclusive to lecturers but also non-academic staff and administrators since the poor salary rate applies to all career or job roles across the university sector. On the other hand, lack of development, poor work conditions and environment and corruption all emerged as having high financial significance on the education sector. This finding therefore makes it imperative for the government (both federal and states) to urgently review their policies and bring education to the top of their priorities in terms of funding and development which will require financing. A lesson to be learned from Finland who focused on and built their education sector for almost

half a century and now appears as one of the world's leading benchmarks as their school system is now 100% funded. In addition, the national policies on education should therefore have emphasis on meeting the yearnings and expectations of lecturers as outlined under theme 4 of this study, Desiring positive changes in public education. This includes; Increase pay, funding and pension, government support (in relation to research and development), Improving work environment/condition and Implement policies and develop education.

Limitations and critique to the research

1. Methodological limitation:

This study adopts a phenomenological research design because it is an experiential enquiry. I later realized that the study does not conform strictly to its principles in the following way: My study was about the experiences of lecturers working in a public university sector and their professional motivation for choosing a teaching career. My questions to them were semi-structured and descriptive (sample found in the appendix). I noticed most responses were not personalized to them and were less of a description probably due to follow-up questions. Regarding experiences, responses were majorly pejorative, and generic based on happenings around the education sector. In some cases, some participants were more comfortable referring to other people's experience. This is not to say that the answers were irrelevant to my research questions, it rather means that phenomenological reduction being one of the basic elements of my methodology loses its sense. In essence they did not detach themselves from the experiences of others in the same situation/position. Following Depraz, (1999), he described phenomenological reduction as a first-person experience of consciousness whereby the person's experiences are isolated from the environment. This may have impacted on my analysis although may have no significant effect on the result. In a nutshell, Moustakas (1994,

p90) says that ‘despite practice, some entities are simply not bracketable as there are lived experiences that are so severe, intense and telling, some things that are not ingrained and some people so attached to each other that clear openness or pure consciousness is virtually an impossibility’.

2. Value Laden:

It must be acknowledged that qualitative research may be value laden whereby reflexivity is hard to meet especially during data interpretation and discussion. As far as this study is concerned, my background as a Nigerian and experiences of the study context as a former student of one of the universities under study can be said to have influenced my understanding and interpretation of the data. However, this gave me the opportunity to probe for underlying values, beliefs, and assumptions as seen in the reflexivity section of chapter three. To remove researcher bias, I employed a vigorous peer-review, supervisor’s review, external audit (guidance) and participants also reviewed their individual interview transcript. Probing my believes, values or interpretation this way made it difficult to influence the research process and interpretation of findings (Choy, 2014).

3. Sample size and generalization:

Being a qualitative and phenomenological study, my study does not have a large sample size. Although the sample size was appropriate for the research design, it is possible that it may not be a true representation of all lecturers in Nigerian public universities and therefore generalization may be inappropriate. However, the number of participants ensured depth over breadth. Also, saturation can be said to have been reached judging from the consistency/similarity in my participants’ responses.

4. Scarcity of research in relation to teaching professional motivation in Nigeria

This study lack sufficient materials in relation to teaching professional motivation as one of the areas of this research. This is because there are no sufficient studies conducted within the context of Nigeria to determine what motivates teachers and lecturers to the teaching profession. However, due to the dearth of research, majority of the literature in this regard where taken from other context for example Anghel, (2020), Heinz (2015), Wong, Tang, and Cheng, (2014), Bruinsma, and Jansen (2010), DeLong, (1987). It is however understandable that there may be systemic differences considering the different context (countries), but this may only have little or no effect on individual disposition and personality-driven decision when it comes to professional motivation.

Contribution to knowledge and practice

This study contributes to the study of Egbule, (2003) and Umaru and Ombugus (2017) by extending the sources of job (dis)satisfaction of Nigerian lecturers and fill a methodological gap in determining lecturers' job satisfaction within the Nigerian higher education literature. The former study shows an improving trend in the expressed level of job satisfaction of lecturers especially in the Nigerian public universities while the later did not show how the Identified factors affect lecturers' satisfaction. It follows that the improvement identified by the former invalidates autonomy as a factor for job satisfaction and this is also confirmed by the study of Umaru and Ombugus (2017). An implication of this is that there is a lack of involvement of lecturers in decision making and in things that affects their job. While this can be a problem, it is one of the causes of lecturers' job satisfaction within government owned universities in the country (Egbule, 2003). It is however imperative that autonomy as well as the work environment are the most cited contributing factors of dissatisfaction among lecturers in federal universities unlike state universities where only lack of autonomy is predominantly

the case. This brought about the argument that although all universities in Nigeria (whether federal, state, or private) have policy standards and programmes that are federally approved by the National Universities Commission (NUC) and are also controlled by them, however lecturers under the different university structures have differing factors of satisfaction from one another. This in general can be attributed to their differing experiences which may be sector specific.

Using the experiences of lecturers in the two public Universities of this study, This study was able to identify a new and entirely different factor or problem which is known to be affecting lecturers job satisfaction based on their experiences which Ebule (2003) and Umaru and Ombugus (2017) did not identify. This factor is known to be corruption. One of the major dissatisfying factors that has a devastating effect on lecturers and affects the integrity of the education system. This new finding from this study did not only expose the ills of the education system such as tribalistic treatment, nepotism and bribery, it also increases the scope of factors that other researchers like Egbugle (2003) and Umaru and Ombugus (2017) among others have attributed to lecturers (dis)satisfaction in Nigeria.

Following from the above, This study contributes to knowledge by extending the sources of job (dis)satisfaction of Nigerian lecturers and fill a methodological gap in determining lecturers' job satisfaction within the Nigerian higher education literature. It also highlights possible experiences and sectoral challenges that potential lecturers and teachers may come across therefore give a foresight of their career expectations.

The study contributes to HR practice by giving the universities a recruitment insight based on lecturers' predominant career motivation which will enable them to manage future lecturer's satisfaction by recruiting altruistically motivated candidates. It also identifies the experiences that influences whether people are likely to stay in the career or not. In this regard, Heinz, (2013, p1) Submitted that: 'The reasons that people give for deciding to become a

teacher are important considerations in designing recruitment strategies, and in identifying the sources of job satisfaction that influence whether people are likely to stay in the career’.

Recommendation for further research

This study-initiated conversations regarding lecturers’ professional motivation and lived experiences working in a public university in Nigeria. Although the finding is not an indication for a complete or absolute knowledge around the explored areas. It rather compels further research to solidify the evidence and to look into any gap or limitations found or other areas of concern to lecturers and the public university sector in Nigeria to have a better understanding and to make an informed decision career wise and for educational development purposes. It is therefore recommended that:

1. Further research should consider the lack of female participants in this study to design a more gender balanced sample size. This will help to understand gender differences regarding lecturers’ professional motivation and job satisfaction.
2. As a qualitative researcher, This study was limited to only 12 participants and therefore not suitable to generalize across all tertiary institutions in Nigeria therefore further research should utilize different quantitative methodologies with a large sample size so that generalization can be possible.
3. Due to the high controversy of salary issues and the concern for education funding in this study, it is recommended that further research be focused on the effects of educational budget on lecturers’ satisfaction and tertiary educational development in Nigeria.

My research has offered a foundation to encourage other researchers to seek further exploration into ways of developing the Nigerian education system as well as enhancing the teaching career.

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Appendix. 1 – Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

1. Study title and Researcher Details

Title: Professional motive and experiences working in a Nigerian public University: A determinant of Lecturers' Job satisfaction

Researcher's Detail:

Name: Tombari Ganago

Contact: Mobile; [REDACTED]

2. Invitation paragraph

This is to formally invite you to participate in the above-mentioned study which is to investigate the professional motive and experiences working in a Nigerian public University as a determinant of lecturers' job satisfaction. The interview for this study will take about 40-50 minutes to complete. It is made up of questions related to why you chose a lecturing career and your lived experiences as a lecturer in a Nigerian public University. This study is ethically approved by the University of the west of Scotland and the confidentiality of all information taken from you will be ensued.

3. What is the purpose of the study?

The study's main purpose is to investigate lecturers' professional motive and what they experience in Nigerian public universities in other to determine their job satisfaction. The study employs a phenomenological method to explore the personal stories and lived experiences of lecturers regarding their career in two Nigerian public universities through face-to-face interviews. Considering their predominant career motive and experiences, this study will determine whether the motive and experiences they encounter influences their satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to participate because you fit the profile of the population being studied; that is, you are a lecturer in one of the tertiary institutions selected for this study.

5. Do I have to take part?

Participation is voluntary and you may decide to withdraw at any time. Your decision is highly respected.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

There is no risk associated with participating in this study. Also, the study is subject to ethical approval from the university of the west of Scotland.

7. Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All information provided will be kept strictly confidential. Steps will be taken to ensure that participants cannot be identified through the report. No questions with the potential of exposing your identity such as your name will be asked.

8. What will happen to the results of the research study?

The result of the study is for academic purpose as well as helping organizations concerned to make informed decisions based on the findings. All section with the potential of exposing your name will be represented with an alphabet especially in the direct quote in the data analysis chapter. Also all data collected will be destroyed after the study is finished, submitted and intended degree awarded.

9. Contact for Further Information

If you require more information on this study, you can contact Tombari Ganago on; [REDACTED]
email; [REDACTED]

Appendix 2. – Participants Consent Form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Introduction and Invitation:

My name is Tombari Ganago. I am a doctoral student at the University of the west of Scotland, London campus. I would like to invite you to participate in my study which is to investigate lecturers' professional motive and career experiences in a Nigerian public university aiming at determining their Job satisfaction.

Purpose of the study

The study's main purpose is to investigate lecturers' professional motive and what they experience in Nigerian public universities in other to determine their job satisfaction. The study employs a phenomenological method to explore the personal stories and lived experiences of lecturers regarding their career in two Nigerian public universities through face-to-face interviews. Considering their predominant career motive and experiences, this study will determine whether the motive and experiences they encounter influences their satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Procedure

If you agree to participate in my research, I will conduct an interview with you at the time and location of your choice. The questions will involve things about your reason for choosing a teaching profession and your experiences as a lecturer in one of the public universities in Nigeria as a way of determining your job satisfaction. The interview should last for about 40 to 50 minutes.

With your permission I will audiotape the interview. The recording is to accurately record your response and will be used for transcription. If you wish not to continue with the interview, you can stop at any time. The audio record will be deleted, and transcripts destroyed after the entire research is completed.

Risk and Discomfort

There is no risk associated with participating in this study. Also, the study is subject to ethical approval from the university of the west of Scotland.

Confidentiality

All information provided will be kept strictly confidential. Steps will be taken to ensure that participants cannot be identified through the report. Nothing that has the potential of exposing your identity such as your name will be written in the report.

Rights

Participation in research is completely voluntary. You may decide to withdraw at any time. Your decision is highly respected.

Further Information

If you require more information on this study, you can contact me on; [REDACTED]
email; [REDACTED]

Consent

You will be given a copy of this form to keep for your own record

I have read and understood all the information written in this form.

If you wish to participate in this study, please sign below

Participant's name

Participant's Signature

Date

Appendix 3. – Semi-structured Interview Questions

Interview Questions	Link to Research Question
Can you describe your career experiences prior to lecturing?	1
What drove you into a teaching profession? What was your reason for becoming a lecturer?	1
What are the experiences you can think of at the time you were given the lecturing job? For example, think about the recruitment processes you went through and how you were able to get the job.	2
As a lecturer can you describe the things you experience working in a public university sector?	2
Is there anything you think stands out about your experiences in your university?	2
Now, what do you feel about the profession? Do you feel passionate about lecturing considering all the experiences you have spoken about? Why?	1 & 2
Please can you describe the things you find satisfying from your experiences as a lecturer in the university where you teach?	3
Describe the things you find dissatisfying based on your experiences as a lecturer.	3
Considering what motivated you into lecturing, do you feel you are satisfied or dissatisfied? Why? Overall, if you are to compare, which one would you say you are more satisfied or dissatisfied with: The reason that motivated you into teaching OR the various experiences you spoke about? Please give reasons for your answer.	3
What would you suggest can be done to better your professional experience and enhance your job satisfaction as a lecturer? Think about all you have told me.	Recommendation

Appendix4. – Consent email to the Universities of study

REQUEST FOR AUTORIZATION TO CARRY OUT A RESEARCH STUDY IN YOUR UNIVERSITY

Dear Sir/Ma,

My name is Ganago Tombari. I am currently studying for a Doctorate degree in Business Administration with the University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom. My research topic centres on “Professional motive and experiences working in a Nigerian public University: A determinant of Lecturers’ Job satisfaction”.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the reason why lecturers choose the profession and their experiences in a Nigerian public university in order to determine their job satisfaction. The study will involve a face-to-face interview to take information from participants.

This study covers two tertiary institutions in Southern Nigeria of which your university is part. My sample frame will cover only six (6) academic staff members (lecturers) for each of these institutions.

In order to undertake this study, I am seeking your permission to collect interview data in your institution. My study requires that the interview be recorded for transcription purposes and by doing so, I will duly observe all ethical procedures and respect the confidentiality of respondents and the university during and after the data collection process.

I hereby request your Authorization to carry out the above-mentioned study in your University and will be glad to share my findings with the University for academic purposes.

I will appreciate if my request is granted as I await your response.

Regards,

Tombari Ganago.

April 16, 2019.

Appendix 5. – Unstructured Coding and theming process

Codes (subject of experiences) Level 4	Theme Level 3	Theme Level 2	Conceptual Category Level 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor salary • Insufficient pay • Payment delay • Poor salary leading to strike • poor salary compared to other careers 	Poor salary	Salary Issues	Experiencing Sectoral/Systemic Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • receiving low pay compared to doctors, bankers and nurses • Pay bias b/w lecturers and politicians 	pay disparity		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business ventures to boost salary • Diversifying into other career • working as a freelance lecturer for more pay • into other income sources (cryptocurrency) 	Diversifying into other sources of income		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sorting (Bribery) • The administration is corrupt • Two-way (lecturer-student) bribery 	Bribery and corruption	Corruption	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal network job favouritism • Prejudiced/nepotistic promotion • Politicking high positions 	Nepotism		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tribalism • Tribalistic recruitment • Politicking leadership positions 	Tribalism		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor promotion scheme • Promotion bureaucracy • No promotion 	Poor promotion	Bad working condition, environment and policy	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • consistent Strike from bad working conditions and policy • Unrealistic government policies • Poor pension scheme • Pension is delayed 	Bad condition and policy		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor working environment • Poor office /infrastructure • Overcrowded classroom • No good equipment in lab • Library is outdated 	Poor work environment		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of teaching development • lack of technology • No technological development of lecturers • No intellectual development(training) • Using outdated curricular • Lack of curricular development • Poor educational standard • The education system is bad • Poor educational structure and payment <u>critiqued opinion</u> • curriculum is developing • current curricula include ICT 	Poor curricular/structural development	Lack of development	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor funding for education • education budget is low 	Poor Funding		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible work pattern • have time for other engagements • Have time for family • Have time to do business • supervision and accountability is flexible • Job security over low pay 	Work flexibility	Flexibility	Experiencing flexibility of processes and work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smooth employment experience • interview process was simple • interview was rigorous • employment is based on recommendation • getting job without an interview (nepotism) 	Employment process flexibility		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government should fund education • lecturers need to be supported for research and development • Government should increase Lecturers' salary • Government should review education policies 		Expectations from the government	Desiring positive changes in Public education
Codes (subject of Professional Motivation) Level 4	Theme Level 3	Theme Level 2	Conceptual Category Level 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imparting knowledge • To Impact students • To make a social impact • The desire to impact • For moral impact • To Impact knowledge • To enlighten people • To render academic assistance 	Making impact		Passion to make an impact in Students
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passion to teach • Love for teaching • Sunday school teaching inspiration 	Passion for teaching		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idleness • Poverty • Frustration from unemployment • Repetitive nature of previous job (medical) 	Absence of personal and career expectation		Absence of personal and career expectation

Appendix 6 – Colour coding process

T: Sir how long have you been lecturing?

C: I've been lecturing for the past 5 years

T: Wow that's nice

C: Yeah

T: Sir, can you describe your career experiences prior to lecturing?

C: Well, I wasn't doing anything actually before I went into teaching I was idle which as a matter of fact not the best for anyone but that was where I found myself so I had to cease the lecturing opportunity when it came. So when I went into teaching even though I can't say the experience has been excellent at least to some extent it's been good because I really loved teaching and reaching out to people through teaching also

T: Do you mean it wasn't a conscious decision to go into the career path?

C: Well, I would say yes and No. yes in the sense that I didn't intent to be a lecturer right from time. You know when people choose courses right from secondary school, I never thought I would be interested in teaching someday. And then I said No because you know someone cannot force a job or career on you against your will so in that sense I consciously made the decision

T: Ok, I understand,

so can you tell me what actually drove your interest, I mean like what were you wishing to achieve?

C: Ok, If I say my love for teaching it will be an understatement, actually my love to impact in people, knowledge wise and morally. In terms of what I wanted to achieve, well, I believe everyone has a career goal and I would say eehm I would say teaching is a career that most people go into because they want to impart knowledge and in one way or the other impact the lives of the younger generation too so irrespective of the remuneration that comes with it, what I wanted to achieve is that sense of fulfilment and satisfaction knowing that I have impacted the lives of people

T: So in terms of being a public university lecturer for the past 5 years can you describe your experiences within the system

C: Aaah...there are so many oh. Where do I start from?

T: You can start from anywhere, ok for example, think about the recruitment processes you went through and how you were able to get the job and then while on the job what happens? what other things do you commonly experience. So those are the kind of things I'm talking about

C: Ok, just like I said earlier, I was jobless for some years even though I always try to develop myself. So I got the information that they are recruiting for entry lecturers more like starting with teaching assistant then after one year of probation you become a junior lecturer so I just decided to apply and try my luck. I applied and as time went by they called us for interview then followed by another oral interview then they shortlisted the names. I met the cut off figure and then I was called up. So the recruitment was that smooth, no too much of hassle

T: Woah, that was great. so was there any other thing you remember that played out during the recruitment?

C: Eeemh...you know in Nigeria anything happens, especially this our university system. In fact even in secondary schools, recruitment is always like the same. As in some people don't even go through the interview but when it's time you see them getting the job because they have connection but in my case, there was no man-know-man, I'm talking about my case oh, there was no man-know-man, no paying somebody. It was an open something because it was actually for both indigenes and none-indigenes, so it was just based on you being qualified, then the written and oral test if you can pass it. I think the cut off figure was 160 and I got exactly 160 then and that qualified me to have the job.

TG Tombari Ganago
5years experience

TG Tombari Ganago
Idleness/ joblessness

TG Tombari Ganago
Love for teaching

TG Tombari Ganago
No prior interest in lecturing

TG Tombari Ganago
Desire to make an impact

TG Tombari Ganago
Smooth recruitment/interview process

TG Tombari Ganago
nepotism during recruitment (corruption)

TG Tombari Ganago
job offer based on self-effort